

Magic Squares of Order 11 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025

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*The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=15857>*

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

*This work brings **dates** and **days of the year** 2025 in terms of magic squares of order 11 for the month of **June 2025**. 12 different types of magic squares of order 11 are considered. Most of them are based on **cornered**, **single-digit bordered** and **double-digit bordered** magic squares. In all these cases, the respective **magic rectangles** are of equal sums. There are 12 different types of magic squares of order 11 divided in two parts. The first part with **six** magic squares where, we have started directly with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. The second part is also with **six** different types having magic square of order 3. All the examples represents **dates** in two different ways, and the **days of the year** are represented by **magic sums**. For similar kind of work for the orders 3 to 10 refer author's work [31, 32, 33, 34].*

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1 Introduction

In the previous papers the author [31, 32, 33, 34] worked in representing **days** and **dates** of the year 2025 for the magic squares of orders 3 to 10. Let's call this kind of work as **reduced or less entries** magic squares. A short idea of this kind of representations for orders 3 to 5 can be seen in F. Gaspalou web-site [4], where the representations are in terms of magic sums. This work brings the results in general forms. In all the cases, the magic sum represents **days of the year** and **dates** are represented by some entries. The entries are non sequential positive or negative numbers. For more details refer author's work [31, 32, 33, 34].

This work brings **dates** and **days** of the year 2025 in terms of magic squares of order 11 for the months of **May to December, 2025**. It is based on **reduced entries** magic squares of order 11. In this work we have considered **twelve types of reduced entries** magic squares of order 11. These are based on **single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered** and **cornered** magic squares. These are divided in two parts. The first part with **six** different types of magic squares of order 11 are with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5, i.e., the work starts directly with magic squares of order 5. The second part also with **six** different types includes magic squares of order 3. For more details see the subsection below.

1.1 With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

- (i) The **first type** is a double-digit bordered magic square of order 11 embedded with cornered magic square of order 7. The internal magic square of order 7 contains a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . The external parte is with four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×7 .
- (ii) The **second type** is a cornered magic square of order 11, where the magic squares of order 9, 7 and 5 are in the left upper corner. The magic rectangles of orders 2×5 , 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length for each case.

- (ii) The **third type** is a cornered magic square of order 11 with double-digit bordered magic square of order 9 at the upper left corner embedded with a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×5 are of equal width and length. The two magic rectangles of orders 2×9 are also of equal width and length.
- (iv) The **forth type** is a cornered magic square of order 11 with single-digit bordered magic square of order 9 at the upper left corner embedded with cornered magic square of order 7. It contains two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 and a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. The magic rectangles of order 2×9 are also of equal width and length. Even though the magic square of order 9 is semi-magic at one diagonal, but it allows to write a magic square of order 11.
- (v) The **fifth type** is also a cornered magic square of order 11 with single-digit bordered magic square of order 7 at the upper left corner embedded with magic square of order 5. The magic square of order 9 is also a part of cornered magic square of order 11. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal sums in each case. Even though the magic square of order 7 is semi-magic but still we have orders 9 and 11 as magic squares.
- (vi) The **sixth type** is also a cornered magic square of order 11 with single-digit bordered magic square of order 9 at the upper left corner embedded with magic squares of orders 5 and 7. The magic square of order 5 is **pandiagonal**. The two magic rectangles of order 2×9 are of equal width and length. Even though the we have a semi-magic square at one diagonal of order 9, but still the order 11 is a magic square.

1.2 With Magic Square of Order 3

Considering magic square of order 3 requires little more attention on magic sum as in this case the entries are **fractional-type** to bring magic square of order 3. To avoid this, we can consider as multiple of 3 the sum of magic squares of order 3.

- (vii) The **seventh type** is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with double-digit magic squares of order 7. The internal part is a magic square of order 3. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×7 in each case are of equal width and length. To avoid fractional entries the difference between the sums of magic squares is considered as multiple of 4. Moreover, the magic sum of magic squares of order 3 is considered as multiple of 3, otherwise it gives decimal entries. In this case, an alternative approach based on width of magic rectangles is also suggested.
- (viii) The **eight type** is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 are at the left upper corner of magic square of order 11. In each case the magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×5 , 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length. Here also to avoid **fractional** and **decimal** entries the width of magic rectangles is considered multiples of 2 and magic sum of order 3 should be considered as multiple of 3.
- (ix) The **ninth type** is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where at upper left corner there is a double-digit bordered magic square of order 7 embedded with magic square of order 3. In this case the four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal width and length. It also contains a magic square of order 9. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and 2×9 are also of equal width and length in each case. Again here to avoid fractional values, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3.
- (x) The **tenth type** is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where at upper left corner there is a single-digit bordered magic square of order 9 embedded with double-digit bordered magic square of order 7. It also contains magic square of order 3. In this case the four

magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal width and length. The two magic rectangles of order 2×9 are also of equal width and length. Even though the magic square of order 9 is a semi-magic at one diagonal, but still we have order 11 as a magic square.

- (xi) The **eleventh type** is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where at upper left corner there is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 embedded with magic square of orders 3. In this case the two magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal width and length. The magic rectangles of order 2×9 are also of equal width and length. Even though the magic square of order 7 is **semi-magic** at one diagonal, but still we have order 11 as a magic square. In order to have order 7 as a magic square, we must have the condition $\frac{S}{5} = \frac{T}{7}$.
- (x) The **twelfth type** is a cornered magic square of order 11, where at upper left corner there is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with magic square of orders 3. In this case the two magic rectangles of order 2×9 are of equal width and length. Even though the magic square of order 9 is **semi-magic** at one diagonal, but still we have order 11 as a magic square. In order to have order 9 as a magic square, we must have the condition $\frac{S}{5} = \frac{T}{7} = \frac{L}{9}$.

The above twelve reduced entries magic squares are explained in with figures and entries in the subsection 2.1.

2 Magic Squares of Order 11

Below are three examples of examples of magic squares of order 11.

Example 2.1. *Let's consider a magic square of order 11*

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										671
	58	63	62	54	68	43	79	87	35	13	109	671
	65	61	57	55	67	78	44	25	97	104	18	671
	60	59	64	72	50	75	47	24	98	8	114	671
	56	52	53	73	71	38	84	89	33	3	119	671
	66	70	69	51	49	39	83	92	30	106	16	671
	81	37	40	76	77	74	42	29	93	5	117	671
	41	85	82	46	45	80	48	23	99	105	17	671
	21	96	91	27	88	90	22	86	28	108	14	671
	101	26	31	95	34	32	100	94	36	107	15	671
	120	9	118	116	121	11	19	115	12	10	20	671
	2	113	4	6	1	111	103	7	110	102	112	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

*It is a **cornered** magic squares, where in each case the magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×5 , 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal sums. It contains magic squares of orders 4, 5, 7 and 9 in the upper left corner.*

Example 2.2. Let's consider a magic square of order 11

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
	121	28	100	98	96	95	32	34	36	30	1	671
	119	21	78	74	76	41	40	38	80	101	3	671
	117	23	37	70	73	53	55	54	85	99	5	671
	115	25	39	50	60	65	58	72	83	97	7	671
	11	93	79	51	59	61	63	71	43	29	111	671
	13	91	77	66	64	57	62	56	45	31	109	671
	15	89	75	68	49	69	67	52	47	33	107	671
	17	87	42	48	46	81	82	84	44	35	105	671
	19	92	22	24	26	27	90	88	86	94	103	671
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

It is a well-known **single-digit bordered** magic square. The inner blocks are magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9.

Example 2.3. Let's consider a magic square of order 11

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										671
	112	92	9	21	14	29	34	121	117	105	17	671
	10	30	113	101	108	93	88	1	5	20	102	671
	100	22	85	79	42	55	44	50	72	94	28	671
	8	114	37	43	80	67	78	40	82	31	91	671
	107	15	49	73	62	63	58	76	46	24	98	671
	96	26	38	84	57	61	65	70	52	111	11	671
	35	87	66	56	64	59	60	69	53	25	97	671
	104	18	71	51	83	75	45	48	54	19	103	671
	6	116	81	41	39	47	77	74	68	120	2	671
	4	118	95	99	3	12	7	109	32	86	106	671
	89	33	27	23	119	110	115	13	90	36	16	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic squares where the magic rectangles of order 2×3 and 2×7 are of equal sums in each case. For more details on these kind of magic squares refer author's work [25, 26, 27, 28].

2.1 Reduced Entries: Magic Squares of Order 11

Below are **twelve** magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**. These are constructed inspired by Examples 2.1, 2.2 and 2.3. There are two partes. One with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 and another with magic square of order 3.

2.1.1 With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

Below are **six** magic square of order 11 with **reduced entries**. It included magic squares of order 5, 7 and 9. The magic square of order 5 is a **pandiagonal**.

Result 2.1. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

m-A24	A26	$A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45-5*m/2$	m-A40	m-A41	m-A42	m-A43	m-A44	m-A45	$2*T-5*m-A46-A25-A26$	$A24-T+5*m/2+A25+A46$
A25	A24	$7*m/2-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45$	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	$T-3*m/2-A46-A24-A25$	A46
$A18+A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-5*m/2$	$7*m/2-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23$	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	$7*m/2-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38$	$A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38-5*m/2$
m-A18	A18	$A8-A2+A7$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	A33	m-A33
m-A19	A19	$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A8$	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	$5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13$	$3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16$	A34	m-A34
m-A20	A20	$A7-A3+A5$	$A1-A6+A8$	$A2+A3-A7$	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	$A7-A2+A6$	A15	T-S-A15	A35	m-A35
m-A21	A21	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	$A3+A4-A5$	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A6$	A8	A16	T-S-A16	A36	m-A36
m-A22	A22	$T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13$	A10	$A7+A8+3*T/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13-3*S/2$	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	A37	m-A37
m-A23	A23	$A7-A10+A8-A14+A13$	T-S-A10	$S/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13-T/2$	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	A38	m-A38
$A24+A46-A39$	$7*m/2+A25+A46-A39-T$	$7*m/2-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32$	A27	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A39	$A39-A24-5*m+2*T-A25-2*A46$
$A39+T-5*m/2-A25-A46$	$2*T-5*m-A26-A25-A24-A46+A39$	$A27+A28+A29+A30+A31+A32-5*m/2$	m-A27	m-A28	m-A29	m-A30	m-A31	m-A32	$A26+5*m-2*T+2*A25+A24+2*A46-A39$	m-A39

Explanations:

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 embedded with **cornered** magic square of order 7. The internal magic square of order 7 contains a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5 and two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 . The external parte is with four equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×7 . Here S, T and R are the magic sums of orders 5, 7 and 11 respectively. Moreover, $R = T + m$, m is the width of the magic rectangle 2×7 .

Result 2.2. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	$2*L-5*T-A23-A7+2*S+2*A14+2*A10+2*A11+A16$	$4*T-L+A23+A7-2*S-2*A14-2*A10-2*A11-A16$	A37	R-L-A37
A8-A2+A7	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	L-T-A23	A23	$A37-R-4*T+A29-A30+7*L/2+A25-A24+5*S/2-A21-A20-2*A19-A22+A16+2*A15+2*A12-2*A18$	$2*R-9*L/2-A37+4*T-A29+A30-A25+A24-5*S/2+A21+A20+2*A19+A22-A16-2*A15-2*A12+2*A18$
$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A8$	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	$5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13$	$3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16$	L-T-A24	A24	$4*T+11*R/2-A38-A29-A41-A40+A30-A39-A42-A43-8*L-A25+A24-5*S/2+A21+A20+2*A19+A22-A16-2*A15-2*A12+2*A18-2*A37$	$2*A37-4*T-9*R/2+A38+A29+A41+A40-A30+A39+A42+A43+7*L+A25-A24+5*S/2-A21-A20-2*A19-A22+A16+2*A15+2*A12-2*A18$
$A7-A3+A5$	A1-A6+A8	$A2+A3-A7$	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	$A7-A2+A6$	A15	T-S-A15	L-T-A25	A25	A38	R-L-A38
S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16	$(13*T-7*L)/2+A25+A24+2*A23+A27+A26+A7-2*S-2*A14-2*A10-2*A11-A16$	$(9*L-15*T)/2-A25-A24-2*A23-A27-A26-A7+2*S+2*A14+2*A10+2*A11+A16$	A39	R-L-A39
$T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13$	A10	$A7+A8+3*(T-S)/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13$	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	L-T-A26	A26	A40	R-L-A40
$A7-A10+A8-A14+A13$	T-S-A10	$(S-T)/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13$	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	L-T-A27	A27	A41	R-L-A41
A18	$A18-2*A15-A12$	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A20-A19-A22+2*A15+A12-2*A18$	A19	A20	A21	A22	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$	A42	R-L-A42
L-T-A18	$L-T+2*A15+A12-A18$	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A20+A19+A22-2*A15-A12+2*A18$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2	A43	R-L-A43
A29	A30	$9*(R-L)/2-A36-A35-A33-A30-A34-A32-A31-A29$	A31	A32	A33	A34	A35	A36	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
R-L-A29	R-L-A30	$7*(L-R)/2+A36+A35+A33+A30+A34+A32+A31+A29$	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where the magic squares of order 9, 7 and 5 are in the left upper corner. The magic of orders 2×5 , 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal width and length for each order, i.e., $(T - S) \times (\frac{5}{2} \times (T - S))$, $(T - S) \times (\frac{7}{2} \times (T - S))$ and $(T - S) \times (\frac{9}{2} \times (T - S))$ respectively. The letters S, T, L and R represents the magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively.

Result 2.3. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

$(T-S)/2-A28$	A29	$A20+A21+A22+A23-2*(T-S)$	$(T-S)/2-A20$	$(T-S)/2-A21$	$(T-S)/2-A22$	$(T-S)/2-A23$	$(7*S-3*T)/2-A14-A19-A29$	$A28+2*T-3*S+A14+A19$	$5*S+A17-A8+A18+A32-A7+A39$	$R-T-5*S-A17+A8-A18-A32+A7-A39$
A30	A28	$5*(T-S)/2-A20-A21-A22-A23$	A20	A21	A22	A23	$(5*S-3*T)/2-A28-A14-A19$	$A14+A19-A30$	A39	R-T-A39
$A24+A25+A26+A27-2*(T-S)$	$5*(T-S)/2-A24-A25-A26-A27$	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4$	A3	A4	$5*(T-S)/2-A15-A16-A17-A18$	$A15+A16+A17+A18-2*(T-S)$	$9*(R-T)/2-A40-A43-A42-A41-A44-A45-2*A39-5*S-A17+A8-A18-A32+A7$	$7*(T-R)/2+2*A39+5*S+A17-A8+A18+A32-A7+A40+A43+A42+A41+A44+A45$
$(T-S)/2-A24$	A24	$A8-A2+A7$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7$	A6	$S-A1-A3-A4-A8$	A15	$(T-S)/2-A15$	A40	R-T-A40
$(T-S)/2-A25$	A25	$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8$	A7	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A8$	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	A16	$(T-S)/2-A16$	A41	R-T-A41
$(T-S)/2-A26$	A26	$A7-A3+A5$	$A1-A6+A8$	$A2+A3-A7$	$S-A1-A5-A7-A8$	$A7-A2+A6$	A17	$(T-S)/2-A17$	A42	R-T-A42
$(T-S)/2-A27$	A27	$S-A1-A4-A7-A8$	$A3+A4-A5$	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A6$	A8	A18	$(T-S)/2-A18$	A43	R-T-A43
$(7*S-3*T)/2-A14-A30-A29$	$(5*S-3*T)/2-A14-A28-A29$	$5*(T-S)/2-A10-A11-A12-A13$	A10	A11	A12	A13	$(3*T-7*S)/2+A28+2*A14+A19+A29$	$A29-A19+A30$	A44	R-T-A44
$2*T-3*S+A28+A14+A29$	A14	$A10+A11+A12+A13-2*(T-S)$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	$(T-S)/2-A12$	$(T-S)/2-A13$	A19	$3*S-T-A28-2*A14-A19-A29$	A45	R-T-A45
$R-6*T+A11+2*A10+A16+2*A15+A13+A12$	A32	$(7*R+3*T)/2-A38-A37-A35-A32-A36-A34-A33-A11-2*A10-A16-2*A15-A13-A12$	A33	A34	A35	a36	A37	A38	$(R-T)/2$	$5*T-4*R$
$5*T-A11-2*A10-A16-2*A15-A13-A12$	R-T-A32	$A38+A37+A35+A32+A36+A34+A33+A11+2*A10+A16+2*A15+A13+A12-5*(T+R)/2$	R-T-A33	R-T-A34	R-T-A35	R-T-A36	R-T-A37	R-T-A38	$5*T-4*R$	$(R-T)/2$

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11 with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 at the upper left corner embedded with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×5 are of equal width and length. The two magic

rectangles of orders 2×9 are also of equal width and length. The letter S, T and R represents the magic squares of orders 5, 9 and 11 respectively.

Result 2.4. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

L-T-A31	T-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18-L+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	R-3*T-A18+A25+A12-A33+A16+2*A15+2*A10+2*A11+2*A14+2*S-A7+A34-L+A41	3*T+A18-A25-A12+A33-A16-2*A15-2*A10-2*A11-2*A14-2*S+A7-A34-A41
L-T-A24	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	A13	T-S-A13	A24	A41	R-L-A41
L-T-A25	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	A14	T-S-A14	A25	3*T+7*R/2+A18-A25-A43-A46-A47-A44-A12+A33-A45-A42-7*L/2-A16-2*A15-2*A10-2*A11-2*A14-2*S+A7-A34-2*A41	A25+A43+A46+A47+A44+A12-A33+A45+A42+5*L/2+A16+2*A15+2*A10+2*A11+2*A14+2*S-A7+A34+2*A41-3*T-5*R/2-A18
L-T-A26	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	5*(T-S)/2-A16-A15-A14-A13	3*(S-T)/2+A13+A14+A15+A16	A26	A42	R-L-A42
L-T-A27	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	A15	T-S-A15	A27	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A28	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	A16	T-S-A16	A28	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A29	T-S-A7+A10-A8+A14-A13	A10	A7+A8+3*T/2-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13-3*S/2	A11	A12	(T-S)/2	3*S-2*T	A29	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A30	A7-A10+A8-A14+A13	T-S-A10	S/2+A12+A11+2*A10-A7-A8+A14-A13-T/2	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	3*S-2*T	(T-S)/2	A30	A46	R-L-A46
8*T+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24-7*L	2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31	A47	R-L-A47
A33	a34	9*(R-L)/2-A40-A39-A37-A34-A38-A36-A35-A33	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	A40	(R-L)/2	5*L-4*R
R-L-A33	R-L-A34	7*(L-R)/2+A40+A39+A37+A34+A38+A36+A35+A33	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	5*L-4*R	(R-L)/2

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 at the upper left corner embedded with **cornered** magic square of order 7. It contains two equal sums magic rectangles of order 2×5 and a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 5. The magic rectangles of order 2×9 are also of equal width and length. Even though the magic square of order 9

is **semi-magic** at one diagonal, but it allows to write a magic square of order 11. The letters S, T, L and R represents magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively.

Result 2.5. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

A17	T-S+A10+A14-A13	A10	S-A17-A18-A12-A11-2*A10-A14+A13	A11	A12	A18	L-T-A25	A25	A40+5*T+R-A32-2*A25-A13+A33+ A18+2*A8-L-A28-2*A27-A30-A29-7*S+A7+A23+A22+2*A21-A14+A10+ 2*A20+A24-A11-2*A16-A15-A17	A32+2*A25+A13-A33-A18-2*A8+ A28+2*A27+A30+A29+7*S-A7-A23-A22-2*A21+A14-A10-2*A20-A24+A11+2*A16+A15+A17-A40-5*T
A14	A1	A2	S-A1-A2-A3-A4	A3	A4	T-S-A14	L-T-A26	A26	A40	R-L-A40
5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-A15-A13	A8-A2+A7	A5	A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-A6-A7	A6	S-A1-A3-A4-A8	5*S-4*T+A13+A14+A15+A16-A18+A17	5*(T-L)/2+A26+A25+A27+A28+A29+A30	7*(L-T)/2-A26-A25-A27-A28-A29-A30	7*R/2-A41+A32+ 2*A25-A44-A43+A13-A33-A42-A18-A45-A46-2*A8-7*L/2+A28+2*A27+A30+A29+7*S-A7-A23-A22-2*A21+A14-A10-2*A20-A24+A11+2*A16+A15+A17-2*A40-5*T	2*A40+5*T-5*R/2+A41-A32-2*A25+A44+A43-A13+A33+A42+A18+A45+A46+2*A8+5*L/2-A28-2*A27-A30-A29-7*S+A7+ A23+A22+2*A21-A14+A10+ 2*A20+A24-A11-2*A16-A15-A17
A15	A2+A3+A4-A5-A7	S-A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A8	A7	A7-A2-A3+A5+A8	A1+A2+A3-A6-A7	T-S-A15	L-T-A27	A27	A41	R-L-A41
A16	A7-A3+A5	A1-A6+A8	A2+A3-A7	S-A1-A5-A7-A8	A7-A2+A6	T-S-A16	L-T-A28	A28	A42	R-L-A42
A13	S-A1-A4-A7-A8	A3+A4-A5	A7-A2-A3+A5+A6	A1+A2-A6	A8	T-S-A13	L-T-A29	A29	A43	R-L-A43
6*S-A18-4*T	A13-A10-A14	T-S-A10	A17+A18+A12+A11+2*A10+T-2*S+A14-A13	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17	L-T-A30	A30	A44	R-L-A44
A20	5*T-A25+A26-A13+A18+A8-5*S+A7-A14+A10+A20-A16-A15-A17-L	(9*L-17*T)/2-A23-A22-A21-A24+A25-A26+A13-A18-A8+5*S-A7+A14-A10-2*A20+A16+A15+A17	A21	A22	A23	A24	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A20	2*L-6*T+A25-A26+A13-A18-A8+5*S-A7+A14-A10-A20+ A16+A15+A17	(15*T-7*L)/2+A23+A22+A21+A24-A25+A26-A13+A18+A8-5*S+A7-A14+A10+2*A20-A16-A15-A17	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2	A46	R-L-A46
A32	A33	9*(R-L)/2-A39-A38-A36-A33-A37-A35-A34-A32	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	(R-L)/2	5*L-4*R
R-L-A32	R-L-A33	7*(L-R)/2+A39+A38+A36+A33+A37+A35+A34+A32	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	5*L-4*R	(R-L)/2

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 at the upper left corner embedded with magic square of order 5. The magic square of order 9 is also a part of **cornered** magic square of order 11. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal sums in each case. Even though the magic square of order 7 is **semi-magic** but still we have order 9 and 11 as magic squares. The letters S, T, L and R represents magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively.

Result 2.6. Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:

L-T-A33	$T-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21-A20-$ $L+2*A33+A32+A31+A30+$ $A29+A28+A27+A26$	A20	A21	A22	A23	A24	A25	L-A33-A32- A31-A30-A29- A28-A27-A26	$A43-4*T+R-$ $A35+A13+A36-A18-$ $A8+A27+5*S-A7+A14-$ $A10+A16+A15+A17-$ A20-L	$4*T+A35-A13-$ $A36+A18+A8-A27-$ $5*S+A7-A14+A10-A16-$ A15-A17+A20-A43
L-T-A26	A17	$T-S+A10+A14-A13$	A10	$S-A17-A18-A12-A11-$ $2*A10-A14+A13$	A11	A12	A18	A26	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A27	A14	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2-A3-A4$	A3	A4	T-S-A14	A27	$4*T+7*(R-L)/2-$ $A44+A35-A47-A46-$ $A13-A36-A45+A18-A48-$ $A49+A8-A27-5*S+A7-$ $A14+A10-A16-A15-$ $A17+A20-2*A43$	$2*A43-4*T-5*(R-L)/2+$ $A44-A35+A47+$ $A46+A13+A36+A45-$ $A18+A48+A49-$ $A8+A27+5*S-A7+A14-$ $A10+A16+A15+A17-A20$
L-T-A28	$5*T-6*S-A17+A18-A16-A14-$ A15-A13	$A8-A2+A7$	A5	$A1+A2+A3+A4-A5-$ A6-A7	A6	$S-A1-A3-A4-A8$	$5*S-4*T+A13+$ $A14+A15+A16-$ A18+A17	A28	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A29	A15	$A2+A3+A4-A5-A7$	$S-A1-A2-A3-$ A4+A6-A8	A7	$A7-A2-$ A3+A5+A8	$A1+A2+A3-A6-A7$	T-S-A15	A29	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A30	A16	$A7-A3+A5$	$A1-A6+A8$	$A2+A3-A7$	$S-A1-A5-A7-A8$	$A7-A2+A6$	T-S-A16	A30	A46	R-L-A46
L-T-A31	A13	$S-A1-A4-A7-A8$	$A3+A4-A5$	$A7-A2-A3+A5+A6$	$A1+A2-A6$	A8	T-S-A13	A31	A47	R-L-A47
L-T-A32	$6*S-A18-4*T$	$A13-A10-A14$	T-S-A10	$A17+A18+A12+A11$ $+2*A10+T-$ $2*S+A14-A13$	T-S-A11	T-S-A12	T-S-A17	A32	A48	R-L-A48
$8*T+A33+A32+A31+$ $A30+A29+A28+$ A27+A26-7*L	$2*L-2*T+A25+A24+$ $A23+A22+A21+A20-2*A33-$ $A32-A31-A30-A29-A28-$ A27-A26	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	L-T-A25	A33	A49	R-L-A49
A35	A36	$9*(R-L)/2-A42-A41-$ $A39-A36-A40-A38-$ A37-A35	A37	A38	A39	A40	A41	A42	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
R-L-A35	R-L-A36	$7*(L-R)/2+ A42+$ $A41+A39+A36+A40$ $+A38+A37+A35$	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11 with **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 at the upper left corner embedded with magic squares of orders 5 and 7. The magic square of order 5 is **pandiagonal**. The two magic rectangles of order 2×9 are of equal width and length. Even though the we have a semi-magic square at one diagonal of order 9, but still the order 11 is a magic square. The letters S, T, L and R represents magic squares of orders 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively.

2.2 With Magic Square of Order 3

Below are **six** magic square of order 11 with **reduced entries**. These includes magic square of order 3.

Result 2.7. *Let's consider following magic squares of order 11 with **reduced entries**:*

$(R-T)/2-A24$	A26	$A40+A41+A42+A43+A44+A45-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A40$	$(R-T)/2-A41$	$(R-T)/2-A42$	$(R-T)/2-A43$	$(R-T)/2-A44$	$(R-T)/2-A45$	$(9*T-5*R)/2-A46-A25-A26$	$(5*R-9*T)/4+A24+A25+A46$
A25	A24	$7*(R-T)/4-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44-A45$	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	$(7*T-3*R)/4-A46-A24-A25$	A46
$A18+A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-5*(R-T)/4$	$7*(R-T)/4-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23$	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A9	$A12-A14-A9+(5*S-T)/4$	$7*(R-T)/4-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38$	$A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38-5*(R-T)/4$
$(R-T)/2-A18$	A18	A13	A12	$3*(T-S)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A33	$(R-T)/2-A33$
$(R-T)/2-A19$	A19	$A15+A16-(T-S)/4$	$3*(T-S)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-S/3$	$2*S/3-A2$	$2*S/3-A1$	$3*(T-S)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-S)/4$	A34	$(R-T)/2-A34$
$(R-T)/2-A20$	A20	$(T-S)/2-A15$	A15	$4*S/3-2*A1-A2$	$S/3$	$2*A1+A2-2*S/3$	A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A35	$(R-T)/2-A35$
$(R-T)/2-A21$	A21	$(T-S)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	$S-A1-A2$	A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	A36	$(R-T)/2-A36$
$(R-T)/2-A22$	A22	$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-S)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*S-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A37	$(R-T)/2-A37$
$(R-T)/2-A23$	A23	$A12-A13+(5*S-T)/4-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*S-T)/4-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A4$	$(T-S)/2-A5$	$A14+A13-A6$	$T-3*S-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$	A38	$(R-T)/2-A38$
$A24+A46-A39$	$(7*R-11*T)/4+A25+A46-A39$	$7*(R-T)/4-A27-A28-A29-A30-A31-A32$	A27	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A39	$(9*T-5*R)/2-A25-2*A46+A39-A24$
$(9*T-5*R)/4-A25-A46+A39$	$(9*T-5*R)/2-A26-A25-A24-A46+A39$	$A27+A28+A29+A30+A31+A32-5*(R-T)/4$	$(R-T)/2-A27$	$(R-T)/2-A28$	$(R-T)/2-A29$	$(R-T)/2-A30$	$(R-T)/2-A31$	$(R-T)/2-A32$	$(5*R-9*T)/2+2*A25+A24+2*A46-A39+A26$	$(R-T)/2-A39$

Explanations:

It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 11 exactly similar to the Example 2.3 embedded with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7. It contains magic square of order 3. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×7 in each case are of equal width and length. The letters S, T and R represents magic squares of orders 3, 7 and 11 respectively. We observe here that

in some entries there is division by 4. To avoid decimal entries the difference between R and T, and T and S should be multiple of 4. Moreover, some of the entries in the magic square of order 3 are divided by 3. Again here also, to avoid fractional or decimal entries, the magic square of order 3, i.e., S should be multiple of 3. Even if we allow decimal or fractional entries still we have magic squares of orders 3, 7 and 11.

• Alternative Approach

There is an alternative way of writing this magic square with defied widths of magic rectangles of orders 2×3 and 2×7 as d and m. In this case the above magic square stands as given below:

m-A24	A26	A40+A41+A42+ A43+A44+A45- 5*m/2	m-A40	m-A41	m-A42	m-A43	m-A44	m-A45	2*(S+2*d)-5*m- A46-A25-A26	A24-S-2*d +5*m/2+A25+A46
A25	A24	7*m/2-A40-A41- A42-A43-A44- A45	A40	A41	A42	A43	A44	A45	S+2*d-3*m/2-A46- A24-A25	A46
A18+A19+A20+A 21+A22+A23- 5*m/2	7*m/2-A18-A19- A20-A21-A22- A23	d-A12	A14	A10+A11-d/2	d-A10	d-A11	A9	A12-A14-A9+S- d/2	7*m/2-A33-A34- A35-A36-A37-A38	A33+A34+A35+A3 6+A37+A38-5*m/2
m-A18	A18	A13	A12	3*d/2-A10-A11	A10	A11	3*d/2- A12+A14+A9-S	2*S-A13-A14-A9- d	A33	m-A33
m-A19	A19	A15+A16-d/2	3*d/2-A15-A16	A1+A2-S/3	2*S/3-A2	2*S/3-A1	3*d/2-A7-A8	A7+A8-d/2	A34	m-A34
m-A20	A20	d-A15	A15	4*S/3-2*A1-A2	S/3	2*A1+A2-2*S/3	A7	d-A7	A35	m-A35
m-A21	A21	d-A16	A16	A1	A2	S-A1-A2	A8	d-A8	A36	m-A36
m-A22	A22	A14-A6+A9	3*d/2-A12+A13- S+A14-A6+A9	3*d/2-A4-A5	A4	A5	A12-2*A14-2*A9 +2*S-A13+A6-d	A6	A37	m-A37
m-A23	A23	A12-A13+S-d/2- A14+A6-A9	2*S-d-2*A14+A6- A9-A13	A4+A5-d/2	d-A4	d-A5	A14+A13-A6	2*d- A12+2*A14+2*A 9-2*S+A13-A6	A38	m-A38
A24+A46-A39	7*m/2+A25+A46- A39-S-2*d	7*m/2-A27-A28- A29-A30-A31- A32	A27	A28	A29	A30	A31	A32	A39	A39-A24-5*m+ 2*(S+2*d)-A25- 2*A46
A39+S+2*d- 5*m/2-A25-A46	2*(S+2*d)-5*m- A26-A25-A24- A46+A39	A27+A28+A29+ A30+A31+A32- 5*m/2	m-A27	m-A28	m-A29	m-A30	m-A31	m-A32	A26+5*m- 2*(S+2*d)+2*A25+ A24+2*A46-A39	m-A39

Explanations:

In this case the magic squares of orders 3, 7 and 11 respectively given as S , $T = S + 2d$ and $R = S + 2d + 2m$. Again to avoid decimal or fractional entries d and m should be multiples of 2 and S multiple of 3.

Result 2.8. Let's consider following **cornered** magic squares of order 11 with reduced entries:

$A1+A2-M/3$	$2*M/3-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$3*(S-M)/2-A5-A6$	$A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A11	T-S-A11	A21	L-T-A21	A35	R-L-A35
$4*M/3-2*A1-A2$	M/3	$2*A1+A2-2*M/3$	A5	S-M-A5	A12	T-S-A12	A22	L-T-A22	A36	R-L-A36
A1	A2	M-A1-A2	A6	S-M-A6	A13	T-S-A13	A23	L-T-A23	$9*(R-L)/2-A37-A40-A39-A38-A41-A42-A36-A35$	$7*(L-R)/2+A36+A35+A37+A40+A39+A38+A41+A42$
$A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A6-(S-M)/2$	A4	$A1+2*(S-M)-2*A4+A2-2*A5-A6$	(S-M)/2	2*M-S	$5*(T-S)/2-A11-A12-A13-A14$	$3*(S-T)/2+A11+A12+A13+A14$	A24	L-T-A24	A37	R-L-A37
$A1+3*(S-M)/2+A2-2*A5-A6-A4$	S-M-A4	$2*A4-S+M-A1-A2+2*A5+A6$	2*M-S	(S-M)/2	A14	T-S-A14	$7*(L-T)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26$	$5*(T-L)/2+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26$	A38	R-L-A38
$T-3*S/2-M/2+A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11$	A8	A9	$3*T/2-S+M/2-2*A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11-A9-A10$	A10	(T-S)/2	$3*S-2*T$	A25	L-T-A25	A39	R-L-A39
$S/2+M/2-A8-2*A4+A1+A2-2*A5-A12+A11$	T-S-A8	T-S-A9	$2*A8+2*A4-A1-A2+2*A5+A12-A11+A9+A10-T/2-M/2$	T-S-A10	$3*S-2*T$	(T-S)/2	A26	L-T-A26	A40	R-L-A40
A16	$5*S-4*T-L+A16+2*A13+2*A4+2*A1+2*A21-A22-A1-A2+2*A9+2*A8+2*A5+A10+A14$	A17	A18	$(9*L+T)/2-5*S-2*A16-2*A13-2*A4-2*A12-A21+A22+A1+A2-2*A9-2*A8-2*A5-A10-A14-A17-A18-A19-A20$	A19	A20	(L-T)/2	$4*T-3*L$	A41	R-L-A41
L-T-A16	$2*L+3*T-5*S-A16-2*A13-2*A4-2*A12-A21+A22+A1+A2-2*A9-2*A8-2*A5-A10-A14$	L-T-A17	L-T-A18	$5*S-(3*T+7*L)/2+2*A16+2*A13+2*A4+2*A12+A21-A22-A1-A2+2*A9+2*A8+2*A5+A10+A14+A17+A18+A19+A20$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$4*T-3*L$	(L-T)/2	A42	R-L-A42
A28	$(5*S-T)/2+A28+A17-A18+A10+A14-A24+A23-A36+A35-R$	$(11*R-9*L+T-5*S)/2-A34-A33-A31-2*A28-A17+A18-A10-A14+A24-A23+A36-A35-A32-A30-A29$	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	(R-L)/2	$5*L-4*R$
R-L-A28	$2*R-L-A28+(T-5*S)/2-A17+A18-A10-A14+A24-A23+A36-A35$	$(7*L-9*R+5*S-T)/2+A34+A33+A31+2*A28+A17-A18+A10+A14-A24+A23-A36+A35+A32+A30+A29$	R-L-A29	R-L-A30	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	$5*L-4*R$	(R-L)/2

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11 exactly similar to Example 2.1, where the magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7 and 9 are at the left upper corner of magic square of order 11. In each case the magic rectangles of orders 2×3 , 2×5 , 2×7 and 2×9 are of equal

width and length. In each order there are two magic two magic rectangles. The letter M, S, T, L and R are respectively the magic sums of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11. To avoid fractional values, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3.

Result 2.9. Let's consider following **cornered** magic squares of order 11 with reduced entries:

$(T-S)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$	A23	L-T-A23	A37	R-L-A37
A13	A12	$3*(T-S)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A24	L-T-A24	A38	R-L-A38
$A15+A16-(T-S)/4$	$3*(T-S)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-S/3$	$2*S/3-A2$	$2*S/3-A1$	$3*(T-S)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-S)/4$	A25	L-T-A25	A39	R-L-A39
$(T-S)/2-A15$	A15	$4*S/3-2*A1-A2$	S/3	$2*A1+A2-2*S/3$	A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A26	L-T-A26	A40	R-L-A40
$(T-S)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	S-A1-A2	A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	$7*(L-T)/2-A23-A24-A25-A26-A27-A28$	$5*(T-L)/2+A23+A24+A25+A26+A27+A28$	$9*(R-L)/2-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43-A44$	$7*(L-R)/2+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43+A44$
A14-A6+A9	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-S)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*S-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A27	L-T-A27	A41	R-L-A41
$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A4$	$(T-S)/2-A5$	A14+A13-A6	T-3*S-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6	A28	L-T-A28	A42	R-L-A42
A18	$(5*T-3*S)/2-L+A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*A7-A8-A24+A23$	A19	A20	$(9*L+3*S)/2-6*T-2*A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*A7+A8+A24-A23-A19-A20-A21-A22$	A21	A22	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A18	$2*L+(3*S-7*T)/2-A18+2*A4+A5-A1-A2+2*A7+A8+A24-A23$	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	$5*T-(7*L+3*S)/2+2*A18-2*A4-A5+A1+A2-2*A7-A8-A24+A23+A19+A20+A21+A22$	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2	A44	R-L-A44
A30	$3*(T-S)/2-R+A25-A26+A30+2*A14+2*A9-A12+A13-A6+A8+A5-A20+A19+A37-A38$	A31	A32	$(3*S-3*T-9*L+11*R)/2-A25+A26-2*A30-A31-A32-A33-A34-A35-A36-2*A14-2*A9+A12-A13+A6-A8-A5+A20-A19-A37+A38$	A33	A34	A35	A36	(R-L)/2	5*L-4*R
R-L-A30	$2*R-L-3*(T-S)/2-A37+A38-A25+A26-A30-2*A14-2*A9+A12-A13+A6-A8-A5+A20-A19$	R-L-A31	R-L-A32	$(3*T-9*R+7*L-3*S)/2+A25-A26+2*A30+A31+A32+A33+A34+A35+A36+2*A14+2*A9-A12+A13-A6+A8+A5-A20+A19+A37-A38$	R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	5*L-4*R	(R-L)/2

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where at upper left corner there is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 embedded with magic square of order 3. In this case the four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal width and length. It also contains a magic square of order 9. The magic rectangles of orders 2×7 and 2×9 are also of equal width and length in each case.

Again here to avoid fractional values, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3. The letters S, T, L and R represents magic sums of orders 3, 7, 9 and 11 respectively.

Result 2.10. Let's consider following **cornered** magic squares of order 11 with reduced entries:

L-T-A31	$T-L-A23-A22-A21-A20-A19-A18+2*A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	A18	A19	A20	A21	A22	A23	L-A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24	A40	R-L-A40
L-T-A24	$(T-S)/2-A12$	A14	$A10+A11-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A10$	$(T-S)/2-A11$	A9	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A14-A9$	A24	A41	R-L-A41
L-T-A25	A13	A12	$3*(T-S)/4-A10-A11$	A10	A11	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A14+A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-A13-A14-A9$	A25	$9*(R-L)/2-A47-A46-A45-A44-A43-A42-A41-A40$	$7*(L-R)/2+A47+A46+A45+A44+A43+A42+A41+A40$
L-T-A26	$A15+A16-(T-S)/4$	$3*(T-S)/4-A15-A16$	$A1+A2-S/3$	$2*S/3-A2$	$2*S/3-A1$	$3*(T-S)/4-A7-A8$	$A7+A8-(T-S)/4$	A26	A42	R-L-A42
L-T-A27	$(T-S)/2-A15$	A15	$4*S/3-2*A1-A2$	S/3	$2*A1+A2-2*S/3$	A7	$(T-S)/2-A7$	A27	A43	R-L-A43
L-T-A28	$(T-S)/2-A16$	A16	A1	A2	S-A1-A2	A8	$(T-S)/2-A8$	A28	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A29	$A14-A6+A9$	$(3*T-7*S)/4-A12+A13+A14-A6+A9$	$3*(T-S)/4-A4-A5$	A4	A5	$(5*S-T)/2+A12-2*A14-2*A9-A13+A6$	A6	A29	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A30	$(5*S-T)/4+A12-A13-A14+A6-A9$	$(5*S-T)/2-2*A14+A6-A9-A13$	$A4+A5-(T-S)/4$	$(T-S)/2-A4$	$(T-S)/2-A5$	$A14+A13-A6$	$T-3*S-A12+2*A14+2*A9+A13-A6$	A30	A46	R-L-A46
$8*T-7*L+A31+A30+A29+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24$	$2*L-2*T+A23+A22+A21+A20+A19+A18-2*A31-A30-A29-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24$	L-T-A18	L-T-A19	L-T-A20	L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	A31	A47	R-L-A47
$R+3*(S-T)/2-L-A40+A41+2*A7+A8-A1-A2-A18+2*A4+A5+A33+A25$	A33	$7*(R-L)/2+3*(T-S)/2-A39-A38-A37-A36-A35-A34-2*A33+A40-A41-2*A7-A8+A1+A2+A18-2*A4-A5-A25$	A34	A35	A36	A37	A38	A39	$(R-L)/2$	$5*L-4*R$
$3*(T-S)/2+A40-A41-2*A7-A8+A1+A2+A18-2*A4-A5-A33-A25$	R-L-A33	$5*(L-R)/2+3*(S-T)/2+A39+A38+A37+A36+A35+A34+2*A33-A40+A41+2*A7+A8-A1-A2-A18+2*A4+A5+A25$	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	$5*L-4*R$	$(R-L)/2$

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where at upper left corner there is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 7. It also contains magic square of order 3. In this case the four magic rectangles of order 2×3 are of equal width and length. The magic rectangles of order 2×9 are also of equal width and length.

The letter *S*, *T*, *L* and *R* represents magic squares of orders 3, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. Even though the magic square of order 9 is **semi-magic** at one diagonal, but still we have order 11 as a magic square.

Result 2.11. Let's consider following **cornered** magic squares of order 11 with reduced entries:

A18	T-S+A11+A15-A14	A11	S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	A19	L-S-A21+A22-A11+A7-A2-A5-A15+A27-A1	S-T+A21-A22+A11-A7+A2+A5+A15-A27+A1	A41	R-L-A41
5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18	A27	L-T-A27	A28-A29+A12-A24+S+A17+A23-A34+A33+A41-R+M+A6	2*R-L-A28+A29-A12+A24-S-A17-A23+A34-A33-A41-M-A6
A15	3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6	T-S-A15	A28	L-T-A28	A42	R-L-A42
A16	A5	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-A5	T-S-A16	A29	L-T-A29	A43	R-L-A43
A17	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	T-S-A17	(5*L-7*T)/2+ A21-A22+S+A11-A7+A2+A5+A15-2*A27+A1-A28-A29-A30-A31	(5*T-3*L)/2-A21+A22-S-A11+A7-A2-A5-A15 +2*A27-A1+A28+A29+A30+A31	(11*R-9*L)/2-2*A41-A28+A29-A12+A24-S-A17-A23+A34-A33-M-A6-A42-A43-A44-A45-A46-A47	(7*L-9*R)/2+2*A41+A28-A29+A12-A24+S+A17+A23-A34+A33+M+A6+A42+A43+A44+A45+A46+A47
A14	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	T-S-A14	A30	L-T-A30	A44	R-L-A44
6*S-A19-4*T	A14-A11-A15	T-S-A11	A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18	A31	L-T-A31	A45	R-L-A45
A21	A22	A23	A24	7*(L-T)/2-A21-A22-A23-A24-A25-A26	A25	A26	(L-T)/2	4*T-3*L	A46	R-L-A46
L-T-A21	L-T-A22	L-T-A23	L-T-A24	5*(T-L)/2+A21+A22+A23+A24+A25+A26	L-T-A25	L-T-A26	4*T-3*L	(L-T)/2	A47	R-L-A47
A33	A34	A35	A36	9*(R-L)/2-A33-A34-A35-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40	A37	A38	A39	A40	(R-L)/2	5*L-4*R
R-L-A33	R-L-A34	R-L-A35	R-L-A36	7*(L-R)/2+A33+A34+A35+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	R-L-A40	5*L-4*R	(R-L)/2

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where at upper left corner there is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 7 embedded with magic square of orders 3. In this case the two magic rectangles of order 2×7 are of equal width and length. The magic rectangles of order 2×9 are also of equal width and length. The letter *M*, *S*, *T*, *L* and *R* represents magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. Even though the magic square of order 7 is **semi-magic** at one diagonal, but still we have order 11 as a magic square. In order to have order 7 as a magic square, we must have the condition $\frac{S}{5} = \frac{T}{7}$.

Result 2.12. Let's consider following **cornered** magic squares of order 11 with reduced entries:

L-T-A28	T-L-A34-A33-A32-A31-A30-A29+2*A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21	A29	A30	A31	A32	A33	A34	L-A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21	A22-S-L-A15-A29+A37-A36-A11+A7-A1+A44+T-A2+R-A5	S-T+A15-A22+A29-A37+A36+A11-A7+A1-A44+A2+A5
L-T-A21	A18	T-S+A11+A15-A14	A11	S-A18-A19-A13-A12-2*A11-A15+A14	A12	A13	A19	A21	A44	R-L-A44
L-T-A22	5*T-6*S-A18+A19-A17-A15-A16-A14	A6	M-A6-A9-A8+A7	S-M-A7	A8	A9	5*S-4*T+A14+A15+A16+A17-A19+A18	A22	A45	R-L-A45
L-T-A23	A15	3*S-4*M-A6+A9-A5-A4	A1+A2-M/3	2*M/3-A2	2*M/3-A1	3*M-2*S+A4+A5-A9+A6	T-S-A15	A23	A46	R-L-A46
L-T-A24	A16	A5	4*M/3-2*A1-A2	M/3	2*A1+A2-2*M/3	S-M-A5	T-S-A16	A24	7*(R-L)/2+S-T+A15-A22+A29-A37+A36+A11-A7+A1-2*A44+A2+A5-A45-A46-A47-A48-A49-A50	5*(L-R)/2-S+T-A15+A22-A29+A37-A36-A11+A7-A1+2*A44-A2-A5+A45+A46+A47+A48+A49+A50
L-T-A25	A17	A4	A1	A2	M-A1-A2	S-M-A4	T-S-A17	A25	A47	R-L-A47
L-T-A26	A14	4*M-2*S-A9	A6+A9+A8+S-2*M-A7	A7	S-M-A8	S-M-A6	T-S-A14	A26	A48	R-L-A48
L-T-A27	6*S-A19-4*T	A14-A11-A15	T-S-A11	A18+A19+A13+A12+2*A11+T-2*S+A15-A14	T-S-A12	T-S-A13	T-S-A18	A27	A49	R-L-A49
8*T-7*L+A28+A27+A26+A25+A24+A23+A22+A21	2*L-2*T+A34+A33+A32+A31+A30+A29-2*A28-A27-A26-A25-A24-A23-A22-A21	L-T-A29	L-T-A30	L-T-A31	L-T-A32	L-T-A33	L-T-A34	A28	A50	R-L-A50
A36	A37	A38	A39	9*(R-L)/2-A36-A37-A38-A39-A40-A41-A42-A43	A40	A41	A42	A43	(R-L)/2	5*L-4*R
R-L-A36	R-L-A37	R-L-A38	R-L-A39	7*(L-R)/2+A36+A37+A38+A39+A40+A41+A42+A43	R-L-A40	R-L-A41	R-L-A42	R-L-A43	5*L-4*R	(R-L)/2

Explanations:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 11, where at upper left corner there is a **single-digit bordered** magic square of order 9 embedded with magic square of orders 3. In this case the two magic rectangles of order 2×9 are of equal width and length. The letter M, S, T, L and R represents magic squares of orders 3, 5, 7, 9 and 11 respectively. Even though the magic square of order 9 is **semi-magic** at one diagonal, but still we have order 11 as a magic square. In order to have order 9 as a magic square, we must have the condition $\frac{S}{5} = \frac{T}{7} = \frac{L}{9}$.

The examples given in the next section are based on the Results 2.1 to 2.12, where the entries are some **dates** and the **magic sums** are the **days** of the year 2025.

3 Days and Dates of the Year 2025 for the Month June

This work brings **dates** and **days of the year**, 2025 in terms of magic squares of order 11. This section is only for the month **June, 2025**. As explained above, here there are total twelve types of magic squares of order 11 based on the Results 2.1 to 2.12. The readers can see the complete work as **pdf files** for the months of **June, September** and **December 2025** at the author’s web-site link <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=15857>.

■ 152nd Day of the Year - 01.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-93	108	152	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-78	56	152	
108	-78	1	6	10	20	25	23	7	-168	198	152	
2	28	29	15	4	16	-2	24	6	43	-13	152	
1	29	19	8	17	24	-6	-23	53	44	-14	152	
0	30	12	3	9	11	27	25	5	45	-15	152	
-1	31	1	30	22	-9	18	26	4	46	-16	152	
-2	32	16	20	-4	21	22	15	2	47	-17	152	
-3	33	14	10	34	9	8	2	15	48	-18	152	
41	55	-2185	106	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-98	152	
-25	-78	2215	-76	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	169	-19	152	
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
1	6	18	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-27	152	
49	25	-26	26	-4	34	-4	-21	43	57	-27	152	
-1	16	27	54	-26	-63	93	-22	44	-342	372	152	
32	3	-1	-11	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-28	152	
-11	20	52	-19	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-29	152	
6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-30	152	
24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-31	152	
38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-32	152	
-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-33	152	
106	50	-2311	51	52	53	54	55	2025	15	2	152	
-76	-20	2341	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-1995	2	15	152	
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
	-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-481	152
	40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-19	152
	58	-37	1	6	28	20	25	-1	22	-740	770	152
	-13	34	29	15	4	16	16	25	-4	50	-20	152
	-14	35	19	26	17	24	-6	26	-5	51	-21	152
	-15	36	12	3	9	29	27	27	-6	52	-22	152
	-16	37	19	30	22	-9	18	28	-7	53	-23	152
	-6	-84	-2070	106	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-24	152
	105	24	2091	-85	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-25	152
	1777	42	-1957	43	44	45	46	47	48	15	2	152
	-1747	-12	1987	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	2	15	152
	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
	-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	187	-157	152
	-22	1	6	18	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-31	152
	-23	49	25	-26	26	-4	34	-4	45	-500	530	152
	-24	-1	16	27	54	-26	-63	93	46	62	-32	152
	-25	32	3	-1	-11	47	35	-5	47	63	-33	152
	-26	-11	20	52	-19	28	36	-6	48	64	-34	152
	-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-35	152
	-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-36	152
	326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-37	152
	106	54	-2335	55	56	57	58	59	2025	15	2	152
	-76	-24	2365	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	-1995	2	15	152
	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
	37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	1946	-1916	152
	34	1	6	28	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-30	152
	-117	49	25	-26	26	6	137	230	-208	-2252	2282	152
	35	-1	26	27	54	-26	-15	-25	47	61	-31	152
	36	32	3	-1	-1	47	-16	-26	48	62	-32	152
	33	-1	20	52	-19	28	-13	-27	49	63	-33	152
	42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-34	152
	40	-33	-2146	41	106	2025	44	11	34	65	-35	152
	-18	55	2168	-19	-84	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-36	152
	52	53	-309	54	55	56	57	58	59	15	2	152
	-22	-23	339	-24	-25	-26	-27	-28	-29	2	15	152
	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
	-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	83	-53	152
	-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-23	152
	-15	24	1	6	18	20	25	6	37	-340	370	152
	-16	-17	29	15	4	16	6	47	38	54	-24	152
	-17	25	19	16	17	24	-6	5	39	55	-25	152
	-18	26	12	3	9	19	27	4	40	56	-26	152
	-19	23	9	30	22	-9	18	7	41	57	-27	152
	-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-28	152
	262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-29	152
	45	46	-2288	106	48	2025	50	51	52	15	2	152
	-15	-16	2318	-76	-18	-1995	-20	-21	-22	2	15	152
	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
-4	36	84	29	24	-22	10	5	-25	-93	108	152	
35	34	-54	1	6	52	20	25	55	-78	56	152	
108	-78	6	24	27	8	7	19	1	-168	198	152	
2	28	23	22	1	20	21	27	-22	43	-13	152	
1	29	37	-9	11	12	13	7	21	44	-14	152	
0	30	3	25	14	12	10	17	11	45	-15	152	
-1	31	2	26	11	12	13	18	10	46	-16	152	
-2	32	27	34	14	13	15	-27	16	47	-17	152	
-3	33	-6	-30	14	15	13	31	55	48	-18	152	
41	55	-2185	106	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-98	152	
-25	-78	2215	-76	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	169	-19	152	
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
2121	-2005	-86	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	-15	152	
-2197	10	2217	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	-16	152	
106	2025	-2101	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-253	283	152	
-2096	14	2157	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	-17	152	
2146	36	-2107	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	-18	152	
-2087	18	19	2085	20	11	36	35	-15	49	-19	152	
2109	4	3	-2063	2	36	11	36	-16	50	-20	152	
26	-1970	27	28	1900	29	30	10	42	51	-21	152	
-6	1990	-7	-8	-1880	-9	-10	42	10	52	-22	152	
38	76	-118	1	6	20	25	43	44	15	2	152	
-8	-46	148	29	24	10	5	-13	-14	2	15	152	
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
6	24	2117	-78	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	-15	152	
23	22	-2089	106	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	-16	152	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	-17	152	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	-18	152	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-260	292	152	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-19	152	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-20	152	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-21	152	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-22	152	
40	73	1	6	-112	20	25	45	46	16	-8	152	
-8	-41	31	26	144	12	7	-13	-14	-8	16	152	
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										152
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	-18	152	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	-19	152	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-284	316	152	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	-20	152	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-21	152	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-22	152	
1	27	46	-2089	106	2025	-51	16	39	55	-23	152	
0	-18	-54	2117	-78	-1997	31	79	40	56	-24	152	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-25	152	
2265	43	-2305	44	45	1	6	20	25	16	-8	152	
-2233	-11	2337	-12	-13	31	26	12	7	-8	16	152	
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										152
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	25	-7	51	-29	152	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	152	-130	152	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-30	152	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-31	152	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-157	175	-431	453	152	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-32	152	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-33	152	
1	6	33	34	-56	20	25	9	58	56	-34	152	
17	12	-15	-16	74	-2	-7	58	9	57	-35	152	
106	44	45	46	-2313	47	2025	49	50	11	42	152	
-84	-22	-23	-24	2335	-25	-2003	-27	-28	42	11	152	
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										152
-20	161	39	1	6	20	25	44	-146	35	-13	152	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-32	152	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-33	152	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-34	152	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-335	357	152	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-35	152	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-36	152	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-37	152	
262	-143	-21	17	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-38	152	
46	47	48	106	-2329	2025	51	52	53	11	42	152	
-24	-25	-26	-84	2351	-2003	-29	-30	-31	42	11	152	
152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	152	

■ 153rd Day of the Year - 02.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-91	107	153	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-77	56	153	
108	-78	2	6	18	20	25	23	-1	-168	198	153	
2	28	29	15	5	16	6	24	-2	43	-13	153	
1	29	19	16	17	24	-5	-43	65	44	-14	153	
0	30	12	4	9	19	27	25	-3	45	-15	153	
-1	31	9	30	22	-8	18	26	-4	46	-16	153	
-2	32	8	20	-16	21	22	11	27	47	-17	153	
-3	33	14	2	38	1	0	27	11	48	-18	153	
41	54	-2285	206	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-96	153	
-24	-76	2315	-176	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	167	-19	153	
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
2	6	28	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-25	153	
49	25	-25	26	6	34	-14	-23	43	176	-144	153	
-1	26	27	54	-25	-88	108	-24	44	-452	484	153	
32	4	-1	-1	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-26	153	
-1	20	52	-18	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-27	153	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-28	153	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-29	153	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-30	153	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-31	153	
206	50	-2402	51	52	53	54	55	2025	16	-7	153	
-174	-18	2434	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1993	-7	16	153	
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
	-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-484	153
	40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	-17	153
	62	-42	2	6	28	20	25	-6	26	-736	768	153
	-14	34	29	15	5	16	16	25	-5	50	-18	153
	-15	35	19	26	17	24	-5	26	-6	51	-19	153
	-16	36	12	4	9	29	27	27	-7	52	-20	153
	-17	37	19	30	22	-8	18	28	-8	53	-21	153
	-1	-80	-2175	206	21	2025	23	52	50	54	-22	153
	100	24	2195	-186	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-23	153
	1984	42	-2155	43	44	45	46	47	48	16	-7	153
	-1952	-10	2187	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-7	16	153
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
	-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	108	-76	153
	-24	2	6	28	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-29	153
	-25	49	25	-25	26	6	34	-14	45	-412	444	153
	-26	-1	26	27	54	-25	-88	108	46	62	-30	153
	-27	32	4	-1	-1	47	35	-15	47	63	-31	153
	-28	-1	20	52	-18	28	36	-16	48	64	-32	153
	-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-33	153
	-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-34	153
	341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-35	153
	206	54	-2426	55	56	57	58	59	2025	16	-7	153
	-174	-22	2458	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-1993	-7	16	153
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
	37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	2116	-2084	153
	34	2	6	18	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-28	153
	-58	49	25	-25	26	-4	88	235	-215	-2413	2445	153
	35	-1	16	27	54	-25	-5	-27	47	61	-29	153
	36	32	4	-1	-11	47	-6	-28	48	62	-30	153
	33	-11	20	52	-18	28	-3	-29	49	63	-31	153
	-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-32	153
	40	18	-2304	41	206	2025	44	10	41	65	-33	153
	-20	2	2324	-21	-186	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-34	153
	52	53	-300	54	55	56	57	58	59	16	-7	153
	-20	-21	332	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-7	16	153
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
	-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	138	-96	153
	-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	-11	153
	-29	24	2	6	28	20	25	-2	37	-341	383	153
	-30	-68	29	15	5	16	16	90	38	54	-12	153
	-31	25	19	26	17	24	-5	-3	39	55	-13	153
	-32	26	12	4	9	29	27	-4	40	56	-14	153
	-33	23	19	30	22	-8	18	-1	41	57	-15	153
	-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	-16	153
	363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	-17	153
	45	46	-2334	206	48	2025	50	51	52	21	-57	153
	-3	-4	2376	-164	-6	-1983	-8	-9	-10	-57	21	153
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
-2	36	80	30	26	-20	12	7	-23	-109	116	153	
35	34	-48	2	6	52	20	25	55	-84	56	153	
103	-71	6	24	27	8	7	19	-2	-161	193	153	
4	28	23	22	1	20	21	30	-28	43	-11	153	
3	29	37	-9	12	10	11	7	21	44	-12	153	
2	30	3	25	10	11	12	17	11	45	-13	153	
1	31	2	26	11	12	10	18	10	46	-14	153	
0	32	27	37	14	13	15	-33	16	47	-15	153	
-1	33	-9	-36	14	15	13	31	61	48	-16	153	
41	65	-2278	206	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-114	153	
-33	-94	2310	-174	-6	-7	-8	-1993	-10	185	-17	153	
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
2220	-2003	-184	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	-15	153	
-2393	11	2415	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	-16	153	
206	2025	-2198	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-253	283	153	
-2195	14	2253	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	-17	153	
2243	34	-2205	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	-18	153	
-2191	18	19	2184	20	10	41	35	-13	49	-19	153	
2211	2	1	-2164	0	41	10	36	-14	50	-20	153	
26	-2062	27	28	1999	29	30	11	35	51	-21	153	
-4	2084	-5	-6	-1977	-7	-8	35	11	52	-22	153	
38	78	-121	2	6	20	25	43	44	15	3	153	
-8	-48	151	28	24	10	5	-13	-14	3	15	153	
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
2	24	2219	-182	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	-15	153	
23	22	-2195	206	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	-16	153	
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	-17	153	
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	-18	153	
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-260	292	153	
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	-19	153	
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	-20	153	
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	-21	153	
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	-22	153	
40	60	2	6	-100	20	25	45	46	16	-7	153	
-8	-28	30	26	132	12	7	-13	-14	-7	16	153	
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										153
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	-18	153	
6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	-19	153	
5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-284	316	153	
4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	-20	153	
3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	-21	153	
2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	-22	153	
1	27	31	-2195	206	2025	-29	16	39	55	-23	153	
0	-7	-32	2219	-182	-2001	31	53	40	56	-24	153	
101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-25	153	
2477	43	-2518	44	45	2	6	20	25	16	-7	153	
-2445	-11	2550	-12	-13	30	26	12	7	-7	16	153	
153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										153
	28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	25	-5	51	-29	153
	-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	251	-229	153
	25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-30	153
	26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-31	153
	27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-150	170	-530	552	153
	24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-32	153
	7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-33	153
	2	6	33	34	-50	20	25	10	51	56	-34	153
	18	14	-13	-14	70	0	-5	51	10	57	-35	153
	206	44	45	46	-2413	47	2025	49	50	11	43	153
	-184	-22	-23	-24	2435	-25	-2003	-27	-28	43	11	153
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										153
	-19	159	39	2	6	20	25	44	-145	35	-13	153
	-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-32	153
	-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-33	153
	-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-34	153
	-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-335	357	153
	-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-35	153
	-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-36	153
	-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-37	153
	255	-140	-20	17	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-38	153
	46	47	48	206	-2429	2025	51	52	53	11	43	153
	-24	-25	-26	-184	2451	-2003	-29	-30	-31	43	11	153
	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153	153

■ 154th Day of the Year - 03.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154
	-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-89	106	154
	35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-76	56	154
	108	-78	3	6	8	20	25	23	9	-168	198	154
	2	28	29	15	6	16	-4	24	8	43	-13	154
	1	29	19	6	17	24	-4	-18	50	44	-14	154
	0	30	12	5	9	9	27	25	7	45	-15	154
	-1	31	-1	30	22	-7	18	26	6	46	-16	154
	-2	32	18	20	-1	21	22	16	-2	47	-17	154
	-3	33	14	12	33	11	10	-2	16	48	-18	154
	41	53	-2385	306	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-94	154
	-23	-74	2415	-276	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	165	-19	154
	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154
	3	6	16	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-25	154
	49	25	-24	26	-6	34	-4	-21	43	255	-223	154
	-1	14	27	54	-24	-63	93	-22	44	-531	563	154
	32	5	-1	-13	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-26	154
	-13	20	52	-17	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-27	154
	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-28	154
	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-29	154
	38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-30	154
	-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-31	154
	306	50	-2502	51	52	53	54	55	2025	16	-6	154
	-274	-18	2534	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1993	-6	16	154
	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154
	-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-479	154
	40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-17	154
	58	-37	3	6	26	20	25	-1	22	-731	763	154
	-13	34	29	15	6	16	14	25	-4	50	-18	154
	-14	35	19	24	17	24	-4	26	-5	51	-19	154
	-15	36	12	5	9	27	27	27	-6	52	-20	154
	-16	37	17	30	22	-7	18	28	-7	53	-21	154
	-6	-84	-2270	306	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-22	154
	105	24	2291	-285	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-23	154
	2179	42	-2350	43	44	45	46	47	48	16	-6	154
	-2147	-10	2382	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-6	16	154
	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154
	-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-11	43	154
	-22	3	6	16	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-29	154
	-23	49	25	-24	26	-6	34	-4	45	-293	325	154
	-24	-1	14	27	54	-24	-63	93	46	62	-30	154
	-25	32	5	-1	-13	47	35	-5	47	63	-31	154
	-26	-13	20	52	-17	28	36	-6	48	64	-32	154
	-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-33	154
	-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-34	154
	326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-35	154
	306	54	-2526	55	56	57	58	59	2025	16	-6	154
	-274	-22	2558	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-1993	-6	16	154
	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154
	37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	2148	-2116	154
	34	3	6	26	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-28	154
	-117	49	25	-24	26	4	137	230	-208	-2445	2477	154
	35	-1	24	27	54	-24	-15	-25	47	61	-29	154
	36	32	5	-1	-3	47	-16	-26	48	62	-30	154
	33	-3	20	52	-17	28	-13	-27	49	63	-31	154
	42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-32	154
	40	-33	-2346	41	306	2025	44	11	34	65	-33	154
	-18	55	2368	-19	-284	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-34	154
	52	53	-300	54	55	56	57	58	59	16	-6	154
	-20	-21	332	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	-6	16	154
	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154
	-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	85	-53	154
	-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-21	154
	-15	24	3	6	16	20	25	6	37	-333	365	154
	-16	-17	29	15	6	16	4	47	38	54	-22	154
	-17	25	19	14	17	24	-4	5	39	55	-23	154
	-18	26	12	5	9	17	27	4	40	56	-24	154
	-19	23	7	30	22	-7	18	7	41	57	-25	154
	-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-26	154
	262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-27	154
	45	46	-2479	306	48	2025	50	51	52	16	-6	154
	-13	-14	2511	-274	-16	-1993	-18	-19	-20	-6	16	154
	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154											
-6	36	91	25	22	-24	8	3	-27	-71	97	154	2321	-2005	-286	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	-13	154
35	34	-63	3	6	52	20	25	55	-69	56	154	-2597	10	2617	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	-14	154
113	-85	6	24	27	8	7	19	7	-175	203	154	306	2025	-2301	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-244	276	154
0	28	23	22	1	20	21	21	-10	43	-15	154	-2296	14	2357	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	-15	154
-1	29	37	-9	9	16	17	7	21	44	-16	154	2346	36	-2307	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	-16	154
-2	30	3	25	22	14	6	17	11	45	-17	154	-2287	18	19	2285	20	11	36	35	-15	49	-17	154
-3	31	2	26	11	12	19	18	10	46	-18	154	2309	4	3	-2263	2	36	11	36	-16	50	-18	154
-4	32	27	28	14	13	15	-15	16	47	-19	154	26	-2170	27	28	2100	29	30	10	42	51	-19	154
-5	33	0	-18	14	15	13	31	43	48	-20	154	-6	2190	-7	-8	-2080	-9	-10	42	10	52	-20	154
41	42	-2392	306	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-76	154	38	74	-109	3	6	20	25	43	44	16	-6	154
-14	-56	2420	-278	-10	-11	-12	-1997	-14	147	-21	154	-6	-42	141	29	26	12	7	-11	-12	-6	16	154
154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										154											
6	24	2317	-278	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	-13	154	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	-16	154
23	22	-2289	306	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	-14	154	6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	-17	154
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	-15	154	5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-275	309	154
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	-16	154	4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	-18	154
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-251	285	154	3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-19	154
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-17	154	2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-20	154
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-18	154	1	27	46	-2289	306	2025	-51	16	39	55	-21	154
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-19	154	0	-18	-54	2317	-278	-1997	31	79	40	56	-22	154
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-20	154	100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-23	154
40	71	3	6	-103	20	25	45	46	17	-16	154	2667	43	-2700	44	45	3	6	20	25	17	-16	154
-6	-37	31	28	137	14	9	-11	-12	-16	17	154	-2633	-9	2734	-10	-11	31	28	14	9	-16	17	154
154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										154
	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	23	-5	51	-27	154
	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	350	-326	154
	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-28	154
	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-29	154
	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-155	173	-620	644	154
	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-30	154
	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-31	154
	3	6	33	34	-58	20	25	9	58	56	-32	154
	15	12	-15	-16	76	-2	-7	58	9	57	-33	154
	306	44	45	46	-2504	47	2025	49	50	12	34	154
	-282	-20	-21	-22	2528	-23	-2001	-25	-26	34	12	154
	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										154
	-20	159	39	3	6	20	25	44	-146	37	-13	154
	-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-30	154
	-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-31	154
	-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-32	154
	-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-328	352	154
	-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-33	154
	-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-34	154
	-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-35	154
	262	-141	-21	15	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-36	154
	46	47	48	306	-2520	2025	51	52	53	12	34	154
	-22	-23	-24	-282	2544	-2001	-27	-28	-29	34	12	154
	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154	154

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◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155
	-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-87	105	155
	35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-75	56	155
	108	-78	4	6	16	20	25	23	1	-168	198	155
	2	28	29	15	7	16	4	24	0	43	-13	155
	1	29	19	14	17	24	-3	-38	62	44	-14	155
	0	30	12	6	9	17	27	25	-1	45	-15	155
	-1	31	7	30	22	-6	18	26	-2	46	-16	155
	-2	32	10	20	-13	21	22	12	23	47	-17	155
	-3	33	14	4	37	3	2	23	12	48	-18	155
	41	52	-2485	406	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-92	155
	-22	-72	2515	-376	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	163	-19	155
	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155
	4	6	26	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-23	155
	49	25	-23	26	4	34	-14	-23	43	374	-340	155
	-1	24	27	54	-23	-88	108	-24	44	-641	675	155
	32	6	-1	-3	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-24	155
	-3	20	52	-16	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-25	155
	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-26	155
	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-27	155
	38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-28	155
	-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-29	155
	406	50	-2593	51	52	53	54	55	2025	17	-15	155
	-372	-16	2627	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-1991	-15	17	155
	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155	
		-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-482	155
		40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	-15	155
		62	-42	4	6	26	20	25	-6	26	-727	761	155
		-14	34	29	15	7	16	14	25	-5	50	-16	155
		-15	35	19	24	17	24	-3	26	-6	51	-17	155
		-16	36	12	6	9	27	27	27	-7	52	-18	155
		-17	37	17	30	22	-6	18	28	-8	53	-19	155
		-1	-80	-2375	406	21	2025	23	52	50	54	-20	155
		100	24	2395	-386	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-21	155
		2386	42	-2548	43	44	45	46	47	48	17	-15	155
		-2352	-8	2582	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	17	155
		155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155	
		-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-90	124	155
		-24	4	6	26	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-27	155
		-25	49	25	-23	26	4	34	-14	45	-205	239	155
		-26	-1	24	27	54	-23	-88	108	46	62	-28	155
		-27	32	6	-1	-3	47	35	-15	47	63	-29	155
		-28	-3	20	52	-16	28	36	-16	48	64	-30	155
		-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-31	155
		-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-32	155
		341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-33	155
		406	54	-2617	55	56	57	58	59	2025	17	-15	155
		-372	-20	2651	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-1991	-15	17	155
		155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155	
		37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	2318	-2284	155
		34	4	6	16	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-26	155
		-58	49	25	-23	26	-6	88	235	-215	-2606	2640	155
		35	-1	14	27	54	-23	-5	-27	47	61	-27	155
		36	32	6	-1	-13	47	-6	-28	48	62	-28	155
		33	-13	20	52	-16	28	-3	-29	49	63	-29	155
		-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-30	155
		40	18	-2504	41	406	2025	44	10	41	65	-31	155
		-20	2	2524	-21	-386	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-32	155
		52	53	-291	54	55	56	57	58	59	17	-15	155
		-18	-19	325	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-15	17	155
		155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155	
		-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	140	-96	155
		-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	-9	155
		-29	24	4	6	26	20	25	-2	37	-334	378	155
		-30	-68	29	15	7	16	14	90	38	54	-10	155
		-31	25	19	24	17	24	-3	-3	39	55	-11	155
		-32	26	12	6	9	27	27	-4	40	56	-12	155
		-33	23	17	30	22	-6	18	-1	41	57	-13	155
		-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	-14	155
		363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	-15	155
		45	46	-2525	406	48	2025	50	51	52	22	-65	155
		-1	-2	2569	-362	-4	-1981	-6	-7	-8	-65	22	155
		155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155
-2	36	82	28	26	-20	12	7	-23	-105	114	155	
35	34	-50	4	6	52	20	25	55	-82	56	155	
103	-71	10	24	25	12	11	19	-10	-161	193	155	
4	28	23	22	7	20	21	42	-44	43	-11	155	
3	29	35	-3	14	6	7	13	19	44	-12	155	
2	30	7	25	2	9	16	17	15	45	-13	155	
1	31	6	26	11	12	4	18	14	46	-14	155	
0	32	27	49	20	13	15	-49	16	47	-15	155	
-1	33	-17	-52	12	19	17	31	81	48	-16	155	
41	63	-2478	406	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-110	155	
-31	-90	2510	-374	-6	-7	-8	-1993	-10	181	-17	155	
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155
2420	-2003	-384	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	-13	155	
-2793	11	2815	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	-14	155	
406	2025	-2398	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-244	276	155	
-2395	14	2453	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	-15	155	
2443	34	-2405	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	-16	155	
-2391	18	19	2384	20	10	41	35	-13	49	-17	155	
2411	2	1	-2364	0	41	10	36	-14	50	-18	155	
26	-2262	27	28	2199	29	30	11	35	51	-19	155	
-4	2284	-5	-6	-2177	-7	-8	35	11	52	-20	155	
38	76	-112	4	6	20	25	43	44	16	-5	155	
-6	-44	144	28	26	12	7	-11	-12	-5	16	155	
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155
2	24	2419	-382	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	-13	155	
23	22	-2395	406	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	-14	155	
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	-15	155	
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	-16	155	
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-251	285	155	
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	-17	155	
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	-18	155	
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	-19	155	
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	-20	155	
40	58	4	6	-91	20	25	45	46	17	-15	155	
-6	-24	30	28	125	14	9	-11	-12	-15	17	155	
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										155
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	-16	155	
6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	-17	155	
5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-275	309	155	
4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	-18	155	
3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	-19	155	
2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	-20	155	
1	27	31	-2395	406	2025	-29	16	39	55	-21	155	
0	-7	-32	2419	-382	-2001	31	53	40	56	-22	155	
101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-23	155	
2879	43	-2913	44	45	4	6	20	25	17	-15	155	
-2845	-9	2947	-10	-11	30	28	14	9	-15	17	155	
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										155											
28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	23	-3	51	-27	155	-19	157	39	4	6	20	25	44	-145	37	-13	155
-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	449	-425	155	-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-30	155
25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-28	155	-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-31	155
26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-29	155	-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-32	155
27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-148	168	-719	743	155	-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-328	352	155
24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-30	155	-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-33	155
7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-31	155	-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-34	155
4	6	33	34	-52	20	25	10	51	56	-32	155	-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-35	155
16	14	-13	-14	72	0	-5	51	10	57	-33	155	255	-138	-20	15	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-36	155
406	44	45	46	-2604	47	2025	49	50	12	35	155	46	47	48	406	-2620	2025	51	52	53	12	35	155
-382	-20	-21	-22	2628	-23	-2001	-25	-26	35	12	155	-22	-23	-24	-382	2644	-2001	-27	-28	-29	35	12	155
155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	155	

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◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156											
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-85	104	156	5	6	14	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-23	156
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-74	56	156	49	25	-22	26	-8	34	-4	-21	43	453	-419	156
108	-78	5	6	6	20	25	23	11	-168	198	156	-1	12	27	54	-22	-63	93	-22	44	-720	754	156
2	28	29	15	8	16	-6	24	10	43	-13	156	32	7	-1	-15	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-24	156
1	29	19	4	17	24	-2	-13	47	44	-14	156	-15	20	52	-15	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-25	156
0	30	12	7	9	7	27	25	9	45	-15	156	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-26	156
-1	31	-3	30	22	-5	18	26	8	46	-16	156	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-27	156
-2	32	20	20	2	21	22	17	-6	47	-17	156	38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-28	156
-3	33	14	14	32	13	12	-6	17	48	-18	156	-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-29	156
41	51	-2585	506	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-90	156	506	50	-2693	51	52	53	54	55	2025	17	-14	156
-21	-70	2615	-476	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	161	-19	156	-472	-16	2727	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-1991	-14	17	156
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
	-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-477	156
	40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-15	156
	58	-37	5	6	24	20	25	-1	22	-722	756	156
	-13	34	29	15	8	16	12	25	-4	50	-16	156
	-14	35	19	22	17	24	-2	26	-5	51	-17	156
	-15	36	12	7	9	25	27	27	-6	52	-18	156
	-16	37	15	30	22	-5	18	28	-7	53	-19	156
	-6	-84	-2470	506	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-20	156
	105	24	2491	-485	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-21	156
	2581	42	-2743	43	44	45	46	47	48	17	-14	156
	-2547	-8	2777	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-14	17	156
	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
	-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-209	243	156
	-22	5	6	14	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-27	156
	-23	49	25	-22	26	-8	34	-4	45	-86	120	156
	-24	-1	12	27	54	-22	-63	93	46	62	-28	156
	-25	32	7	-1	-15	47	35	-5	47	63	-29	156
	-26	-15	20	52	-15	28	36	-6	48	64	-30	156
	-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-31	156
	-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-32	156
	326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-33	156
	506	54	-2717	55	56	57	58	59	2025	17	-14	156
	-472	-20	2751	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-1991	-14	17	156
	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
	37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	2350	-2316	156
	34	5	6	24	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-26	156
	-117	49	25	-22	26	2	137	230	-208	-2638	2672	156
	35	-1	22	27	54	-22	-15	-25	47	61	-27	156
	36	32	7	-1	-5	47	-16	-26	48	62	-28	156
	33	-5	20	52	-15	28	-13	-27	49	63	-29	156
	42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-30	156
	40	-33	-2546	41	506	2025	44	11	34	65	-31	156
	-18	55	2568	-19	-484	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-32	156
	52	53	-291	54	55	56	57	58	59	17	-14	156
	-18	-19	325	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-14	17	156
	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
	-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	87	-53	156
	-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-19	156
	-15	24	5	6	14	20	25	6	37	-326	360	156
	-16	-17	29	15	8	16	2	47	38	54	-20	156
	-17	25	19	12	17	24	-2	5	39	55	-21	156
	-18	26	12	7	9	15	27	4	40	56	-22	156
	-19	23	5	30	22	-5	18	7	41	57	-23	156
	-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-24	156
	262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-25	156
	45	46	-2670	506	48	2025	50	51	52	17	-14	156
	-11	-12	2704	-472	-14	-1991	-16	-17	-18	-14	17	156
	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156

◆ **With Magic Squares of Order 3**

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
-4	36	88	25	24	-22	10	5	-25	-85	104	156	
35	34	-58	5	6	52	20	25	55	-74	56	156	
108	-78	8	24	26	10	9	19	0	-168	198	156	
2	28	23	22	4	20	21	30	-24	43	-13	156	
1	29	36	-6	11	12	13	10	20	44	-14	156	
0	30	5	25	14	12	10	17	13	45	-15	156	
-1	31	4	26	11	12	13	18	12	46	-16	156	
-2	32	27	37	17	13	15	-29	16	47	-17	156	
-3	33	-7	-32	13	17	15	31	59	48	-18	156	
41	51	-2585	506	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-90	156	
-21	-70	2615	-476	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	161	-19	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
2521	-2005	-486	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	-11	156	
-2997	10	3017	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	-12	156	
506	2025	-2501	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-235	269	156	
-2496	14	2557	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	-13	156	
2546	36	-2507	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	-14	156	
-2487	18	19	2485	20	11	36	35	-15	49	-15	156	
2509	4	3	-2463	2	36	11	36	-16	50	-16	156	
26	-2370	27	28	2300	29	30	10	42	51	-17	156	
-6	2390	-7	-8	-2280	-9	-10	42	10	52	-18	156	
38	72	-100	5	6	20	25	43	44	17	-14	156	
-4	-38	134	29	28	14	9	-9	-10	-14	17	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
6	24	2517	-478	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	-11	156	
23	22	-2489	506	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	-12	156	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	-13	156	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	-14	156	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-242	278	156	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-15	156	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-16	156	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-17	156	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-18	156	
40	69	5	6	-94	20	25	45	46	18	-24	156	
-4	-33	31	30	130	16	11	-9	-10	-24	18	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	-14	156	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	-15	156	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-266	302	156	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	-16	156	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-17	156	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-18	156	
1	27	46	-2489	506	2025	-51	16	39	55	-19	156	
0	-18	-54	2517	-478	-1997	31	79	40	56	-20	156	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-21	156	
3069	43	-3095	44	45	5	6	20	25	18	-24	156	
-3033	-7	3131	-8	-9	31	30	16	11	-24	18	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										156
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	21	-3	51	-25	156	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	548	-522	156	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-26	156	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-27	156	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-153	171	-809	835	156	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-28	156	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-29	156	
5	6	33	34	-60	20	25	9	58	56	-30	156	
13	12	-15	-16	78	-2	-7	58	9	57	-31	156	
506	44	45	46	-2695	47	2025	49	50	13	26	156	
-480	-18	-19	-20	2721	-21	-1999	-23	-24	26	13	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										156
-20	157	39	5	6	20	25	44	-146	39	-13	156	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-28	156	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-29	156	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-30	156	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-321	347	156	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-31	156	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-32	156	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-33	156	
262	-139	-21	13	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-34	156	
46	47	48	506	-2711	2025	51	52	53	13	26	156	
-20	-21	-22	-480	2737	-1999	-25	-26	-27	26	13	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

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◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

6	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										157
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-83	103	157	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-73	56	157	
108	-78	6	6	14	20	25	23	3	-168	198	157	
2	28	29	15	9	16	2	24	2	43	-13	157	
1	29	19	12	17	24	-1	-33	59	44	-14	157	
0	30	12	8	9	15	27	25	1	45	-15	157	
-1	31	5	30	22	-4	18	26	0	46	-16	157	
-2	32	12	20	-10	21	22	13	19	47	-17	157	
-3	33	14	6	36	5	4	19	13	48	-18	157	
41	50	-2685	606	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-88	157	
-20	-68	2715	-576	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	159	-19	157	
157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	

6	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										157
6	6	24	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-21	157	
49	25	-21	26	2	34	-14	-23	43	572	-536	157	
-1	22	27	54	-21	-88	108	-24	44	-830	866	157	
32	8	-1	-5	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-22	157	
-5	20	52	-14	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-23	157	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-24	157	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-25	157	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-26	157	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-27	157	
606	50	-2784	51	52	53	54	55	2025	18	-23	157	
-570	-14	2820	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1989	-23	18	157	
157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	157	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
	-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-477	156
	40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-15	156
	58	-37	5	6	24	20	25	-1	22	-722	756	156
	-13	34	29	15	8	16	12	25	-4	50	-16	156
	-14	35	19	22	17	24	-2	26	-5	51	-17	156
	-15	36	12	7	9	25	27	27	-6	52	-18	156
	-16	37	15	30	22	-5	18	28	-7	53	-19	156
	-6	-84	-2470	506	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-20	156
	105	24	2491	-485	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-21	156
	2581	42	-2743	43	44	45	46	47	48	17	-14	156
	-2547	-8	2777	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-14	17	156
	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
	-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-209	243	156
	-22	5	6	14	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-27	156
	-23	49	25	-22	26	-8	34	-4	45	-86	120	156
	-24	-1	12	27	54	-22	-63	93	46	62	-28	156
	-25	32	7	-1	-15	47	35	-5	47	63	-29	156
	-26	-15	20	52	-15	28	36	-6	48	64	-30	156
	-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-31	156
	-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-32	156
	326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-33	156
	506	54	-2717	55	56	57	58	59	2025	17	-14	156
	-472	-20	2751	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-1991	-14	17	156
	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
	37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	2350	-2316	156
	34	5	6	24	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-26	156
	-117	49	25	-22	26	2	137	230	-208	-2638	2672	156
	35	-1	22	27	54	-22	-15	-25	47	61	-27	156
	36	32	7	-1	-5	47	-16	-26	48	62	-28	156
	33	-5	20	52	-15	28	-13	-27	49	63	-29	156
	42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-30	156
	40	-33	-2546	41	506	2025	44	11	34	65	-31	156
	-18	55	2568	-19	-484	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-32	156
	52	53	-291	54	55	56	57	58	59	17	-14	156
	-18	-19	325	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-14	17	156
	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
	-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	87	-53	156
	-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-19	156
	-15	24	5	6	14	20	25	6	37	-326	360	156
	-16	-17	29	15	8	16	2	47	38	54	-20	156
	-17	25	19	12	17	24	-2	5	39	55	-21	156
	-18	26	12	7	9	15	27	4	40	56	-22	156
	-19	23	5	30	22	-5	18	7	41	57	-23	156
	-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-24	156
	262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-25	156
	45	46	-2670	506	48	2025	50	51	52	17	-14	156
	-11	-12	2704	-472	-14	-1991	-16	-17	-18	-14	17	156
	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156

◆ **With Magic Squares of Order 3**

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
-4	36	88	25	24	-22	10	5	-25	-85	104	156	
35	34	-58	5	6	52	20	25	55	-74	56	156	
108	-78	8	24	26	10	9	19	0	-168	198	156	
2	28	23	22	4	20	21	30	-24	43	-13	156	
1	29	36	-6	11	12	13	10	20	44	-14	156	
0	30	5	25	14	12	10	17	13	45	-15	156	
-1	31	4	26	11	12	13	18	12	46	-16	156	
-2	32	27	37	17	13	15	-29	16	47	-17	156	
-3	33	-7	-32	13	17	15	31	59	48	-18	156	
41	51	-2585	506	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-90	156	
-21	-70	2615	-476	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	161	-19	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
2521	-2005	-486	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	-11	156	
-2997	10	3017	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	-12	156	
506	2025	-2501	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-235	269	156	
-2496	14	2557	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	-13	156	
2546	36	-2507	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	-14	156	
-2487	18	19	2485	20	11	36	35	-15	49	-15	156	
2509	4	3	-2463	2	36	11	36	-16	50	-16	156	
26	-2370	27	28	2300	29	30	10	42	51	-17	156	
-6	2390	-7	-8	-2280	-9	-10	42	10	52	-18	156	
38	72	-100	5	6	20	25	43	44	17	-14	156	
-4	-38	134	29	28	14	9	-9	-10	-14	17	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
6	24	2517	-478	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	-11	156	
23	22	-2489	506	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	-12	156	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	-13	156	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	-14	156	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-242	278	156	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-15	156	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-16	156	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-17	156	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-18	156	
40	69	5	6	-94	20	25	45	46	18	-24	156	
-4	-33	31	30	130	16	11	-9	-10	-24	18	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										156
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	-14	156	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	-15	156	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-266	302	156	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	-16	156	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-17	156	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-18	156	
1	27	46	-2489	506	2025	-51	16	39	55	-19	156	
0	-18	-54	2517	-478	-1997	31	79	40	56	-20	156	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-21	156	
3069	43	-3095	44	45	5	6	20	25	18	-24	156	
-3033	-7	3131	-8	-9	31	30	16	11	-24	18	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										156
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	21	-3	51	-25	156	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	548	-522	156	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-26	156	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-27	156	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-153	171	-809	835	156	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-28	156	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-29	156	
5	6	33	34	-60	20	25	9	58	56	-30	156	
13	12	-15	-16	78	-2	-7	58	9	57	-31	156	
506	44	45	46	-2695	47	2025	49	50	13	26	156	
-480	-18	-19	-20	2721	-21	-1999	-23	-24	26	13	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

5	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										156
-20	157	39	5	6	20	25	44	-146	39	-13	156	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-28	156	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-29	156	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-30	156	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-321	347	156	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-31	156	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-32	156	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-33	156	
262	-139	-21	13	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-34	156	
46	47	48	506	-2711	2025	51	52	53	13	26	156	
-20	-21	-22	-480	2737	-1999	-25	-26	-27	26	13	156	
156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	156	

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◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-81	102	158	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-72	56	158	
108	-78	7	6	4	20	25	23	13	-168	198	158	
2	28	29	15	10	16	-8	24	12	43	-13	158	
1	29	19	2	17	24	0	-8	44	44	-14	158	
0	30	12	9	9	5	27	25	11	45	-15	158	
-1	31	-5	30	22	-3	18	26	10	46	-16	158	
-2	32	22	20	5	21	22	18	-10	47	-17	158	
-3	33	14	16	31	15	14	-10	18	48	-18	158	
41	49	-2785	706	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-86	158	
-19	-66	2815	-676	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	157	-19	158	
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158
7	6	12	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-21	158	
49	25	-20	26	-10	34	-4	-21	43	651	-615	158	
-1	10	27	54	-20	-63	93	-22	44	-909	945	158	
32	9	-1	-17	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-22	158	
-17	20	52	-13	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-23	158	
6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-24	158	
24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-25	158	
38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-26	158	
-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-27	158	
706	50	-2884	51	52	53	54	55	2025	18	-22	158	
-670	-14	2920	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1989	-22	18	158	
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158															
		-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-475	158			-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-407	443	158
		40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-13	158			-22	7	6	12	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-25	158
		58	-37	7	6	22	20	25	-1	22	-713	749	158			-23	49	25	-20	26	-10	34	-4	45	121	-85	158
		-13	34	29	15	10	16	10	25	-4	50	-14	158			-24	-1	10	27	54	-20	-63	93	46	62	-26	158
		-14	35	19	20	17	24	0	26	-5	51	-15	158			-25	32	9	-1	-17	47	35	-5	47	63	-27	158
		-15	36	12	9	9	23	27	27	-6	52	-16	158			-26	-17	20	52	-13	28	36	-6	48	64	-28	158
		-16	37	13	30	22	-3	18	28	-7	53	-17	158			-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-29	158
		-6	-84	-2670	706	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-18	158			-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-30	158
		105	24	2691	-685	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-19	158			326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-31	158
		2983	42	-3136	43	44	45	46	47	48	18	-22	158			706	54	-2908	55	56	57	58	59	2025	18	-22	158
		-2947	-6	3172	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-22	18	158			-670	-18	2944	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-1989	-22	18	158
		158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158			158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158															
		37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	2552	-2516	158			-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	89	-53	158
		34	7	6	22	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-24	158			-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-17	158
		-117	49	25	-20	26	0	137	230	-208	-2831	2867	158			-15	24	7	6	12	20	25	6	37	-319	355	158
		35	-1	20	27	54	-20	-15	-25	47	61	-25	158			-16	-17	29	15	10	16	0	47	38	54	-18	158
		36	32	9	-1	-7	47	-16	-26	48	62	-26	158			-17	25	19	10	17	24	0	5	39	55	-19	158
		33	-7	20	52	-13	28	-13	-27	49	63	-27	158			-18	26	12	9	9	13	27	4	40	56	-20	158
		42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-28	158			-19	23	3	30	22	-3	18	7	41	57	-21	158
		40	-33	-2746	41	706	2025	44	11	34	65	-29	158			-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-22	158
		-18	55	2768	-19	-684	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-30	158			262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-23	158
		52	53	-282	54	55	56	57	58	59	18	-22	158			45	46	-2861	706	48	2025	50	51	52	18	-22	158
		-16	-17	318	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	-22	18	158			-9	-10	2897	-670	-12	-1989	-14	-15	-16	-22	18	158
		158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158			158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158
-4	36	90	23	24	-22	10	5	-25	-81	102	158	
35	34	-60	7	6	52	20	25	55	-72	56	158	
108	-78	6	24	27	8	7	19	7	-168	198	158	
2	28	23	22	1	20	21	21	-10	43	-13	158	
1	29	37	-9	9	16	17	7	21	44	-14	158	
0	30	3	25	22	14	6	17	11	45	-15	158	
-1	31	2	26	11	12	19	18	10	46	-16	158	
-2	32	27	28	14	13	15	-15	16	47	-17	158	
-3	33	0	-18	14	15	13	31	43	48	-18	158	
41	49	-2785	706	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-86	158	
-19	-66	2815	-676	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	157	-19	158	
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158
2721	-2005	-686	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	-9	158	
-3397	10	3417	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	-10	158	
706	2025	-2701	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-226	262	158	
-2696	14	2757	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	-11	158	
2746	36	-2707	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	-12	158	
-2687	18	19	2685	20	11	36	35	-15	49	-13	158	
2709	4	3	-2663	2	36	11	36	-16	50	-14	158	
26	-2570	27	28	2500	29	30	10	42	51	-15	158	
-6	2590	-7	-8	-2480	-9	-10	42	10	52	-16	158	
38	70	-91	7	6	20	25	43	44	18	-22	158	
-2	-34	127	29	30	16	11	-7	-8	-22	18	158	
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158
6	24	2717	-678	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	-9	158	
23	22	-2689	706	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	-10	158	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	-11	158	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	-12	158	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-233	271	158	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-13	158	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-14	158	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-15	158	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-16	158	
40	67	7	6	-85	20	25	45	46	19	-32	158	
-2	-29	31	32	123	18	13	-7	-8	-32	19	158	
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										158
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	-12	158	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	-13	158	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-257	295	158	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	-14	158	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-15	158	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-16	158	
1	27	46	-2689	706	2025	-51	16	39	55	-17	158	
0	-18	-54	2717	-678	-1997	31	79	40	56	-18	158	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-19	158	
3471	43	-3490	44	45	7	6	20	25	19	-32	158	
-3433	-5	3528	-6	-7	31	32	18	13	-32	19	158	
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										158
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	19	-1	51	-23	158	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	746	-718	158	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-24	158	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-25	158	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-151	169	-998	1026	158	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-26	158	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-27	158	
7	6	33	34	-62	20	25	9	58	56	-28	158	
11	12	-15	-16	80	-2	-7	58	9	57	-29	158	
706	44	45	46	-2886	47	2025	49	50	14	18	158	
-678	-16	-17	-18	2914	-19	-1997	-21	-22	18	14	158	
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	

7	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										158
-20	155	39	7	6	20	25	44	-146	41	-13	158	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-26	158	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-27	158	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-28	158	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-314	342	158	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-29	158	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-30	158	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-31	158	
262	-137	-21	11	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-32	158	
46	47	48	706	-2902	2025	51	52	53	14	18	158	
-18	-19	-20	-678	2930	-1997	-23	-24	-25	18	14	158	
158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	

■ 159th Day of the Year - 08.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

8	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-79	101	159	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-71	56	159	
108	-78	8	6	12	20	25	23	5	-168	198	159	
2	28	29	15	11	16	0	24	4	43	-13	159	
1	29	19	10	17	24	1	-28	56	44	-14	159	
0	30	12	10	9	13	27	25	3	45	-15	159	
-1	31	3	30	22	-2	18	26	2	46	-16	159	
-2	32	14	20	-7	21	22	14	15	47	-17	159	
-3	33	14	8	35	7	6	15	14	48	-18	159	
41	48	-2885	806	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-84	159	
-18	-64	2915	-776	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	155	-19	159	
159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	

8	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159
8	6	22	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-19	159	
49	25	-19	26	0	34	-14	-23	43	770	-732	159	
-1	20	27	54	-19	-88	108	-24	44	-1019	1057	159	
32	10	-1	-7	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-20	159	
-7	20	52	-12	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-21	159	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-22	159	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-23	159	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-24	159	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-25	159	
806	50	-2975	51	52	53	54	55	2025	19	-31	159	
-768	-12	3013	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-1987	-31	19	159	
159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	

8	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159
	-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-478	159
	40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	-11	159
	62	-42	8	6	22	20	25	-6	26	-709	747	159
	-14	34	29	15	11	16	10	25	-5	50	-12	159
	-15	35	19	20	17	24	1	26	-6	51	-13	159
	-16	36	12	10	9	23	27	27	-7	52	-14	159
	-17	37	13	30	22	-2	18	28	-8	53	-15	159
	-1	-80	-2775	806	21	2025	23	52	50	54	-16	159
	100	24	2795	-786	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-17	159
	3190	42	-3334	43	44	45	46	47	48	19	-31	159
	-3152	-4	3372	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-31	19	159
	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159

8	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159
	-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-486	524	159
	-24	8	6	22	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-23	159
	-25	49	25	-19	26	0	34	-14	45	209	-171	159
	-26	-1	20	27	54	-19	-88	108	46	62	-24	159
	-27	32	10	-1	-7	47	35	-15	47	63	-25	159
	-28	-7	20	52	-12	28	36	-16	48	64	-26	159
	-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-27	159
	-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-28	159
	341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-29	159
	806	54	-2999	55	56	57	58	59	2025	19	-31	159
	-768	-16	3037	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-1987	-31	19	159
	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159

8	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159
	37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	2722	-2684	159
	34	8	6	12	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-22	159
	-58	49	25	-19	26	-10	88	235	-215	-2992	3030	159
	35	-1	10	27	54	-19	-5	-27	47	61	-23	159
	36	32	10	-1	-17	47	-6	-28	48	62	-24	159
	33	-17	20	52	-12	28	-3	-29	49	63	-25	159
	-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-26	159
	40	18	-2904	41	806	2025	44	10	41	65	-27	159
	-20	2	2924	-21	-786	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-28	159
	52	53	-273	54	55	56	57	58	59	19	-31	159
	-14	-15	311	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-31	19	159
	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159

8	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159
	-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	144	-96	159
	-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	-5	159
	-29	24	8	6	22	20	25	-2	37	-320	368	159
	-30	-68	29	15	11	16	10	90	38	54	-6	159
	-31	25	19	20	17	24	1	-3	39	55	-7	159
	-32	26	12	10	9	23	27	-4	40	56	-8	159
	-33	23	13	30	22	-2	18	-1	41	57	-9	159
	-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	-10	159
	363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	-11	159
	45	46	-2907	806	48	2025	50	51	52	24	-81	159
	3	2	2955	-758	0	-1977	-2	-3	-4	-81	24	159
	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

8	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159											
-2	36	86	24	26	-20	12	7	-23	-97	110	159	2820	-2003	-784	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	-9	159
35	34	-54	8	6	52	20	25	55	-78	56	159	-3593	11	3615	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	-10	159
103	-71	6	24	27	8	7	19	4	-161	193	159	806	2025	-2798	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-226	262	159
4	28	23	22	1	20	21	24	-16	43	-11	159	-2795	14	2853	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	-11	159
3	29	37	-9	10	14	15	7	21	44	-12	159	2843	34	-2805	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	-12	159
2	30	3	25	18	13	8	17	11	45	-13	159	-2791	18	19	2784	20	10	41	35	-13	49	-13	159
1	31	2	26	11	12	16	18	10	46	-14	159	2811	2	1	-2764	0	41	10	36	-14	50	-14	159
0	32	27	31	14	13	15	-21	16	47	-15	159	26	-2662	27	28	2599	29	30	11	35	51	-15	159
-1	33	-3	-24	14	15	13	31	49	48	-16	159	-4	2684	-5	-6	-2577	-7	-8	35	11	52	-16	159
41	59	-2878	806	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-102	159	38	72	-94	8	6	20	25	43	44	18	-21	159
-27	-82	2910	-774	-6	-7	-8	-1993	-10	173	-17	159	-2	-36	130	28	30	16	11	-7	-8	-21	18	159
159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159

8	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										159											
2	24	2819	-782	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	-9	159	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	-12	159
23	22	-2795	806	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	-10	159	6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	-13	159
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	-11	159	5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-257	295	159
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	-12	159	4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	-14	159
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-233	271	159	3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	-15	159
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	-13	159	2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	-16	159
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	-14	159	1	27	31	-2795	806	2025	-29	16	39	55	-17	159
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	-15	159	0	-7	-32	2819	-782	-2001	31	53	40	56	-18	159
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	-16	159	101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-19	159
40	54	8	6	-73	20	25	45	46	19	-31	159	3683	43	-3703	44	45	8	6	20	25	19	-31	159
-2	-16	30	32	111	18	13	-7	-8	-31	19	159	-3645	-5	3741	-6	-7	30	32	18	13	-31	19	159
159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159

8	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										159
	28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	19	1	51	-23	159
	-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	845	-817	159
	25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-24	159
	26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-25	159
	27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-144	164	-1097	1125	159
	24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-26	159
	7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-27	159
	8	6	33	34	-56	20	25	10	51	56	-28	159
	12	14	-13	-14	76	0	-5	51	10	57	-29	159
	806	44	45	46	-2986	47	2025	49	50	14	19	159
	-778	-16	-17	-18	3014	-19	-1997	-21	-22	19	14	159
	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159

8	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										159
	-19	153	39	8	6	20	25	44	-145	41	-13	159
	-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-26	159
	-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-27	159
	-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-28	159
	-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-314	342	159
	-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-29	159
	-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-30	159
	-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-31	159
	255	-134	-20	11	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-32	159
	46	47	48	806	-3002	2025	51	52	53	14	19	159
	-18	-19	-20	-778	3030	-1997	-23	-24	-25	19	14	159
	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159	159

■ 160th Day of the Year - 09.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
	-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-77	100	160
	35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-70	56	160
	108	-78	9	6	2	20	25	23	15	-168	198	160
	2	28	29	15	12	16	-10	24	14	43	-13	160
	1	29	19	0	17	24	2	-3	41	44	-14	160
	0	30	12	11	9	3	27	25	13	45	-15	160
	-1	31	-7	30	22	-1	18	26	12	46	-16	160
	-2	32	24	20	8	21	22	19	-14	47	-17	160
	-3	33	14	18	30	17	16	-14	19	48	-18	160
	41	47	-2985	906	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-82	160
	-17	-62	3015	-876	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	153	-19	160
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
	9	6	10	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-19	160
	49	25	-18	26	-12	34	-4	-21	43	849	-811	160
	-1	8	27	54	-18	-63	93	-22	44	-1098	1136	160
	32	11	-1	-19	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-20	160
	-19	20	52	-11	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-21	160
	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-22	160
	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-23	160
	38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-24	160
	-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-25	160
	906	50	-3075	51	52	53	54	55	2025	19	-30	160
	-868	-12	3113	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-1987	-30	19	160
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
	-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-473	160
	40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-11	160
	58	-37	9	6	20	20	25	-1	22	-704	742	160
	-13	34	29	15	12	16	8	25	-4	50	-12	160
	-14	35	19	18	17	24	2	26	-5	51	-13	160
	-15	36	12	11	9	21	27	27	-6	52	-14	160
	-16	37	11	30	22	-1	18	28	-7	53	-15	160
	-6	-84	-2870	906	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-16	160
	105	24	2891	-885	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-17	160
	3385	42	-3529	43	44	45	46	47	48	19	-30	160
	-3347	-4	3567	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-30	19	160
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
	-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-605	643	160
	-22	9	6	10	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-23	160
	-23	49	25	-18	26	-12	34	-4	45	328	-290	160
	-24	-1	8	27	54	-18	-63	93	46	62	-24	160
	-25	32	11	-1	-19	47	35	-5	47	63	-25	160
	-26	-19	20	52	-11	28	36	-6	48	64	-26	160
	-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-27	160
	-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-28	160
	326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-29	160
	906	54	-3099	55	56	57	58	59	2025	19	-30	160
	-868	-16	3137	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-1987	-30	19	160
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
	37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	2754	-2716	160
	34	9	6	20	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-22	160
	-117	49	25	-18	26	-2	137	230	-208	-3024	3062	160
	35	-1	18	27	54	-18	-15	-25	47	61	-23	160
	36	32	11	-1	-9	47	-16	-26	48	62	-24	160
	33	-9	20	52	-11	28	-13	-27	49	63	-25	160
	42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-26	160
	40	-33	-2946	41	906	2025	44	11	34	65	-27	160
	-18	55	2968	-19	-884	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-28	160
	52	53	-273	54	55	56	57	58	59	19	-30	160
	-14	-15	311	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	-30	19	160
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
	-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	91	-53	160
	-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-15	160
	-15	24	9	6	10	20	25	6	37	-312	350	160
	-16	-17	29	15	12	16	-2	47	38	54	-16	160
	-17	25	19	8	17	24	2	5	39	55	-17	160
	-18	26	12	11	9	11	27	4	40	56	-18	160
	-19	23	1	30	22	-1	18	7	41	57	-19	160
	-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-20	160
	262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-21	160
	45	46	-3052	906	48	2025	50	51	52	19	-30	160
	-7	-8	3090	-868	-10	-1987	-12	-13	-14	-30	19	160
	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
-4	36	92	21	24	-22	10	5	-25	-77	100	160	
35	34	-62	9	6	52	20	25	55	-70	56	160	
108	-78	10	24	25	12	11	19	-1	-168	198	160	
2	28	23	22	7	20	21	33	-26	43	-13	160	
1	29	35	-3	11	12	13	13	19	44	-14	160	
0	30	7	25	14	12	10	17	15	45	-15	160	
-1	31	6	26	11	12	13	18	14	46	-16	160	
-2	32	27	40	20	13	15	-31	16	47	-17	160	
-3	33	-8	-34	12	19	17	31	63	48	-18	160	
41	47	-2985	906	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-82	160	
-17	-62	3015	-876	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	153	-19	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
2921	-2005	-886	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	-7	160	
-3797	10	3817	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	-8	160	
906	2025	-2901	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-217	255	160	
-2896	14	2957	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	-9	160	
2946	36	-2907	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	-10	160	
-2887	18	19	2885	20	11	36	35	-15	49	-11	160	
2909	4	3	-2863	2	36	11	36	-16	50	-12	160	
26	-2770	27	28	2700	29	30	10	42	51	-13	160	
-6	2790	-7	-8	-2680	-9	-10	42	10	52	-14	160	
38	68	-82	9	6	20	25	43	44	19	-30	160	
0	-30	120	29	32	18	13	-5	-6	-30	19	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
6	24	2917	-878	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	-7	160	
23	22	-2889	906	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	-8	160	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	-9	160	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	-10	160	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-224	264	160	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-11	160	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-12	160	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-13	160	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-14	160	
40	65	9	6	-76	20	25	45	46	20	-40	160	
0	-25	31	34	116	20	15	-5	-6	-40	20	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										160
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	-10	160	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	-11	160	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-248	288	160	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	-12	160	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-13	160	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-14	160	
1	27	46	-2889	906	2025	-51	16	39	55	-15	160	
0	-18	-54	2917	-878	-1997	31	79	40	56	-16	160	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-17	160	
3873	43	-3885	44	45	9	6	20	25	20	-40	160	
-3833	-3	3925	-4	-5	31	34	20	15	-40	20	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										160
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	17	1	51	-21	160	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	944	-914	160	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-22	160	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-23	160	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-149	167	-1187	1217	160	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-24	160	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-25	160	
9	6	33	34	-64	20	25	9	58	56	-26	160	
9	12	-15	-16	82	-2	-7	58	9	57	-27	160	
906	44	45	46	-3077	47	2025	49	50	15	10	160	
-876	-14	-15	-16	3107	-17	-1995	-19	-20	10	15	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

9	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										160
-20	153	39	9	6	20	25	44	-146	43	-13	160	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-24	160	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-25	160	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-26	160	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-307	337	160	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-27	160	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-28	160	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-29	160	
262	-135	-21	9	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-30	160	
46	47	48	906	-3093	2025	51	52	53	15	10	160	
-16	-17	-18	-876	3123	-1995	-21	-22	-23	10	15	160	
160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	

■ 161st Day of the Year - 10.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										161
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-75	99	161	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-69	56	161	
108	-78	10	6	10	20	25	23	7	-168	198	161	
2	28	29	15	13	16	-2	24	6	43	-13	161	
1	29	19	8	17	24	3	-23	53	44	-14	161	
0	30	12	12	9	11	27	25	5	45	-15	161	
-1	31	1	30	22	0	18	26	4	46	-16	161	
-2	32	16	20	-4	21	22	15	11	47	-17	161	
-3	33	14	10	34	9	8	11	15	48	-18	161	
41	46	-3085	1006	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-80	161	
-16	-60	3115	-976	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	151	-19	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										161
10	6	20	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-17	161	
49	25	-17	26	-2	34	-14	-23	43	968	-928	161	
-1	18	27	54	-17	-88	108	-24	44	-1208	1248	161	
32	12	-1	-9	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-18	161	
-9	20	52	-10	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-19	161	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-20	161	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-21	161	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-22	161	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-23	161	
1006	50	-3166	51	52	53	54	55	2025	20	-39	161	
-966	-10	3206	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-1985	-39	20	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										161	
		-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-476	161
		40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	-9	161
		62	-42	10	6	20	20	25	-6	26	-700	740	161
		-14	34	29	15	13	16	8	25	-5	50	-10	161
		-15	35	19	18	17	24	3	26	-6	51	-11	161
		-16	36	12	12	9	21	27	27	-7	52	-12	161
		-17	37	11	30	22	0	18	28	-8	53	-13	161
		-1	-80	-2975	1006	21	2025	23	52	50	54	-14	161
		100	24	2995	-986	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-15	161
		3592	42	-3727	43	44	45	46	47	48	20	-39	161
		-3552	-2	3767	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-39	20	161
		161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										161	
		-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-684	724	161
		-24	10	6	20	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-21	161
		-25	49	25	-17	26	-2	34	-14	45	416	-376	161
		-26	-1	18	27	54	-17	-88	108	46	62	-22	161
		-27	32	12	-1	-9	47	35	-15	47	63	-23	161
		-28	-9	20	52	-10	28	36	-16	48	64	-24	161
		-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-25	161
		-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-26	161
		341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-27	161
		1006	54	-3190	55	56	57	58	59	2025	20	-39	161
		-966	-14	3230	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	-39	20	161
		161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										161	
		37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	2924	-2884	161
		34	10	6	10	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-20	161
		-58	49	25	-17	26	-12	88	235	-215	-3185	3225	161
		35	-1	8	27	54	-17	-5	-27	47	61	-21	161
		36	32	12	-1	-19	47	-6	-28	48	62	-22	161
		33	-19	20	52	-10	28	-3	-29	49	63	-23	161
		-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-24	161
		40	18	-3104	41	1006	2025	44	10	41	65	-25	161
		-20	2	3124	-21	-986	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-26	161
		52	53	-264	54	55	56	57	58	59	20	-39	161
		-12	-13	304	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-39	20	161
		161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										161	
		-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	146	-96	161
		-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	-3	161
		-29	24	10	6	20	20	25	-2	37	-313	363	161
		-30	-68	29	15	13	16	8	90	38	54	-4	161
		-31	25	19	18	17	24	3	-3	39	55	-5	161
		-32	26	12	12	9	21	27	-4	40	56	-6	161
		-33	23	11	30	22	0	18	-1	41	57	-7	161
		-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	-8	161
		363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	-9	161
		45	46	-3098	1006	48	2025	50	51	52	25	-89	161
		5	4	3148	-956	2	-1975	0	-1	-2	-89	25	161
		161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										161
-2	36	88	22	26	-20	12	7	-23	-93	108	161	
35	34	-56	10	6	52	20	25	55	-76	56	161	
103	-71	10	24	25	12	11	19	-4	-161	193	161	
4	28	23	22	7	20	21	36	-32	43	-11	161	
3	29	35	-3	12	10	11	13	19	44	-12	161	
2	30	7	25	10	11	12	17	15	45	-13	161	
1	31	6	26	11	12	10	18	14	46	-14	161	
0	32	27	43	20	13	15	-37	16	47	-15	161	
-1	33	-11	-40	12	19	17	31	69	48	-16	161	
41	57	-3078	1006	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-98	161	
-25	-78	3110	-974	-6	-7	-8	-1993	-10	169	-17	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										161
3020	-2003	-984	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	-7	161	
-3993	11	4015	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	-8	161	
1006	2025	-2998	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-217	255	161	
-2995	14	3053	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	-9	161	
3043	34	-3005	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	-10	161	
-2991	18	19	2984	20	10	41	35	-13	49	-11	161	
3011	2	1	-2964	0	41	10	36	-14	50	-12	161	
26	-2862	27	28	2799	29	30	11	35	51	-13	161	
-4	2884	-5	-6	-2777	-7	-8	35	11	52	-14	161	
38	70	-85	10	6	20	25	43	44	19	-29	161	
0	-32	123	28	32	18	13	-5	-6	-29	19	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										161
2	24	3019	-982	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	-7	161	
23	22	-2995	1006	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	-8	161	
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	-9	161	
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	-10	161	
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-224	264	161	
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	-11	161	
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	-12	161	
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	-13	161	
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	-14	161	
40	52	10	6	-64	20	25	45	46	20	-39	161	
0	-12	30	34	104	20	15	-5	-6	-39	20	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										161
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	-10	161	
6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	-11	161	
5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-248	288	161	
4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	-12	161	
3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	-13	161	
2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	-14	161	
1	27	31	-2995	1006	2025	-29	16	39	55	-15	161	
0	-7	-32	3019	-982	-2001	31	53	40	56	-16	161	
101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-17	161	
4085	43	-4098	44	45	10	6	20	25	20	-39	161	
-4045	-3	4138	-4	-5	30	34	20	15	-39	20	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										161
28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	17	3	51	-21	161	
-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	1043	-1013	161	
25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-22	161	
26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-23	161	
27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-142	162	-1286	1316	161	
24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-24	161	
7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-25	161	
10	6	33	34	-58	20	25	10	51	56	-26	161	
10	14	-13	-14	78	0	-5	51	10	57	-27	161	
1006	44	45	46	-3177	47	2025	49	50	15	11	161	
-976	-14	-15	-16	3207	-17	-1995	-19	-20	11	15	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

10	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										161
-19	151	39	10	6	20	25	44	-145	43	-13	161	
-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-24	161	
-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-25	161	
-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-26	161	
-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-307	337	161	
-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-27	161	
-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-28	161	
-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-29	161	
255	-132	-20	9	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-30	161	
46	47	48	1006	-3193	2025	51	52	53	15	11	161	
-16	-17	-18	-976	3223	-1995	-21	-22	-23	11	15	161	
161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	161	

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◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										162
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-73	98	162	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-68	56	162	
108	-78	11	6	0	20	25	23	17	-168	198	162	
2	28	29	15	14	16	-12	24	16	43	-13	162	
1	29	19	-2	17	24	4	2	38	44	-14	162	
0	30	12	13	9	1	27	25	15	45	-15	162	
-1	31	-9	30	22	1	18	26	14	46	-16	162	
-2	32	26	20	11	21	22	20	-18	47	-17	162	
-3	33	14	20	29	19	18	-18	20	48	-18	162	
41	45	-3185	1106	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-78	162	
-15	-58	3215	-1076	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	149	-19	162	
162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										162
11	6	8	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-17	162	
49	25	-16	26	-14	34	-4	-21	43	1047	-1007	162	
-1	6	27	54	-16	-63	93	-22	44	-1287	1327	162	
32	13	-1	-21	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-18	162	
-21	20	52	-9	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-19	162	
6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-20	162	
24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-21	162	
38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-22	162	
-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-23	162	
1106	50	-3266	51	52	53	54	55	2025	20	-38	162	
-1066	-10	3306	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-1985	-38	20	162	
162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										162															
		-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-471	162			-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-803	843	162
		40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-9	162			-22	11	6	8	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-21	162
		58	-37	11	6	18	20	25	-1	22	-695	735	162			-23	49	25	-16	26	-14	34	-4	45	535	-495	162
		-13	34	29	15	14	16	6	25	-4	50	-10	162			-24	-1	6	27	54	-16	-63	93	46	62	-22	162
		-14	35	19	16	17	24	4	26	-5	51	-11	162			-25	32	13	-1	-21	47	35	-5	47	63	-23	162
		-15	36	12	13	9	19	27	27	-6	52	-12	162			-26	-21	20	52	-9	28	36	-6	48	64	-24	162
		-16	37	9	30	22	1	18	28	-7	53	-13	162			-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-25	162
		-6	-84	-3070	1106	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-14	162			-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-26	162
		105	24	3091	-1085	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-15	162			326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-27	162
		3787	42	-3922	43	44	45	46	47	48	20	-38	162			1106	54	-3290	55	56	57	58	59	2025	20	-38	162
		-3747	-2	3962	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-38	20	162			-1066	-14	3330	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-1985	-38	20	162
		162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162			162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										162															
		37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	2956	-2916	162			-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	93	-53	162
		34	11	6	18	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-20	162			-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-13	162
		-117	49	25	-16	26	-4	137	230	-208	-3217	3257	162			-15	24	11	6	8	20	25	6	37	-305	345	162
		35	-1	16	27	54	-16	-15	-25	47	61	-21	162			-16	-17	29	15	14	16	-4	47	38	54	-14	162
		36	32	13	-1	-11	47	-16	-26	48	62	-22	162			-17	25	19	6	17	24	4	5	39	55	-15	162
		33	-11	20	52	-9	28	-13	-27	49	63	-23	162			-18	26	12	13	9	9	27	4	40	56	-16	162
		42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-24	162			-19	23	-1	30	22	1	18	7	41	57	-17	162
		40	-33	-3146	41	1106	2025	44	11	34	65	-25	162			-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-18	162
		-18	55	3168	-19	-1084	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-26	162			262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-19	162
		52	53	-264	54	55	56	57	58	59	20	-38	162			45	46	-3243	1106	48	2025	50	51	52	20	-38	162
		-12	-13	304	-14	-15	-16	-17	-18	-19	-38	20	162			-5	-6	3283	-1066	-8	-1985	-10	-11	-12	-38	20	162
		162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162			162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										162											
-4	36	94	19	24	-22	10	5	-25	-73	98	162	3121	-2005	-1086	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	-5	162
35	34	-64	11	6	52	20	25	55	-68	56	162	-4197	10	4217	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	-6	162
108	-78	8	24	26	10	9	19	6	-168	198	162	1106	2025	-3101	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-208	248	162
2	28	23	22	4	20	21	24	-12	43	-13	162	-3096	14	3157	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	-7	162
1	29	36	-6	9	16	17	10	20	44	-14	162	3146	36	-3107	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	-8	162
0	30	5	25	22	14	6	17	13	45	-15	162	-3087	18	19	3085	20	11	36	35	-15	49	-9	162
-1	31	4	26	11	12	19	18	12	46	-16	162	3109	4	3	-3063	2	36	11	36	-16	50	-10	162
-2	32	27	31	17	13	15	-17	16	47	-17	162	26	-2970	27	28	2900	29	30	10	42	51	-11	162
-3	33	-1	-20	13	17	15	31	47	48	-18	162	-6	2990	-7	-8	-2880	-9	-10	42	10	52	-12	162
41	45	-3185	1106	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-78	162	38	66	-73	11	6	20	25	43	44	20	-38	162
-15	-58	3215	-1076	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	149	-19	162	2	-26	113	29	34	20	15	-3	-4	-38	20	162
162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										162											
6	24	3117	-1078	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	-5	162	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	-8	162
23	22	-3089	1106	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	-6	162	6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	-9	162
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	-7	162	5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-239	281	162
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	-8	162	4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	-10	162
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-215	257	162	3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-11	162
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-9	162	2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-12	162
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-10	162	1	27	46	-3089	1106	2025	-51	16	39	55	-13	162
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-11	162	0	-18	-54	3117	-1078	-1997	31	79	40	56	-14	162
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-12	162	100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-15	162
40	63	11	6	-67	20	25	45	46	21	-48	162	4275	43	-4280	44	45	11	6	20	25	21	-48	162
2	-21	31	36	109	22	17	-3	-4	-48	21	162	-4233	-1	4322	-2	-3	31	36	22	17	-48	21	162
162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										162
	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	15	3	51	-19	162
	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	1142	-1110	162
	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-20	162
	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-21	162
	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-147	165	-1376	1408	162
	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-22	162
	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-23	162
	11	6	33	34	-66	20	25	9	58	56	-24	162
	7	12	-15	-16	84	-2	-7	58	9	57	-25	162
	1106	44	45	46	-3268	47	2025	49	50	16	2	162
	-1074	-12	-13	-14	3300	-15	-1993	-17	-18	2	16	162
	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162

11	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										162
	-20	151	39	11	6	20	25	44	-146	45	-13	162
	-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-22	162
	-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-23	162
	-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-24	162
	-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-300	332	162
	-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-25	162
	-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-26	162
	-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-27	162
	262	-133	-21	7	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-28	162
	46	47	48	1106	-3284	2025	51	52	53	16	2	162
	-14	-15	-16	-1074	3316	-1993	-19	-20	-21	2	16	162
	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162	162

■ 163rd Day of the Year - 12.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
	-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-71	97	163
	35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-67	56	163
	108	-78	12	6	8	20	25	23	9	-168	198	163
	2	28	29	15	15	16	-4	24	8	43	-13	163
	1	29	19	6	17	24	5	-18	50	44	-14	163
	0	30	12	14	9	9	27	25	7	45	-15	163
	-1	31	-1	30	22	2	18	26	6	46	-16	163
	-2	32	18	20	-1	21	22	16	7	47	-17	163
	-3	33	14	12	33	11	10	7	16	48	-18	163
	41	44	-3285	1206	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-76	163
	-14	-56	3315	-1176	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	147	-19	163
	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
	12	6	18	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-15	163
	49	25	-15	26	-4	34	-14	-23	43	1166	-1124	163
	-1	16	27	54	-15	-88	108	-24	44	-1397	1439	163
	32	14	-1	-11	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-16	163
	-11	20	52	-8	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-17	163
	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-18	163
	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-19	163
	38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-20	163
	-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-21	163
	1206	50	-3357	51	52	53	54	55	2025	21	-47	163
	-1164	-8	3399	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-1983	-47	21	163
	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
	-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-474	163
	40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	-7	163
	62	-42	12	6	18	20	25	-6	26	-691	733	163
	-14	34	29	15	15	16	6	25	-5	50	-8	163
	-15	35	19	16	17	24	5	26	-6	51	-9	163
	-16	36	12	14	9	19	27	27	-7	52	-10	163
	-17	37	9	30	22	2	18	28	-8	53	-11	163
	-1	-80	-3175	1206	21	2025	23	52	50	54	-12	163
	100	24	3195	-1186	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-13	163
	3994	42	-4120	43	44	45	46	47	48	21	-47	163
	-3952	0	4162	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-47	21	163
	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
	-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-882	924	163
	-24	12	6	18	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-19	163
	-25	49	25	-15	26	-4	34	-14	45	623	-581	163
	-26	-1	16	27	54	-15	-88	108	46	62	-20	163
	-27	32	14	-1	-11	47	35	-15	47	63	-21	163
	-28	-11	20	52	-8	28	36	-16	48	64	-22	163
	-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-23	163
	-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-24	163
	341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-25	163
	1206	54	-3381	55	56	57	58	59	2025	21	-47	163
	-1164	-12	3423	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-1983	-47	21	163
	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
	37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	3126	-3084	163
	34	12	6	8	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-18	163
	-58	49	25	-15	26	-14	88	235	-215	-3378	3420	163
	35	-1	6	27	54	-15	-5	-27	47	61	-19	163
	36	32	14	-1	-21	47	-6	-28	48	62	-20	163
	33	-21	20	52	-8	28	-3	-29	49	63	-21	163
	-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-22	163
	40	18	-3304	41	1206	2025	44	10	41	65	-23	163
	-20	2	3324	-21	-1186	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-24	163
	52	53	-255	54	55	56	57	58	59	21	-47	163
	-10	-11	297	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-47	21	163
	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
	-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	148	-96	163
	-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	-1	163
	-29	24	12	6	18	20	25	-2	37	-306	358	163
	-30	-68	29	15	15	16	6	90	38	54	-2	163
	-31	25	19	16	17	24	5	-3	39	55	-3	163
	-32	26	12	14	9	19	27	-4	40	56	-4	163
	-33	23	9	30	22	2	18	-1	41	57	-5	163
	-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	-6	163
	363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	-7	163
	45	46	-3289	1206	48	2025	50	51	52	26	-97	163
	7	6	3341	-1154	4	-1973	2	1	0	-97	26	163
	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
-4	36	95	18	24	-22	10	5	-25	-71	97	163	
35	34	-65	12	6	52	20	25	55	-67	56	163	
108	-78	10	24	25	12	11	19	2	-168	198	163	
2	28	23	22	7	20	21	30	-20	43	-13	163	
1	29	35	-3	10	14	15	13	19	44	-14	163	
0	30	7	25	18	13	8	17	15	45	-15	163	
-1	31	6	26	11	12	16	18	14	46	-16	163	
-2	32	27	37	20	13	15	-25	16	47	-17	163	
-3	33	-5	-28	12	19	17	31	57	48	-18	163	
41	44	-3285	1206	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-76	163	
-14	-56	3315	-1176	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	147	-19	163	
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
3220	-2003	-1184	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	-5	163	
-4393	11	4415	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	-6	163	
1206	2025	-3198	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-208	248	163	
-3195	14	3253	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	-7	163	
3243	34	-3205	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	-8	163	
-3191	18	19	3184	20	10	41	35	-13	49	-9	163	
3211	2	1	-3164	0	41	10	36	-14	50	-10	163	
26	-3062	27	28	2999	29	30	11	35	51	-11	163	
-4	3084	-5	-6	-2977	-7	-8	35	11	52	-12	163	
38	68	-76	12	6	20	25	43	44	20	-37	163	
2	-28	116	28	34	20	15	-3	-4	-37	20	163	
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
2	24	3219	-1182	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	-5	163	
23	22	-3195	1206	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	-6	163	
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	-7	163	
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	-8	163	
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-215	257	163	
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	-9	163	
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	-10	163	
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	-11	163	
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	-12	163	
40	50	12	6	-55	20	25	45	46	21	-47	163	
2	-8	30	36	97	22	17	-3	-4	-47	21	163	
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										163
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	-8	163	
6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	-9	163	
5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-239	281	163	
4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	-10	163	
3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	-11	163	
2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	-12	163	
1	27	31	-3195	1206	2025	-29	16	39	55	-13	163	
0	-7	-32	3219	-1182	-2001	31	53	40	56	-14	163	
101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-15	163	
4487	43	-4493	44	45	12	6	20	25	21	-47	163	
-4445	-1	4535	-2	-3	30	36	22	17	-47	21	163	
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										163
28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	15	5	51	-19	163	
-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	1241	-1209	163	
25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-20	163	
26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-21	163	
27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-140	160	-1475	1507	163	
24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-22	163	
7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-23	163	
12	6	33	34	-60	20	25	10	51	56	-24	163	
8	14	-13	-14	80	0	-5	51	10	57	-25	163	
1206	44	45	46	-3368	47	2025	49	50	16	3	163	
-1174	-12	-13	-14	3400	-15	-1993	-17	-18	3	16	163	
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	

12	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										163
-19	149	39	12	6	20	25	44	-145	45	-13	163	
-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-22	163	
-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-23	163	
-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-24	163	
-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-300	332	163	
-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-25	163	
-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-26	163	
-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-27	163	
255	-130	-20	7	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-28	163	
46	47	48	1206	-3384	2025	51	52	53	16	3	163	
-14	-15	-16	-1174	3416	-1993	-19	-20	-21	3	16	163	
163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	163	

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◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-69	96	164	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-66	56	164	
108	-78	13	6	-2	20	25	23	19	-168	198	164	
2	28	29	15	16	16	-14	24	18	43	-13	164	
1	29	19	-4	17	24	6	7	35	44	-14	164	
0	30	12	15	9	-1	27	25	17	45	-15	164	
-1	31	-11	30	22	3	18	26	16	46	-16	164	
-2	32	28	20	14	21	22	21	-22	47	-17	164	
-3	33	14	22	28	21	20	-22	21	48	-18	164	
41	43	-3385	1306	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-74	164	
-13	-54	3415	-1276	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	145	-19	164	
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	

13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
13	6	6	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-15	164	
49	25	-14	26	-16	34	-4	-21	43	1245	-1203	164	
-1	4	27	54	-14	-63	93	-22	44	-1476	1518	164	
32	15	-1	-23	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-16	164	
-23	20	52	-7	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-17	164	
6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-18	164	
24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-19	164	
38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-20	164	
-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-21	164	
1306	50	-3457	51	52	53	54	55	2025	21	-46	164	
-1264	-8	3499	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-1983	-46	21	164	
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	

13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164	13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
	-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-469	164		-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-1001	1043	164
	40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-7	164		-22	13	6	6	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-19	164
	58	-37	13	6	16	20	25	-1	22	-686	728	164		-23	49	25	-14	26	-16	34	-4	45	742	-700	164
	-13	34	29	15	16	16	4	25	-4	50	-8	164		-24	-1	4	27	54	-14	-63	93	46	62	-20	164
	-14	35	19	14	17	24	6	26	-5	51	-9	164		-25	32	15	-1	-23	47	35	-5	47	63	-21	164
	-15	36	12	15	9	17	27	27	-6	52	-10	164		-26	-23	20	52	-7	28	36	-6	48	64	-22	164
	-16	37	7	30	22	3	18	28	-7	53	-11	164		-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-23	164
	-6	-84	-3270	1306	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-12	164		-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-24	164
	105	24	3291	-1285	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-13	164		326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-25	164
	4189	42	-4315	43	44	45	46	47	48	21	-46	164		1306	54	-3481	55	56	57	58	59	2025	21	-46	164
	-4147	0	4357	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-46	21	164		-1264	-12	3523	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-1983	-46	21	164
	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164		164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164

13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164	13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
	37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	3158	-3116	164		-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	95	-53	164
	34	13	6	16	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-18	164		-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-11	164
	-117	49	25	-14	26	-6	137	230	-208	-3410	3452	164		-15	24	13	6	6	20	25	6	37	-298	340	164
	35	-1	14	27	54	-14	-15	-25	47	61	-19	164		-16	-17	29	15	16	16	-6	47	38	54	-12	164
	36	32	15	-1	-13	47	-16	-26	48	62	-20	164		-17	25	19	4	17	24	6	5	39	55	-13	164
	33	-13	20	52	-7	28	-13	-27	49	63	-21	164		-18	26	12	15	9	7	27	4	40	56	-14	164
	42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-22	164		-19	23	-3	30	22	3	18	7	41	57	-15	164
	40	-33	-3346	41	1306	2025	44	11	34	65	-23	164		-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-16	164
	-18	55	3368	-19	-1284	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-24	164		262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-17	164
	52	53	-255	54	55	56	57	58	59	21	-46	164		45	46	-3434	1306	48	2025	50	51	52	21	-46	164
	-10	-11	297	-12	-13	-14	-15	-16	-17	-46	21	164		-3	-4	3476	-1264	-6	-1983	-8	-9	-10	-46	21	164
	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164		164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
-4	36	96	17	24	-22	10	5	-25	-69	96	164	
35	34	-66	13	6	52	20	25	55	-66	56	164	
108	-78	6	24	27	8	7	19	13	-168	198	164	
2	28	23	22	1	20	21	15	2	43	-13	164	
1	29	37	-9	7	20	21	7	21	44	-14	164	
0	30	3	25	30	16	2	17	11	45	-15	164	
-1	31	2	26	11	12	25	18	10	46	-16	164	
-2	32	27	22	14	13	15	-3	16	47	-17	164	
-3	33	6	-6	14	15	13	31	31	48	-18	164	
41	43	-3385	1306	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-74	164	
-13	-54	3415	-1276	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	145	-19	164	
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	

13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
3321	-2005	-1286	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	-3	164	
-4597	10	4617	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	-4	164	
1306	2025	-3301	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-199	241	164	
-3296	14	3357	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	-5	164	
3346	36	-3307	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	-6	164	
-3287	18	19	3285	20	11	36	35	-15	49	-7	164	
3309	4	3	-3263	2	36	11	36	-16	50	-8	164	
26	-3170	27	28	3100	29	30	10	42	51	-9	164	
-6	3190	-7	-8	-3080	-9	-10	42	10	52	-10	164	
38	64	-64	13	6	20	25	43	44	21	-46	164	
4	-22	106	29	36	22	17	-1	-2	-46	21	164	
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	

13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
6	24	3317	-1278	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	-3	164	
23	22	-3289	1306	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	-4	164	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	-5	164	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	-6	164	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-206	250	164	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-7	164	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-8	164	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-9	164	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-10	164	
40	61	13	6	-58	20	25	45	46	22	-56	164	
4	-17	31	38	102	24	19	-1	-2	-56	22	164	
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	

13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										164
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	-6	164	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	-7	164	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-230	274	164	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	-8	164	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-9	164	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-10	164	
1	27	46	-3289	1306	2025	-51	16	39	55	-11	164	
0	-18	-54	3317	-1278	-1997	31	79	40	56	-12	164	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-13	164	
4677	43	-4675	44	45	13	6	20	25	22	-56	164	
-4633	1	4719	0	-1	31	38	24	19	-56	22	164	
164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	

13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										164
	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	13	5	51	-17	164
	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	1340	-1306	164
	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-18	164
	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-19	164
	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-145	163	-1565	1599	164
	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-20	164
	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-21	164
	13	6	33	34	-68	20	25	9	58	56	-22	164
	5	12	-15	-16	86	-2	-7	58	9	57	-23	164
	1306	44	45	46	-3459	47	2025	49	50	17	-6	164
	-1272	-10	-11	-12	3493	-13	-1991	-15	-16	-6	17	164
	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164

13	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										164
	-20	149	39	13	6	20	25	44	-146	47	-13	164
	-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-20	164
	-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-21	164
	-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-22	164
	-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-293	327	164
	-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-23	164
	-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-24	164
	-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-25	164
	262	-131	-21	5	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-26	164
	46	47	48	1306	-3475	2025	51	52	53	17	-6	164
	-12	-13	-14	-1272	3509	-1991	-17	-18	-19	-6	17	164
	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164	164

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◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
	-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-67	95	165
	35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-65	56	165
	108	-78	14	6	6	20	25	23	11	-168	198	165
	2	28	29	15	17	16	-6	24	10	43	-13	165
	1	29	19	4	17	24	7	-13	47	44	-14	165
	0	30	12	16	9	7	27	25	9	45	-15	165
	-1	31	-3	30	22	4	18	26	8	46	-16	165
	-2	32	20	20	2	21	22	17	3	47	-17	165
	-3	33	14	14	32	13	12	3	17	48	-18	165
	41	42	-3485	1406	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-72	165
	-12	-52	3515	-1376	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	143	-19	165
	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
	14	6	16	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-13	165
	49	25	-13	26	-6	34	-14	-23	43	1364	-1320	165
	-1	14	27	54	-13	-88	108	-24	44	-1586	1630	165
	32	16	-1	-13	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-14	165
	-13	20	52	-6	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-15	165
	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-16	165
	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-17	165
	38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-18	165
	-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-19	165
	1406	50	-3548	51	52	53	54	55	2025	22	-55	165
	-1362	-6	3592	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-1981	-55	22	165
	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
	-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-472	165
	40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	-5	165
	62	-42	14	6	16	20	25	-6	26	-682	726	165
	-14	34	29	15	17	16	4	25	-5	50	-6	165
	-15	35	19	14	17	24	7	26	-6	51	-7	165
	-16	36	12	16	9	17	27	27	-7	52	-8	165
	-17	37	7	30	22	4	18	28	-8	53	-9	165
	-1	-80	-3375	1406	21	2025	23	52	50	54	-10	165
	100	24	3395	-1386	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-11	165
	4396	42	-4513	43	44	45	46	47	48	22	-55	165
	-4352	2	4557	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-55	22	165
	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
	-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-1080	1124	165
	-24	14	6	16	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-17	165
	-25	49	25	-13	26	-6	34	-14	45	830	-786	165
	-26	-1	14	27	54	-13	-88	108	46	62	-18	165
	-27	32	16	-1	-13	47	35	-15	47	63	-19	165
	-28	-13	20	52	-6	28	36	-16	48	64	-20	165
	-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-21	165
	-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-22	165
	341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-23	165
	1406	54	-3572	55	56	57	58	59	2025	22	-55	165
	-1362	-10	3616	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-1981	-55	22	165
	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
	37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	3328	-3284	165
	34	14	6	6	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-16	165
	-58	49	25	-13	26	-16	88	235	-215	-3571	3615	165
	35	-1	4	27	54	-13	-5	-27	47	61	-17	165
	36	32	16	-1	-23	47	-6	-28	48	62	-18	165
	33	-23	20	52	-6	28	-3	-29	49	63	-19	165
	-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-20	165
	40	18	-3504	41	1406	2025	44	10	41	65	-21	165
	-20	2	3524	-21	-1386	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-22	165
	52	53	-246	54	55	56	57	58	59	22	-55	165
	-8	-9	290	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-55	22	165
	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
	-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	150	-96	165
	-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	1	165
	-29	24	14	6	16	20	25	-2	37	-299	353	165
	-30	-68	29	15	17	16	4	90	38	54	0	165
	-31	25	19	14	17	24	7	-3	39	55	-1	165
	-32	26	12	16	9	17	27	-4	40	56	-2	165
	-33	23	7	30	22	4	18	-1	41	57	-3	165
	-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	-4	165
	363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	-5	165
	45	46	-3480	1406	48	2025	50	51	52	27	-105	165
	9	8	3534	-1352	6	-1971	4	3	2	-105	27	165
	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
-2	36	92	18	26	-20	12	7	-23	-85	104	165	
35	34	-60	14	6	52	20	25	55	-72	56	165	
103	-71	6	24	27	8	7	19	10	-161	193	165	
4	28	23	22	1	20	21	18	-4	43	-11	165	
3	29	37	-9	8	18	19	7	21	44	-12	165	
2	30	3	25	26	15	4	17	11	45	-13	165	
1	31	2	26	11	12	22	18	10	46	-14	165	
0	32	27	25	14	13	15	-9	16	47	-15	165	
-1	33	3	-12	14	15	13	31	37	48	-16	165	
41	53	-3478	1406	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-90	165	
-21	-70	3510	-1374	-6	-7	-8	-1993	-10	161	-17	165	
165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
3420	-2003	-1384	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	-3	165	
-4793	11	4815	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	-4	165	
1406	2025	-3398	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-199	241	165	
-3395	14	3453	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	-5	165	
3443	34	-3405	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	-6	165	
-3391	18	19	3384	20	10	41	35	-13	49	-7	165	
3411	2	1	-3364	0	41	10	36	-14	50	-8	165	
26	-3262	27	28	3199	29	30	11	35	51	-9	165	
-4	3284	-5	-6	-3177	-7	-8	35	11	52	-10	165	
38	66	-67	14	6	20	25	43	44	21	-45	165	
4	-24	109	28	36	22	17	-1	-2	-45	21	165	
165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
2	24	3419	-1382	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	-3	165	
23	22	-3395	1406	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	-4	165	
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	-5	165	
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	-6	165	
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-206	250	165	
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	-7	165	
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	-8	165	
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	-9	165	
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	-10	165	
40	48	14	6	-46	20	25	45	46	22	-55	165	
4	-4	30	38	90	24	19	-1	-2	-55	22	165	
165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										165
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	-6	165	
6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	-7	165	
5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-230	274	165	
4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	-8	165	
3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	-9	165	
2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	-10	165	
1	27	31	-3395	1406	2025	-29	16	39	55	-11	165	
0	-7	-32	3419	-1382	-2001	31	53	40	56	-12	165	
101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-13	165	
4889	43	-4888	44	45	14	6	20	25	22	-55	165	
-4845	1	4932	0	-1	30	38	24	19	-55	22	165	
165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										165
	28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	13	7	51	-17	165
	-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	1439	-1405	165
	25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-18	165
	26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-19	165
	27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-138	158	-1664	1698	165
	24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-20	165
	7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-21	165
	14	6	33	34	-62	20	25	10	51	56	-22	165
	6	14	-13	-14	82	0	-5	51	10	57	-23	165
	1406	44	45	46	-3559	47	2025	49	50	17	-5	165
	-1372	-10	-11	-12	3593	-13	-1991	-15	-16	-5	17	165
	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165

14	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										165
	-19	147	39	14	6	20	25	44	-145	47	-13	165
	-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-20	165
	-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-21	165
	-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-22	165
	-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-293	327	165
	-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-23	165
	-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-24	165
	-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-25	165
	255	-128	-20	5	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-26	165
	46	47	48	1406	-3575	2025	51	52	53	17	-5	165
	-12	-13	-14	-1372	3609	-1991	-17	-18	-19	-5	17	165
	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165	165

■ 166th Day of the Year - 15.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166
	-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-65	94	166
	35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-64	56	166
	108	-78	15	6	-4	20	25	23	21	-168	198	166
	2	28	29	15	18	16	-16	24	20	43	-13	166
	1	29	19	-6	17	24	8	12	32	44	-14	166
	0	30	12	17	9	-3	27	25	19	45	-15	166
	-1	31	-13	30	22	5	18	26	18	46	-16	166
	-2	32	30	20	17	21	22	22	-26	47	-17	166
	-3	33	14	24	27	23	22	-26	22	48	-18	166
	41	41	-3585	1506	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-70	166
	-11	-50	3615	-1476	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	141	-19	166
	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166
	15	6	4	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-13	166
	49	25	-12	26	-18	34	-4	-21	43	1443	-1399	166
	-1	2	27	54	-12	-63	93	-22	44	-1665	1709	166
	32	17	-1	-25	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-14	166
	-25	20	52	-5	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-15	166
	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-16	166
	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-17	166
	38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-18	166
	-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-19	166
	1506	50	-3648	51	52	53	54	55	2025	22	-54	166
	-1462	-6	3692	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-1981	-54	22	166
	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166	
		-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-467	166
		40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-5	166
		58	-37	15	6	14	20	25	-1	22	-677	721	166
		-13	34	29	15	18	16	2	25	-4	50	-6	166
		-14	35	19	12	17	24	8	26	-5	51	-7	166
		-15	36	12	17	9	15	27	27	-6	52	-8	166
		-16	37	5	30	22	5	18	28	-7	53	-9	166
		-6	-84	-3470	1506	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-10	166
		105	24	3491	-1485	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-11	166
		4591	42	-4708	43	44	45	46	47	48	22	-54	166
		-4547	2	4752	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-54	22	166
		166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166	
		-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-1199	1243	166
		-22	15	6	4	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-17	166
		-23	49	25	-12	26	-18	34	-4	45	949	-905	166
		-24	-1	2	27	54	-12	-63	93	46	62	-18	166
		-25	32	17	-1	-25	47	35	-5	47	63	-19	166
		-26	-25	20	52	-5	28	36	-6	48	64	-20	166
		-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-21	166
		-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-22	166
		326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-23	166
		1506	54	-3672	55	56	57	58	59	2025	22	-54	166
		-1462	-10	3716	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-1981	-54	22	166
		166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166	
		37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	3360	-3316	166
		34	15	6	14	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-16	166
		-117	49	25	-12	26	-8	137	230	-208	-3603	3647	166
		35	-1	12	27	54	-12	-15	-25	47	61	-17	166
		36	32	17	-1	-15	47	-16	-26	48	62	-18	166
		33	-15	20	52	-5	28	-13	-27	49	63	-19	166
		42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-20	166
		40	-33	-3546	41	1506	2025	44	11	34	65	-21	166
		-18	55	3568	-19	-1484	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-22	166
		52	53	-246	54	55	56	57	58	59	22	-54	166
		-8	-9	290	-10	-11	-12	-13	-14	-15	-54	22	166
		166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166	
		-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	97	-53	166
		-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-9	166
		-15	24	15	6	4	20	25	6	37	-291	335	166
		-16	-17	29	15	18	16	-8	47	38	54	-10	166
		-17	25	19	2	17	24	8	5	39	55	-11	166
		-18	26	12	17	9	5	27	4	40	56	-12	166
		-19	23	-5	30	22	5	18	7	41	57	-13	166
		-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-14	166
		262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-15	166
		45	46	-3625	1506	48	2025	50	51	52	22	-54	166
		-1	-2	3669	-1462	-4	-1981	-6	-7	-8	-54	22	166
		166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166
-4	36	98	15	24	-22	10	5	-25	-65	94	166	
35	34	-68	15	6	52	20	25	55	-64	56	166	
108	-78	10	24	25	12	11	19	5	-168	198	166	
2	28	23	22	7	20	21	27	-14	43	-13	166	
1	29	35	-3	9	16	17	13	19	44	-14	166	
0	30	7	25	22	14	6	17	15	45	-15	166	
-1	31	6	26	11	12	19	18	14	46	-16	166	
-2	32	27	34	20	13	15	-19	16	47	-17	166	
-3	33	-2	-22	12	19	17	31	51	48	-18	166	
41	41	-3585	1506	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-70	166	
-11	-50	3615	-1476	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	141	-19	166	
166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166
3521	-2005	-1486	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	-1	166	
-4997	10	5017	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	-2	166	
1506	2025	-3501	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-190	234	166	
-3496	14	3557	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	-3	166	
3546	36	-3507	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	-4	166	
-3487	18	19	3485	20	11	36	35	-15	49	-5	166	
3509	4	3	-3463	2	36	11	36	-16	50	-6	166	
26	-3370	27	28	3300	29	30	10	42	51	-7	166	
-6	3390	-7	-8	-3280	-9	-10	42	10	52	-8	166	
38	62	-55	15	6	20	25	43	44	22	-54	166	
6	-18	99	29	38	24	19	1	0	-54	22	166	
166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166
6	24	3517	-1478	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	-1	166	
23	22	-3489	1506	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	-2	166	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	-3	166	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	-4	166	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-197	243	166	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-5	166	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-6	166	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-7	166	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-8	166	
40	59	15	6	-49	20	25	45	46	23	-64	166	
6	-13	31	40	95	26	21	1	0	-64	23	166	
166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										166
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	-4	166	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	-5	166	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-221	267	166	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	-6	166	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-7	166	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-8	166	
1	27	46	-3489	1506	2025	-51	16	39	55	-9	166	
0	-18	-54	3517	-1478	-1997	31	79	40	56	-10	166	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-11	166	
5079	43	-5070	44	45	15	6	20	25	23	-64	166	
-5033	3	5116	2	1	31	40	26	21	-64	23	166	
166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										166
	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	11	7	51	-15	166
	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	1538	-1502	166
	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-16	166
	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-17	166
	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-143	161	-1754	1790	166
	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-18	166
	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-19	166
	15	6	33	34	-70	20	25	9	58	56	-20	166
	3	12	-15	-16	88	-2	-7	58	9	57	-21	166
	1506	44	45	46	-3650	47	2025	49	50	18	-14	166
	-1470	-8	-9	-10	3686	-11	-1989	-13	-14	-14	18	166
	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166

15	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										166
	-20	147	39	15	6	20	25	44	-146	49	-13	166
	-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-18	166
	-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-19	166
	-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-20	166
	-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-286	322	166
	-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-21	166
	-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-22	166
	-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-23	166
	262	-129	-21	3	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-24	166
	46	47	48	1506	-3666	2025	51	52	53	18	-14	166
	-10	-11	-12	-1470	3702	-1989	-15	-16	-17	-14	18	166
	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166

■ 167th Day of the Year - 16.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

16	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167
	-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-63	93	167
	35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-63	56	167
	108	-78	16	6	4	20	25	23	13	-168	198	167
	2	28	29	15	19	16	-8	24	12	43	-13	167
	1	29	19	2	17	24	9	-8	44	44	-14	167
	0	30	12	18	9	5	27	25	11	45	-15	167
	-1	31	-5	30	22	6	18	26	10	46	-16	167
	-2	32	22	20	5	21	22	18	-1	47	-17	167
	-3	33	14	16	31	15	14	-1	18	48	-18	167
	41	40	-3685	1606	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-68	167
	-10	-48	3715	-1576	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	139	-19	167
	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167

16	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167
	16	6	14	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-11	167
	49	25	-11	26	-8	34	-14	-23	43	1562	-1516	167
	-1	12	27	54	-11	-88	108	-24	44	-1775	1821	167
	32	18	-1	-15	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-12	167
	-15	20	52	-4	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-13	167
	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-14	167
	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-15	167
	38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-16	167
	-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-17	167
	1606	50	-3739	51	52	53	54	55	2025	23	-63	167
	-1560	-4	3785	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-1979	-63	23	167
	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167

16	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167
-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-470	167	
40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	-3	167	
62	-42	16	6	14	20	25	-6	26	-673	719	167	
-14	34	29	15	19	16	2	25	-5	50	-4	167	
-15	35	19	12	17	24	9	26	-6	51	-5	167	
-16	36	12	18	9	15	27	27	-7	52	-6	167	
-17	37	5	30	22	6	18	28	-8	53	-7	167	
-1	-80	-3575	1606	21	2025	23	52	50	54	-8	167	
100	24	3595	-1586	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-9	167	
4798	42	-4906	43	44	45	46	47	48	23	-63	167	
-4752	4	4952	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-63	23	167	
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	

16	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167
-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-1278	1324	167	
-24	16	6	14	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-15	167	
-25	49	25	-11	26	-8	34	-14	45	1037	-991	167	
-26	-1	12	27	54	-11	-88	108	46	62	-16	167	
-27	32	18	-1	-15	47	35	-15	47	63	-17	167	
-28	-15	20	52	-4	28	36	-16	48	64	-18	167	
-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-19	167	
-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-20	167	
341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-21	167	
1606	54	-3763	55	56	57	58	59	2025	23	-63	167	
-1560	-8	3809	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-1979	-63	23	167	
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	

16	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167
37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	3530	-3484	167	
34	16	6	4	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-14	167	
-58	49	25	-11	26	-18	88	235	-215	-3764	3810	167	
35	-1	2	27	54	-11	-5	-27	47	61	-15	167	
36	32	18	-1	-25	47	-6	-28	48	62	-16	167	
33	-25	20	52	-4	28	-3	-29	49	63	-17	167	
-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-18	167	
40	18	-3704	41	1606	2025	44	10	41	65	-19	167	
-20	2	3724	-21	-1586	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-20	167	
52	53	-237	54	55	56	57	58	59	23	-63	167	
-6	-7	283	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-63	23	167	
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	

16	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167
-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	152	-96	167	
-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	3	167	
-29	24	16	6	14	20	25	-2	37	-292	348	167	
-30	-68	29	15	19	16	2	90	38	54	2	167	
-31	25	19	12	17	24	9	-3	39	55	1	167	
-32	26	12	18	9	15	27	-4	40	56	0	167	
-33	23	5	30	22	6	18	-1	41	57	-1	167	
-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	-2	167	
363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	-3	167	
45	46	-3671	1606	48	2025	50	51	52	28	-113	167	
11	10	3727	-1550	8	-1969	6	5	4	-113	28	167	
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

16	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167											
-2	36	94	16	26	-20	12	7	-23	-81	102	167	3620	-2003	-1584	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	-1	167
35	34	-62	16	6	52	20	25	55	-70	56	167	-5193	11	5215	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	-2	167
103	-71	10	24	25	12	11	19	2	-161	193	167	1606	2025	-3598	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-190	234	167
4	28	23	22	7	20	21	30	-20	43	-11	167	-3595	14	3653	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	-3	167
3	29	35	-3	10	14	15	13	19	44	-12	167	3643	34	-3605	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	-4	167
2	30	7	25	18	13	8	17	15	45	-13	167	-3591	18	19	3584	20	10	41	35	-13	49	-5	167
1	31	6	26	11	12	16	18	14	46	-14	167	3611	2	1	-3564	0	41	10	36	-14	50	-6	167
0	32	27	37	20	13	15	-25	16	47	-15	167	26	-3462	27	28	3399	29	30	11	35	51	-7	167
-1	33	-5	-28	12	19	17	31	57	48	-16	167	-4	3484	-5	-6	-3377	-7	-8	35	11	52	-8	167
41	51	-3678	1606	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-86	167	38	64	-58	16	6	20	25	43	44	22	-53	167
-19	-66	3710	-1574	-6	-7	-8	-1993	-10	157	-17	167	6	-20	102	28	38	24	19	1	0	-53	22	167
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167

16	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										167											
2	24	3619	-1582	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	-1	167	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	-4	167
23	22	-3595	1606	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	-2	167	6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	-5	167
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	-3	167	5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-221	267	167
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	-4	167	4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	-6	167
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-197	243	167	3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	-7	167
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	-5	167	2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	-8	167
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	-6	167	1	27	31	-3595	1606	2025	-29	16	39	55	-9	167
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	-7	167	0	-7	-32	3619	-1582	-2001	31	53	40	56	-10	167
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	-8	167	101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-11	167
40	46	16	6	-37	20	25	45	46	23	-63	167	5291	43	-5283	44	45	16	6	20	25	23	-63	167
6	0	30	40	83	26	21	1	0	-63	23	167	-5245	3	5329	2	1	30	40	26	21	-63	23	167
167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167

16	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										167	16	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										167		
		28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	11	9	51	-15	167			-19	145	39	16	6	20	25	44	-145	49	-13	167
		-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	1637	-1601	167			-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-18	167
		25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-16	167			-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-19	167
		26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-17	167			-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-20	167
		27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-136	156	-1853	1889	167			-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-286	322	167
		24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-18	167			-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-21	167
		7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-19	167			-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-22	167
		16	6	33	34	-64	20	25	10	51	56	-20	167			-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-23	167
		4	14	-13	-14	84	0	-5	51	10	57	-21	167			255	-126	-20	3	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-24	167
		1606	44	45	46	-3750	47	2025	49	50	18	-13	167			46	47	48	1606	-3766	2025	51	52	53	18	-13	167
		-1570	-8	-9	-10	3786	-11	-1989	-13	-14	-13	18	167			-10	-11	-12	-1570	3802	-1989	-15	-16	-17	-13	18	167
		167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167			167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167	167

■ 168th Day of the Year - 17.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168	17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168		
		-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-61	92	168			17	6	2	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-11	168
		35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-62	56	168			49	25	-10	26	-20	34	-4	-21	43	1641	-1595	168
		108	-78	17	6	-6	20	25	23	23	-168	198	168			-1	0	27	54	-10	-63	93	-22	44	-1854	1900	168
		2	28	29	15	20	16	-18	24	22	43	-13	168			32	19	-1	-27	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-12	168
		1	29	19	-8	17	24	10	17	29	44	-14	168			-27	20	52	-3	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-13	168
		0	30	12	19	9	-5	27	25	21	45	-15	168			6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-14	168
		-1	31	-15	30	22	7	18	26	20	46	-16	168			24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-15	168
		-2	32	32	20	20	21	22	23	-30	47	-17	168			38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-16	168
		-3	33	14	26	26	25	24	-30	23	48	-18	168			-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-17	168
		41	39	-3785	1706	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-66	168			1706	50	-3839	51	52	53	54	55	2025	23	-62	168
		-9	-46	3815	-1676	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	137	-19	168			-1660	-4	3885	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-1979	-62	23	168
		168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168			168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
	-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-465	168
	40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-3	168
	58	-37	17	6	12	20	25	-1	22	-668	714	168
	-13	34	29	15	20	16	0	25	-4	50	-4	168
	-14	35	19	10	17	24	10	26	-5	51	-5	168
	-15	36	12	19	9	13	27	27	-6	52	-6	168
	-16	37	3	30	22	7	18	28	-7	53	-7	168
	-6	-84	-3670	1706	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-8	168
	105	24	3691	-1685	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-9	168
	4993	42	-5101	43	44	45	46	47	48	23	-62	168
	-4947	4	5147	3	2	1	0	-1	-2	-62	23	168
	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
	-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-1397	1443	168
	-22	17	6	2	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-15	168
	-23	49	25	-10	26	-20	34	-4	45	1156	-1110	168
	-24	-1	0	27	54	-10	-63	93	46	62	-16	168
	-25	32	19	-1	-27	47	35	-5	47	63	-17	168
	-26	-27	20	52	-3	28	36	-6	48	64	-18	168
	-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-19	168
	-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-20	168
	326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-21	168
	1706	54	-3863	55	56	57	58	59	2025	23	-62	168
	-1660	-8	3909	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-1979	-62	23	168
	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
	37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	3562	-3516	168
	34	17	6	12	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-14	168
	-117	49	25	-10	26	-10	137	230	-208	-3796	3842	168
	35	-1	10	27	54	-10	-15	-25	47	61	-15	168
	36	32	19	-1	-17	47	-16	-26	48	62	-16	168
	33	-17	20	52	-3	28	-13	-27	49	63	-17	168
	42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-18	168
	40	-33	-3746	41	1706	2025	44	11	34	65	-19	168
	-18	55	3768	-19	-1684	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-20	168
	52	53	-237	54	55	56	57	58	59	23	-62	168
	-6	-7	283	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	-62	23	168
	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
	-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	99	-53	168
	-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-7	168
	-15	24	17	6	2	20	25	6	37	-284	330	168
	-16	-17	29	15	20	16	-10	47	38	54	-8	168
	-17	25	19	0	17	24	10	5	39	55	-9	168
	-18	26	12	19	9	3	27	4	40	56	-10	168
	-19	23	-7	30	22	7	18	7	41	57	-11	168
	-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-12	168
	262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-13	168
	45	46	-3816	1706	48	2025	50	51	52	23	-62	168
	1	0	3862	-1660	-2	-1979	-4	-5	-6	-62	23	168
	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168

◆ **With Magic Squares of Order 3**

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
	-4 36	100	13	24	-22	10	5	-25	-61	92	168	
	35 34	-70	17	6	52	20	25	55	-62	56	168	
	108 -78	8	24	26	10	9	19	12	-168	198	168	
	2 28	23	22	4	20	21	18	0	43	-13	168	
	1 29	36	-6	7	20	21	10	20	44	-14	168	
	0 30	5	25	30	16	2	17	13	45	-15	168	
	-1 31	4	26	11	12	25	18	12	46	-16	168	
	-2 32	27	25	17	13	15	-5	16	47	-17	168	
	-3 33	5	-8	13	17	15	31	35	48	-18	168	
	41 39	-3785	1706	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-66	168	
	-9 -46	3815	-1676	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	137	-19	168	
	168 168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
	3721 -2005 -1686	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	1	168		
	-5397 10 5417	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	0	168		
	1706 2025 -3701	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-181	227	168		
	-3696 14 3757	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	-1	168		
	3746 36 -3707	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	-2	168		
	-3687 18 19 3685 20	11	36	35	-15	49	-3	168				
	3709 4 3 -3663 2	36	11	36	-16	50	-4	168				
	26 -3570 27 28 3500 29 30	10	42	51	-5	168						
	-6 3590 -7 -8 -3480 -9 -10	42	10	52	-6	168						
	38 60 -46 17 6 20 25	43	44	23	-62	168						
	8 -14 92 29 40 26 21 3 2	-62	23	168								
	168 168 168 168 168 168 168 168 168 168 168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
	6 24	3717	-1678	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	1	168	
	23 22	-3689	1706	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	0	168	
	37 -9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	-1	168	
	3 25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	-2	168	
	2 26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-188	236	168	
	27 46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-3	168	
	-18 -54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-4	168	
	28 -1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-5	168	
	12 41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-6	168	
	40 57	17	6	-40	20	25	45	46	24	-72	168	
	8 -9	31	42	88	28	23	3	2	-72	24	168	
	168 168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										168
	-1 118 28 29 30 31 32 33 -180	50	-2	168								
	6 6 24 27 8 7 19 -11	34	51	-3	168							
	5 23 22 1 20 21 39 -46	35	-212	260	168							
	4 37 -9 15 4 5 7 21	36	52	-4	168							
	3 3 25 -2 8 18 17 11	37	53	-5	168							
	2 2 26 11 12 1 18 10	38	54	-6	168							
	1 27 46 -3689 1706 2025 -51 16	39	55	-7	168							
	0 -18 -54 3717 -1678 -1997 31 79	40	56	-8	168							
	100 -78 12 11 10 9 8 7 41	57	-9	168								
	5481 43 -5465 44 45 17 6 20 25	24	-72	168								
	-5433 5 5513 4 3 31 42 28 23	-72	24	168								
	168 168 168 168 168 168 168 168 168 168 168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										168
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	9	9	51	-13	168	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	1736	-1698	168	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-14	168	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-15	168	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-141	159	-1943	1981	168	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-16	168	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-17	168	
17	6	33	34	-72	20	25	9	58	56	-18	168	
1	12	-15	-16	90	-2	-7	58	9	57	-19	168	
1706	44	45	46	-3841	47	2025	49	50	19	-22	168	
-1668	-6	-7	-8	3879	-9	-1987	-11	-12	-22	19	168	
168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	

17	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										168
-20	145	39	17	6	20	25	44	-146	51	-13	168	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-16	168	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-17	168	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-18	168	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-279	317	168	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-19	168	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-20	168	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-21	168	
262	-127	-21	1	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-22	168	
46	47	48	1706	-3857	2025	51	52	53	19	-22	168	
-8	-9	-10	-1668	3895	-1987	-13	-14	-15	-22	19	168	
168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	168	

■ 169th Day of the Year - 18.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-59	91	169	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-61	56	169	
108	-78	18	6	2	20	25	23	15	-168	198	169	
2	28	29	15	21	16	-10	24	14	43	-13	169	
1	29	19	0	17	24	11	-3	41	44	-14	169	
0	30	12	20	9	3	27	25	13	45	-15	169	
-1	31	-7	30	22	8	18	26	12	46	-16	169	
-2	32	24	20	8	21	22	19	-5	47	-17	169	
-3	33	14	18	30	17	16	-5	19	48	-18	169	
41	38	-3885	1806	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-64	169	
-8	-44	3915	-1776	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	135	-19	169	
169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169
18	6	12	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-9	169	
49	25	-9	26	-10	34	-14	-23	43	1760	-1712	169	
-1	10	27	54	-9	-88	108	-24	44	-1964	2012	169	
32	20	-1	-17	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-10	169	
-17	20	52	-2	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-11	169	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-12	169	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-13	169	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-14	169	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-15	169	
1806	50	-3930	51	52	53	54	55	2025	24	-71	169	
-1758	-2	3978	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-1977	-71	24	169	
169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169	18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169
	-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-468	169		-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-1476	1524	169
	40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	-1	169		-24	18	6	12	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-13	169
	62	-42	18	6	12	20	25	-6	26	-664	712	169		-25	49	25	-9	26	-10	34	-14	45	1244	-1196	169
	-14	34	29	15	21	16	0	25	-5	50	-2	169		-26	-1	10	27	54	-9	-88	108	46	62	-14	169
	-15	35	19	10	17	24	11	26	-6	51	-3	169		-27	32	20	-1	-17	47	35	-15	47	63	-15	169
	-16	36	12	20	9	13	27	27	-7	52	-4	169		-28	-17	20	52	-2	28	36	-16	48	64	-16	169
	-17	37	3	30	22	8	18	28	-8	53	-5	169		-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-17	169
	-1	-80	-3775	1806	21	2025	23	52	50	54	-6	169		-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-18	169
	100	24	3795	-1786	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-7	169		341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-19	169
	5200	42	-5299	43	44	45	46	47	48	24	-71	169		1806	54	-3954	55	56	57	58	59	2025	24	-71	169
	-5152	6	5347	5	4	3	2	1	0	-71	24	169		-1758	-6	4002	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-1977	-71	24	169
	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169		169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169	18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169
	37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	3732	-3684	169		-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	154	-96	169
	34	18	6	2	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-12	169		-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	5	169
	-58	49	25	-9	26	-20	88	235	-215	-3957	4005	169		-29	24	18	6	12	20	25	-2	37	-285	343	169
	35	-1	0	27	54	-9	-5	-27	47	61	-13	169		-30	-68	29	15	21	16	0	90	38	54	4	169
	36	32	20	-1	-27	47	-6	-28	48	62	-14	169		-31	25	19	10	17	24	11	-3	39	55	3	169
	33	-27	20	52	-2	28	-3	-29	49	63	-15	169		-32	26	12	20	9	13	27	-4	40	56	2	169
	-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-16	169		-33	23	3	30	22	8	18	-1	41	57	1	169
	40	18	-3904	41	1806	2025	44	10	41	65	-17	169		-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	0	169
	-20	2	3924	-21	-1786	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-18	169		363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	-1	169
	52	53	-228	54	55	56	57	58	59	24	-71	169		45	46	-3862	1806	48	2025	50	51	52	29	-121	169
	-4	-5	276	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-71	24	169		13	12	3920	-1748	10	-1967	8	7	6	-121	29	169
	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169		169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169											
-4	36	101	12	24	-22	10	5	-25	-59	91	169	3820	-2003	-1784	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	1	169
35	34	-71	18	6	52	20	25	55	-61	56	169	-5593	11	5615	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	0	169
108	-78	10	24	25	12	11	19	8	-168	198	169	1806	2025	-3798	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-181	227	169
2	28	23	22	7	20	21	24	-8	43	-13	169	-3795	14	3853	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	-1	169
1	29	35	-3	8	18	19	13	19	44	-14	169	3843	34	-3805	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	-2	169
0	30	7	25	26	15	4	17	15	45	-15	169	-3791	18	19	3784	20	10	41	35	-13	49	-3	169
-1	31	6	26	11	12	22	18	14	46	-16	169	3811	2	1	-3764	0	41	10	36	-14	50	-4	169
-2	32	27	31	20	13	15	-13	16	47	-17	169	26	-3662	27	28	3599	29	30	11	35	51	-5	169
-3	33	1	-16	12	19	17	31	45	48	-18	169	-4	3684	-5	-6	-3577	-7	-8	35	11	52	-6	169
41	38	-3885	1806	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-64	169	38	62	-49	18	6	20	25	43	44	23	-61	169
-8	-44	3915	-1776	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	135	-19	169	8	-16	95	28	40	26	21	3	2	-61	23	169
169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										169											
2	24	3819	-1782	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	1	169	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	-2	169
23	22	-3795	1806	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	0	169	6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	-3	169
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	-1	169	5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-212	260	169
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	-2	169	4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	-4	169
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-188	236	169	3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	-5	169
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	-3	169	2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	-6	169
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	-4	169	1	27	31	-3795	1806	2025	-29	16	39	55	-7	169
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	-5	169	0	-7	-32	3819	-1782	-2001	31	53	40	56	-8	169
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	-6	169	101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-9	169
40	44	18	6	-28	20	25	45	46	24	-71	169	5693	43	-5678	44	45	18	6	20	25	24	-71	169
8	4	30	42	76	28	23	3	2	-71	24	169	-5645	5	5726	4	3	30	42	28	23	-71	24	169
169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169

18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										169	18	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										169		
		28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	9	11	51	-13	169			-19	143	39	18	6	20	25	44	-145	51	-13	169
		-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	1835	-1797	169			-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-16	169
		25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-14	169			-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-17	169
		26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-15	169			-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-18	169
		27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-134	154	-2042	2080	169			-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-279	317	169
		24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-16	169			-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-19	169
		7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-17	169			-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-20	169
		18	6	33	34	-66	20	25	10	51	56	-18	169			-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-21	169
		2	14	-13	-14	86	0	-5	51	10	57	-19	169			255	-124	-20	1	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-22	169
		1806	44	45	46	-3941	47	2025	49	50	19	-21	169			46	47	48	1806	-3957	2025	51	52	53	19	-21	169
		-1768	-6	-7	-8	3979	-9	-1987	-11	-12	-21	19	169			-8	-9	-10	-1768	3995	-1987	-13	-14	-15	-21	19	169
		169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169			169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169	169

■ 170th Day of the Year - 19.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170	19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170		
		-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-57	90	170			19	6	0	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-9	170
		35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-60	56	170			49	25	-8	26	-22	34	-4	-21	43	1839	-1791	170
		108	-78	19	6	-8	20	25	23	25	-168	198	170			-1	-2	27	54	-8	-63	93	-22	44	-2043	2091	170
		2	28	29	15	22	16	-20	24	24	43	-13	170			32	21	-1	-29	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-10	170
		1	29	19	-10	17	24	12	22	26	44	-14	170			-29	20	52	-1	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-11	170
		0	30	12	21	9	-7	27	25	23	45	-15	170			6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-12	170
		-1	31	-17	30	22	9	18	26	22	46	-16	170			24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-13	170
		-2	32	34	20	23	21	22	24	-34	47	-17	170			38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-14	170
		-3	33	14	28	25	27	26	-34	24	48	-18	170			-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-15	170
		41	37	-3985	1906	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-62	170			1906	50	-4030	51	52	53	54	55	2025	24	-70	170
		-7	-42	4015	-1876	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	133	-19	170			-1858	-2	4078	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-1977	-70	24	170
		170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170			170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170	19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170	
	-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-463	170		-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-1595	1643	170	
	40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	-1	170		-22	19	6	0	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-13	170	
	58	-37	19	6	10	20	25	-1	22	-659	707	170		-23	49	25	-8	26	-22	34	-4	45	1363	-1315	170	
	-13	34	29	15	22	16	-2	25	-4	50	-2	170		-24	-1	-2	27	54	-8	-63	93	46	62	-14	170	
	-14	35	19	8	17	24	12	26	-5	51	-3	170		-25	32	21	-1	-29	47	35	-5	47	63	-15	170	
	-15	36	12	21	9	11	27	27	-6	52	-4	170		-26	-29	20	52	-1	28	36	-6	48	64	-16	170	
	-16	37	1	30	22	9	18	28	-7	53	-5	170		-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-17	170	
	-6	-84	-3870	1906	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-6	170		-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-18	170	
	105	24	3891	-1885	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-7	170		326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-19	170	
	5395	42	-5494	43	44	45	46	47	48	24	-70	170		1906	54	-4054	55	56	57	58	59	2025	24	-70	170	
	-5347	6	5542	5	4	3	2	1	0	-70	24	170		-1858	-6	4102	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-1977	-70	24	170	
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170	19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170	
	37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	3764	-3716	170		-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	101	-53	170	
	34	19	6	10	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-12	170		-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-5	170	
	-117	49	25	-8	26	-12	137	230	-208	-3989	4037	170		-15	24	19	6	0	20	25	6	37	-277	325	170	
	35	-1	8	27	54	-8	-15	-25	47	61	-13	170		-16	-17	29	15	22	16	-12	47	38	54	-6	170	
	36	32	21	-1	-19	47	-16	-26	48	62	-14	170		-17	25	19	-2	17	24	12	5	39	55	-7	170	
	33	-19	20	52	-1	28	-13	-27	49	63	-15	170		-18	26	12	21	9	1	27	4	40	56	-8	170	
	42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-16	170		-19	23	-9	30	22	9	18	7	41	57	-9	170	
	40	-33	-3946	41	1906	2025	44	11	34	65	-17	170		-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-10	170	
	-18	55	3968	-19	-1884	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-18	170		262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-11	170	
	52	53	-228	54	55	56	57	58	59	24	-70	170		45	46	-4007	1906	48	2025	50	51	52	24	-70	170	
	-4	-5	276	-6	-7	-8	-9	-10	-11	-70	24	170		3	2	4055	-1858	0	-1977	-2	-3	-4	-70	24	170	
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170		170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

◆ **With Magic Squares of Order 3**

19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170
	-4	36	102	11	24	-22	10	5	-25	-57	90	170
	35	34	-72	19	6	52	20	25	55	-60	56	170
	108	-78	6	24	27	8	7	19	19	-168	198	170
	2	28	23	22	1	20	21	9	14	43	-13	170
	1	29	37	-9	5	24	25	7	21	44	-14	170
	0	30	3	25	38	18	-2	17	11	45	-15	170
	-1	31	2	26	11	12	31	18	10	46	-16	170
	-2	32	27	16	14	13	15	9	16	47	-17	170
	-3	33	12	6	14	15	13	31	19	48	-18	170
	41	37	-3985	1906	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-62	170
	-7	-42	4015	-1876	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	133	-19	170
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170
	3921	-2005	-1886	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	3	170
	-5797	10	5817	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	2	170
	1906	2025	-3901	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-172	220	170
	-3896	14	3957	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	1	170
	3946	36	-3907	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	0	170
	-3887	18	19	3885	20	11	36	35	-15	49	-1	170
	3909	4	3	-3863	2	36	11	36	-16	50	-2	170
	26	-3770	27	28	3700	29	30	10	42	51	-3	170
	-6	3790	-7	-8	-3680	-9	-10	42	10	52	-4	170
	38	58	-37	19	6	20	25	43	44	24	-70	170
	10	-10	85	29	42	28	23	5	4	-70	24	170
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170
	6	24	3917	-1878	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	3	170
	23	22	-3889	1906	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	2	170
	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	1	170
	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	0	170
	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-179	229	170
	27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	-1	170
	-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	-2	170
	28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-3	170
	12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-4	170
	40	55	19	6	-31	20	25	45	46	25	-80	170
	10	-5	31	44	81	30	25	5	4	-80	25	170
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										170
	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	0	170
	6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	-1	170
	5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-203	253	170
	4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	-2	170
	3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-3	170
	2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-4	170
	1	27	46	-3889	1906	2025	-51	16	39	55	-5	170
	0	-18	-54	3917	-1878	-1997	31	79	40	56	-6	170
	100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-7	170
	5883	43	-5860	44	45	19	6	20	25	25	-80	170
	-5833	7	5910	6	5	31	44	30	25	-80	25	170
	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170

19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										170
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	7	11	51	-11	170	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	1934	-1894	170	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-12	170	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-13	170	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-139	157	-2132	2172	170	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-14	170	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-15	170	
19	6	33	34	-74	20	25	9	58	56	-16	170	
-1	12	-15	-16	92	-2	-7	58	9	57	-17	170	
1906	44	45	46	-4032	47	2025	49	50	20	-30	170	
-1866	-4	-5	-6	4072	-7	-1985	-9	-10	-30	20	170	
170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	

19	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										170
-20	143	39	19	6	20	25	44	-146	53	-13	170	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-14	170	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-15	170	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-16	170	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-272	312	170	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-17	170	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-18	170	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-19	170	
262	-125	-21	-1	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-20	170	
46	47	48	1906	-4048	2025	51	52	53	20	-30	170	
-6	-7	-8	-1866	4088	-1985	-11	-12	-13	-30	20	170	
170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	170	

■ 171st Day of the Year - 20.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										171
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-55	89	171	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-59	56	171	
108	-78	20	6	0	20	25	23	17	-168	198	171	
2	28	29	15	23	16	-12	24	16	43	-13	171	
1	29	19	-2	17	24	13	2	38	44	-14	171	
0	30	12	22	9	1	27	25	15	45	-15	171	
-1	31	-9	30	22	10	18	26	14	46	-16	171	
-2	32	26	20	11	21	22	20	-9	47	-17	171	
-3	33	14	20	29	19	18	-9	20	48	-18	171	
41	36	-4085	2006	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-60	171	
-6	-40	4115	-1976	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	131	-19	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										171
20	6	10	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-7	171	
49	25	-7	26	-12	34	-14	-23	43	1958	-1908	171	
-1	8	27	54	-7	-88	108	-24	44	-2153	2203	171	
32	22	-1	-19	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-8	171	
-19	20	52	0	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-9	171	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-10	171	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-11	171	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-12	171	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-13	171	
2006	50	-4121	51	52	53	54	55	2025	25	-79	171	
-1956	0	4171	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-1975	-79	25	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										171
-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-466	171	
40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	1	171	
62	-42	20	6	10	20	25	-6	26	-655	705	171	
-14	34	29	15	23	16	-2	25	-5	50	0	171	
-15	35	19	8	17	24	13	26	-6	51	-1	171	
-16	36	12	22	9	11	27	27	-7	52	-2	171	
-17	37	1	30	22	10	18	28	-8	53	-3	171	
-1	-80	-3975	2006	21	2025	23	52	50	54	-4	171	
100	24	3995	-1986	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-5	171	
5602	42	-5692	43	44	45	46	47	48	25	-79	171	
-5552	8	5742	7	6	5	4	3	2	-79	25	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										171
-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-1674	1724	171	
-24	20	6	10	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-11	171	
-25	49	25	-7	26	-12	34	-14	45	1451	-1401	171	
-26	-1	8	27	54	-7	-88	108	46	62	-12	171	
-27	32	22	-1	-19	47	35	-15	47	63	-13	171	
-28	-19	20	52	0	28	36	-16	48	64	-14	171	
-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-15	171	
-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-16	171	
341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-17	171	
2006	54	-4145	55	56	57	58	59	2025	25	-79	171	
-1956	-4	4195	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-1975	-79	25	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										171
37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	3934	-3884	171	
34	20	6	0	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-10	171	
-58	49	25	-7	26	-22	88	235	-215	-4150	4200	171	
35	-1	-2	27	54	-7	-5	-27	47	61	-11	171	
36	32	22	-1	-29	47	-6	-28	48	62	-12	171	
33	-29	20	52	0	28	-3	-29	49	63	-13	171	
-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-14	171	
40	18	-4104	41	2006	2025	44	10	41	65	-15	171	
-20	2	4124	-21	-1986	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-16	171	
52	53	-219	54	55	56	57	58	59	25	-79	171	
-2	-3	269	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-79	25	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										171
-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	156	-96	171	
-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	7	171	
-29	24	20	6	10	20	25	-2	37	-278	338	171	
-30	-68	29	15	23	16	-2	90	38	54	6	171	
-31	25	19	8	17	24	13	-3	39	55	5	171	
-32	26	12	22	9	11	27	-4	40	56	4	171	
-33	23	1	30	22	10	18	-1	41	57	3	171	
-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	2	171	
363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	1	171	
45	46	-4053	2006	48	2025	50	51	52	30	-129	171	
15	14	4113	-1946	12	-1965	10	9	8	-129	30	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										171											
-2	36	98	12	26	-20	12	7	-23	-73	98	171	4020	-2003	-1984	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	3	171
35	34	-66	20	6	52	20	25	55	-66	56	171	-5993	11	6015	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	2	171
103	-71	6	24	27	8	7	19	16	-161	193	171	2006	2025	-3998	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-172	220	171
4	28	23	22	1	20	21	12	8	43	-11	171	-3995	14	4053	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	1	171
3	29	37	-9	6	22	23	7	21	44	-12	171	4043	34	-4005	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	0	171
2	30	3	25	34	17	0	17	11	45	-13	171	-3991	18	19	3984	20	10	41	35	-13	49	-1	171
1	31	2	26	11	12	28	18	10	46	-14	171	4011	2	1	-3964	0	41	10	36	-14	50	-2	171
0	32	27	19	14	13	15	3	16	47	-15	171	26	-3862	27	28	3799	29	30	11	35	51	-3	171
-1	33	9	0	14	15	13	31	25	48	-16	171	-4	3884	-5	-6	-3777	-7	-8	35	11	52	-4	171
41	47	-4078	2006	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-78	171	38	60	-40	20	6	20	25	43	44	24	-69	171
-15	-58	4110	-1974	-6	-7	-8	-1993	-10	149	-17	171	10	-12	88	28	42	28	23	5	4	-69	24	171
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										171											
2	24	4019	-1982	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	3	171	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	0	171
23	22	-3995	2006	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	2	171	6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	-1	171
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	1	171	5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-203	253	171
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	0	171	4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	-2	171
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-179	229	171	3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	-3	171
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	-1	171	2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	-4	171
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	-2	171	1	27	31	-3995	2006	2025	-29	16	39	55	-5	171
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	-3	171	0	-7	-32	4019	-1982	-2001	31	53	40	56	-6	171
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	-4	171	101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-7	171
40	42	20	6	-19	20	25	45	46	25	-79	171	6095	43	-6073	44	45	20	6	20	25	25	-79	171
10	8	30	44	69	30	25	5	4	-79	25	171	-6045	7	6123	6	5	30	44	30	25	-79	25	171
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										171
28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	7	13	51	-11	171	
-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	2033	-1993	171	
25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-12	171	
26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-13	171	
27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-132	152	-2231	2271	171	
24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-14	171	
7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-15	171	
20	6	33	34	-68	20	25	10	51	56	-16	171	
0	14	-13	-14	88	0	-5	51	10	57	-17	171	
2006	44	45	46	-4132	47	2025	49	50	20	-29	171	
-1966	-4	-5	-6	4172	-7	-1985	-9	-10	-29	20	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										171
-19	141	39	20	6	20	25	44	-145	53	-13	171	
-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-14	171	
-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-15	171	
-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-16	171	
-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-272	312	171	
-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-17	171	
-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-18	171	
-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-19	171	
255	-122	-20	-1	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-20	171	
46	47	48	2006	-4148	2025	51	52	53	20	-29	171	
-6	-7	-8	-1966	4188	-1985	-11	-12	-13	-29	20	171	
171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	171	

■ 172nd Day of the Year - 21.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-53	88	172	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-58	56	172	
108	-78	21	6	-10	20	25	23	27	-168	198	172	
2	28	29	15	24	16	-22	24	26	43	-13	172	
1	29	19	-12	17	24	14	27	23	44	-14	172	
0	30	12	23	9	-9	27	25	25	45	-15	172	
-1	31	-19	30	22	11	18	26	24	46	-16	172	
-2	32	36	20	26	21	22	25	-38	47	-17	172	
-3	33	14	30	24	29	28	-38	25	48	-18	172	
41	35	-4185	2106	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-58	172	
-5	-38	4215	-2076	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	129	-19	172	
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	

21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
21	6	-2	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-7	172	
49	25	-6	26	-24	34	-4	-21	43	2037	-1987	172	
-1	-4	27	54	-6	-63	93	-22	44	-2232	2282	172	
32	23	-1	-31	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-8	172	
-31	20	52	1	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-9	172	
6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-10	172	
24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-11	172	
38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-12	172	
-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-13	172	
2106	50	-4221	51	52	53	54	55	2025	25	-78	172	
-2056	0	4271	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-1975	-78	25	172	
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	

21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172	21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-461	172	-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-1793	1843	172		
40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	1	172	-22	21	6	-2	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-11	172		
58	-37	21	6	8	20	25	-1	22	-650	700	172	-23	49	25	-6	26	-24	34	-4	45	1570	-1520	172		
-13	34	29	15	24	16	-4	25	-4	50	0	172	-24	-1	-4	27	54	-6	-63	93	46	62	-12	172		
-14	35	19	6	17	24	14	26	-5	51	-1	172	-25	32	23	-1	-31	47	35	-5	47	63	-13	172		
-15	36	12	23	9	9	27	27	-6	52	-2	172	-26	-31	20	52	1	28	36	-6	48	64	-14	172		
-16	37	-1	30	22	11	18	28	-7	53	-3	172	-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-15	172		
-6	-84	-4070	2106	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-4	172	-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-16	172		
105	24	4091	-2085	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-5	172	326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-17	172		
5797	42	-5887	43	44	45	46	47	48	25	-78	172	2106	54	-4245	55	56	57	58	59	2025	25	-78	172		
-5747	8	5937	7	6	5	4	3	2	-78	25	172	-2056	-4	4295	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-1975	-78	25	172		
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172			

21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172	21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	3966	-3916	172	-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	103	-53	172		
34	21	6	8	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-10	172	-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-3	172		
-117	49	25	-6	26	-14	137	230	-208	-4182	4232	172	-15	24	21	6	-2	20	25	6	37	-270	320	172		
35	-1	6	27	54	-6	-15	-25	47	61	-11	172	-16	-17	29	15	24	16	-14	47	38	54	-4	172		
36	32	23	-1	-21	47	-16	-26	48	62	-12	172	-17	25	19	-4	17	24	14	5	39	55	-5	172		
33	-21	20	52	1	28	-13	-27	49	63	-13	172	-18	26	12	23	9	-1	27	4	40	56	-6	172		
42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-14	172	-19	23	-11	30	22	11	18	7	41	57	-7	172		
40	-33	-4146	41	2106	2025	44	11	34	65	-15	172	-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-8	172		
-18	55	4168	-19	-2084	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-16	172	262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-9	172		
52	53	-219	54	55	56	57	58	59	25	-78	172	45	46	-4198	2106	48	2025	50	51	52	25	-78	172		
-2	-3	269	-4	-5	-6	-7	-8	-9	-78	25	172	5	4	4248	-2056	2	-1975	0	-1	-2	-78	25	172		
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172			

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
-4	36	104	9	24	-22	10	5	-25	-53	88	172	
35	34	-74	21	6	52	20	25	55	-58	56	172	
108	-78	10	24	25	12	11	19	11	-168	198	172	
2	28	23	22	7	20	21	21	-2	43	-13	172	
1	29	35	-3	7	20	21	13	19	44	-14	172	
0	30	7	25	30	16	2	17	15	45	-15	172	
-1	31	6	26	11	12	25	18	14	46	-16	172	
-2	32	27	28	20	13	15	-7	16	47	-17	172	
-3	33	4	-10	12	19	17	31	39	48	-18	172	
41	35	-4185	2106	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-58	172	
-5	-38	4215	-2076	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	129	-19	172	
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	

21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
4121	-2005	-2086	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	5	172	
-6197	10	6217	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	4	172	
2106	2025	-4101	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-163	213	172	
-4096	14	4157	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	3	172	
4146	36	-4107	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	2	172	
-4087	18	19	4085	20	11	36	35	-15	49	1	172	
4109	4	3	-4063	2	36	11	36	-16	50	0	172	
26	-3970	27	28	3900	29	30	10	42	51	-1	172	
-6	3990	-7	-8	-3880	-9	-10	42	10	52	-2	172	
38	56	-28	21	6	20	25	43	44	25	-78	172	
12	-6	78	29	44	30	25	7	6	-78	25	172	
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	

21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
6	24	4117	-2078	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	5	172	
23	22	-4089	2106	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	4	172	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	3	172	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	2	172	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-170	222	172	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	1	172	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	0	172	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	-1	172	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	-2	172	
40	53	21	6	-22	20	25	45	46	26	-88	172	
12	-1	31	46	74	32	27	7	6	-88	26	172	
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	

21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										172
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	2	172	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	1	172	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-194	246	172	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	0	172	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	-1	172	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	-2	172	
1	27	46	-4089	2106	2025	-51	16	39	55	-3	172	
0	-18	-54	4117	-2078	-1997	31	79	40	56	-4	172	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-5	172	
6285	43	-6255	44	45	21	6	20	25	26	-88	172	
-6233	9	6307	8	7	31	46	32	27	-88	26	172	
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	

21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										172
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	5	13	51	-9	172	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	2132	-2090	172	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-10	172	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-11	172	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-137	155	-2321	2363	172	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-12	172	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-13	172	
21	6	33	34	-76	20	25	9	58	56	-14	172	
-3	12	-15	-16	94	-2	-7	58	9	57	-15	172	
2106	44	45	46	-4223	47	2025	49	50	21	-38	172	
-2064	-2	-3	-4	4265	-5	-1983	-7	-8	-38	21	172	
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	

21	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										172
-20	141	39	21	6	20	25	44	-146	55	-13	172	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-12	172	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-13	172	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-14	172	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-265	307	172	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-15	172	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-16	172	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-17	172	
262	-123	-21	-3	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-18	172	
46	47	48	2106	-4239	2025	51	52	53	21	-38	172	
-4	-5	-6	-2064	4281	-1983	-9	-10	-11	-38	21	172	
172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	172	

■ 173rd Day of the Year - 22.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-51	87	173	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-57	56	173	
108	-78	22	6	-2	20	25	23	19	-168	198	173	
2	28	29	15	25	16	-14	24	18	43	-13	173	
1	29	19	-4	17	24	15	7	35	44	-14	173	
0	30	12	24	9	-1	27	25	17	45	-15	173	
-1	31	-11	30	22	12	18	26	16	46	-16	173	
-2	32	28	20	14	21	22	21	-13	47	-17	173	
-3	33	14	22	28	21	20	-13	21	48	-18	173	
41	34	-4285	2206	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-56	173	
-4	-36	4315	-2176	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	127	-19	173	
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
22	6	8	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-5	173	
49	25	-5	26	-14	34	-14	-23	43	2156	-2104	173	
-1	6	27	54	-5	-88	108	-24	44	-2342	2394	173	
32	24	-1	-21	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-6	173	
-21	20	52	2	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-7	173	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-8	173	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-9	173	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-10	173	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-11	173	
2206	50	-4312	51	52	53	54	55	2025	26	-87	173	
-2154	2	4364	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-1973	-87	26	173	
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-464	173	
40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	3	173	
62	-42	22	6	8	20	25	-6	26	-646	698	173	
-14	34	29	15	25	16	-4	25	-5	50	2	173	
-15	35	19	6	17	24	15	26	-6	51	1	173	
-16	36	12	24	9	9	27	27	-7	52	0	173	
-17	37	-1	30	22	12	18	28	-8	53	-1	173	
-1	-80	-4175	2206	21	2025	23	52	50	54	-2	173	
100	24	4195	-2186	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-3	173	
6004	42	-6085	43	44	45	46	47	48	26	-87	173	
-5952	10	6137	9	8	7	6	5	4	-87	26	173	
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-1872	1924	173	
-24	22	6	8	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-9	173	
-25	49	25	-5	26	-14	34	-14	45	1658	-1606	173	
-26	-1	6	27	54	-5	-88	108	46	62	-10	173	
-27	32	24	-1	-21	47	35	-15	47	63	-11	173	
-28	-21	20	52	2	28	36	-16	48	64	-12	173	
-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-13	173	
-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-14	173	
341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-15	173	
2206	54	-4336	55	56	57	58	59	2025	26	-87	173	
-2154	-2	4388	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-1973	-87	26	173	
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	4136	-4084	173	
34	22	6	-2	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-8	173	
-58	49	25	-5	26	-24	88	235	-215	-4343	4395	173	
35	-1	-4	27	54	-5	-5	-27	47	61	-9	173	
36	32	24	-1	-31	47	-6	-28	48	62	-10	173	
33	-31	20	52	2	28	-3	-29	49	63	-11	173	
-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-12	173	
40	18	-4304	41	2206	2025	44	10	41	65	-13	173	
-20	2	4324	-21	-2186	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-14	173	
52	53	-210	54	55	56	57	58	59	26	-87	173	
0	-1	262	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-87	26	173	
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	158	-96	173	
-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	9	173	
-29	24	22	6	8	20	25	-2	37	-271	333	173	
-30	-68	29	15	25	16	-4	90	38	54	8	173	
-31	25	19	6	17	24	15	-3	39	55	7	173	
-32	26	12	24	9	9	27	-4	40	56	6	173	
-33	23	-1	30	22	12	18	-1	41	57	5	173	
-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	4	173	
363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	3	173	
45	46	-4244	2206	48	2025	50	51	52	31	-137	173	
17	16	4306	-2144	14	-1963	12	11	10	-137	31	173	
173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	

◆ **With Magic Squares of Order 3**

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
	-2	36	100	10	26	-20	12	7	-23	-69	96	173
	35	34	-68	22	6	52	20	25	55	-64	56	173
	103	-71	10	24	25	12	11	19	8	-161	193	173
	4	28	23	22	7	20	21	24	-8	43	-11	173
	3	29	35	-3	8	18	19	13	19	44	-12	173
	2	30	7	25	26	15	4	17	15	45	-13	173
	1	31	6	26	11	12	22	18	14	46	-14	173
	0	32	27	31	20	13	15	-13	16	47	-15	173
	-1	33	1	-16	12	19	17	31	45	48	-16	173
	41	45	-4278	2206	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-74	173
	-13	-54	4310	-2174	-6	-7	-8	-1993	-10	145	-17	173
	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
	4220	-2003	-2184	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	5	173
	-6393	11	6415	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	4	173
	2206	2025	-4198	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-163	213	173
	-4195	14	4253	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	3	173
	4243	34	-4205	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	2	173
	-4191	18	19	4184	20	10	41	35	-13	49	1	173
	4211	2	1	-4164	0	41	10	36	-14	50	0	173
	26	-4062	27	28	3999	29	30	11	35	51	-1	173
	-4	4084	-5	-6	-3977	-7	-8	35	11	52	-2	173
	38	58	-31	22	6	20	25	43	44	25	-77	173
	12	-8	81	28	44	30	25	7	6	-77	25	173
	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
	2	24	4219	-2182	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	5	173
	23	22	-4195	2206	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	4	173
	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	3	173
	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	2	173
	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-170	222	173
	27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	1	173
	-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	0	173
	28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	-1	173
	12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	-2	173
	40	40	22	6	-10	20	25	45	46	26	-87	173
	12	12	30	46	62	32	27	7	6	-87	26	173
	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										173
	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	2	173
	6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	1	173
	5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-194	246	173
	4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	0	173
	3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	-1	173
	2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	-2	173
	1	27	31	-4195	2206	2025	-29	16	39	55	-3	173
	0	-7	-32	4219	-2182	-2001	31	53	40	56	-4	173
	101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-5	173
	6497	43	-6468	44	45	22	6	20	25	26	-87	173
	-6445	9	6520	8	7	30	46	32	27	-87	26	173
	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										173
	28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	5	15	51	-9	173
	-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	2231	-2189	173
	25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-10	173
	26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-11	173
	27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-130	150	-2420	2462	173
	24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-12	173
	7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-13	173
	22	6	33	34	-70	20	25	10	51	56	-14	173
	-2	14	-13	-14	90	0	-5	51	10	57	-15	173
	2206	44	45	46	-4323	47	2025	49	50	21	-37	173
	-2164	-2	-3	-4	4365	-5	-1983	-7	-8	-37	21	173
	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173

22	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										173
	-19	139	39	22	6	20	25	44	-145	55	-13	173
	-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-12	173
	-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-13	173
	-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-14	173
	-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-265	307	173
	-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-15	173
	-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-16	173
	-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-17	173
	255	-120	-20	-3	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-18	173
	46	47	48	2206	-4339	2025	51	52	53	21	-37	173
	-4	-5	-6	-2164	4381	-1983	-9	-10	-11	-37	21	173
	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173	173

■ 174th Day of the Year - 23.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
	-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-49	86	174
	35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-56	56	174
	108	-78	23	6	-12	20	25	23	29	-168	198	174
	2	28	29	15	26	16	-24	24	28	43	-13	174
	1	29	19	-14	17	24	16	32	20	44	-14	174
	0	30	12	25	9	-11	27	25	27	45	-15	174
	-1	31	-21	30	22	13	18	26	26	46	-16	174
	-2	32	38	20	29	21	22	26	-42	47	-17	174
	-3	33	14	32	23	31	30	-42	26	48	-18	174
	41	33	-4385	2306	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-54	174
	-3	-34	4415	-2276	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	125	-19	174
	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
	23	6	-4	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-5	174
	49	25	-4	26	-26	34	-4	-21	43	2235	-2183	174
	-1	-6	27	54	-4	-63	93	-22	44	-2421	2473	174
	32	25	-1	-33	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-6	174
	-33	20	52	3	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-7	174
	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-8	174
	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-9	174
	38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-10	174
	-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-11	174
	2306	50	-4412	51	52	53	54	55	2025	26	-86	174
	-2254	2	4464	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-1973	-86	26	174
	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174	23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
	-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-459	174		-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-1991	2043	174
	40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	3	174		-22	23	6	-4	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-9	174
	58	-37	23	6	6	20	25	-1	22	-641	693	174		-23	49	25	-4	26	-26	34	-4	45	1777	-1725	174
	-13	34	29	15	26	16	-6	25	-4	50	2	174		-24	-1	-6	27	54	-4	-63	93	46	62	-10	174
	-14	35	19	4	17	24	16	26	-5	51	1	174		-25	32	25	-1	-33	47	35	-5	47	63	-11	174
	-15	36	12	25	9	7	27	27	-6	52	0	174		-26	-33	20	52	3	28	36	-6	48	64	-12	174
	-16	37	-3	30	22	13	18	28	-7	53	-1	174		-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-13	174
	-6	-84	-4270	2306	21	2025	23	57	50	54	-2	174		-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-14	174
	105	24	4291	-2285	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-3	174		326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-15	174
	6199	42	-6280	43	44	45	46	47	48	26	-86	174		2306	54	-4436	55	56	57	58	59	2025	26	-86	174
	-6147	10	6332	9	8	7	6	5	4	-86	26	174		-2254	-2	4488	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-1973	-86	26	174
	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174		174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174	23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
	37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	4168	-4116	174		-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	105	-53	174
	34	23	6	6	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-8	174		-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	-1	174
	-117	49	25	-4	26	-16	137	230	-208	-4375	4427	174		-15	24	23	6	-4	20	25	6	37	-263	315	174
	35	-1	4	27	54	-4	-15	-25	47	61	-9	174		-16	-17	29	15	26	16	-16	47	38	54	-2	174
	36	32	25	-1	-23	47	-16	-26	48	62	-10	174		-17	25	19	-6	17	24	16	5	39	55	-3	174
	33	-23	20	52	3	28	-13	-27	49	63	-11	174		-18	26	12	25	9	-3	27	4	40	56	-4	174
	42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-12	174		-19	23	-13	30	22	13	18	7	41	57	-5	174
	40	-33	-4346	41	2306	2025	44	11	34	65	-13	174		-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-6	174
	-18	55	4368	-19	-2284	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-14	174		262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-7	174
	52	53	-210	54	55	56	57	58	59	26	-86	174		45	46	-4389	2306	48	2025	50	51	52	26	-86	174
	0	-1	262	-2	-3	-4	-5	-6	-7	-86	26	174		7	6	4441	-2254	4	-1973	2	1	0	-86	26	174
	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174		174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
-4	36	106	7	24	-22	10	5	-25	-49	86	174	
35	34	-76	23	6	52	20	25	55	-56	56	174	
108	-78	8	24	26	10	9	19	18	-168	198	174	
2	28	23	22	4	20	21	12	12	43	-13	174	
1	29	36	-6	5	24	25	10	20	44	-14	174	
0	30	5	25	38	18	-2	17	13	45	-15	174	
-1	31	4	26	11	12	31	18	12	46	-16	174	
-2	32	27	19	17	13	15	7	16	47	-17	174	
-3	33	11	4	13	17	15	31	23	48	-18	174	
41	33	-4385	2306	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-54	174	
-3	-34	4415	-2276	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	125	-19	174	
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
4321	-2005	-2286	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	7	174	
-6597	10	6617	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	6	174	
2306	2025	-4301	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-154	206	174	
-4296	14	4357	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	5	174	
4346	36	-4307	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	4	174	
-4287	18	19	4285	20	11	36	35	-15	49	3	174	
4309	4	3	-4263	2	36	11	36	-16	50	2	174	
26	-4170	27	28	4100	29	30	10	42	51	1	174	
-6	4190	-7	-8	-4080	-9	-10	42	10	52	0	174	
38	54	-19	23	6	20	25	43	44	26	-86	174	
14	-2	71	29	46	32	27	9	8	-86	26	174	
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
6	24	4317	-2278	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	7	174	
23	22	-4289	2306	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	6	174	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	5	174	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	4	174	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-161	215	174	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	3	174	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	2	174	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	1	174	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	0	174	
40	51	23	6	-13	20	25	45	46	27	-96	174	
14	3	31	48	67	34	29	9	8	-96	27	174	
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										174
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	4	174	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	3	174	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-185	239	174	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	2	174	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	1	174	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	0	174	
1	27	46	-4289	2306	2025	-51	16	39	55	-1	174	
0	-18	-54	4317	-2278	-1997	31	79	40	56	-2	174	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-3	174	
6687	43	-6650	44	45	23	6	20	25	27	-96	174	
-6633	11	6704	10	9	31	48	34	29	-96	27	174	
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										174
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	3	15	51	-7	174	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	2330	-2286	174	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-8	174	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-9	174	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-135	153	-2510	2554	174	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-10	174	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-11	174	
23	6	33	34	-78	20	25	9	58	56	-12	174	
-5	12	-15	-16	96	-2	-7	58	9	57	-13	174	
2306	44	45	46	-4414	47	2025	49	50	22	-46	174	
-2262	0	-1	-2	4458	-3	-1981	-5	-6	-46	22	174	
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										174
-20	139	39	23	6	20	25	44	-146	57	-13	174	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-10	174	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-11	174	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-12	174	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-258	302	174	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-13	174	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-14	174	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-15	174	
262	-121	-21	-5	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-16	174	
46	47	48	2306	-4430	2025	51	52	53	22	-46	174	
-2	-3	-4	-2262	4474	-1981	-7	-8	-9	-46	22	174	
174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	174	

■ 175th Day of the Year - 24.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

24	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-47	85	175	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-55	56	175	
108	-78	24	6	-4	20	25	23	21	-168	198	175	
2	28	29	15	27	16	-16	24	20	43	-13	175	
1	29	19	-6	17	24	17	12	32	44	-14	175	
0	30	12	26	9	-3	27	25	19	45	-15	175	
-1	31	-13	30	22	14	18	26	18	46	-16	175	
-2	32	30	20	17	21	22	22	-17	47	-17	175	
-3	33	14	24	27	23	22	-17	22	48	-18	175	
41	32	-4485	2406	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-52	175	
-2	-32	4515	-2376	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	123	-19	175	
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	

24	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175
24	6	6	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-3	175	
49	25	-3	26	-16	34	-14	-23	43	2354	-2300	175	
-1	4	27	54	-3	-88	108	-24	44	-2531	2585	175	
32	26	-1	-23	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-4	175	
-23	20	52	4	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-5	175	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-6	175	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-7	175	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-8	175	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-9	175	
2406	50	-4503	51	52	53	54	55	2025	27	-95	175	
-2352	4	4557	3	2	1	0	-1	-1971	-95	27	175	
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	

24	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175	24	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175		
		-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-462	175			-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-2070	2124	175
		40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	5	175			-24	24	6	6	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-7	175
		62	-42	24	6	6	20	25	-6	26	-637	691	175			-25	49	25	-3	26	-16	34	-14	45	1865	-1811	175
		-14	34	29	15	27	16	-6	25	-5	50	4	175			-26	-1	4	27	54	-3	-88	108	46	62	-8	175
		-15	35	19	4	17	24	17	26	-6	51	3	175			-27	32	26	-1	-23	47	35	-15	47	63	-9	175
		-16	36	12	26	9	7	27	27	-7	52	2	175			-28	-23	20	52	4	28	36	-16	48	64	-10	175
		-17	37	-3	30	22	14	18	28	-8	53	1	175			-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-11	175
		-1	-80	-4375	2406	21	2025	23	52	50	54	0	175			-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-12	175
		100	24	4395	-2386	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	-1	175			341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-13	175
		6406	42	-6478	43	44	45	46	47	48	27	-95	175			2406	54	-4527	55	56	57	58	59	2025	27	-95	175
		-6352	12	6532	11	10	9	8	7	6	-95	27	175			-2352	0	4581	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-1971	-95	27	175
		175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175			175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

24	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175	24	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175		
		37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	4338	-4284	175			-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	160	-96	175
		34	24	6	-4	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-6	175			-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	11	175
		-58	49	25	-3	26	-26	88	235	-215	-4536	4590	175			-29	24	24	6	6	20	25	-2	37	-264	328	175
		35	-1	-6	27	54	-3	-5	-27	47	61	-7	175			-30	-68	29	15	27	16	-6	90	38	54	10	175
		36	32	26	-1	-33	47	-6	-28	48	62	-8	175			-31	25	19	4	17	24	17	-3	39	55	9	175
		33	-33	20	52	4	28	-3	-29	49	63	-9	175			-32	26	12	26	9	7	27	-4	40	56	8	175
		-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-10	175			-33	23	-3	30	22	14	18	-1	41	57	7	175
		40	18	-4504	41	2406	2025	44	10	41	65	-11	175			-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	6	175
		-20	2	4524	-21	-2386	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-12	175			363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	5	175
		52	53	-201	54	55	56	57	58	59	27	-95	175			45	46	-4435	2406	48	2025	50	51	52	32	-145	175
		2	1	255	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-95	27	175			19	18	4499	-2342	16	-1961	14	13	12	-145	32	175
		175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175			175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

24	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175											
-4	36	107	6	24	-22	10	5	-25	-47	85	175	4420	-2003	-2384	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	7	175
35	34	-77	24	6	52	20	25	55	-55	56	175	-6793	11	6815	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	6	175
108	-78	10	24	25	12	11	19	14	-168	198	175	2406	2025	-4398	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-154	206	175
2	28	23	22	7	20	21	18	4	43	-13	175	-4395	14	4453	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	5	175
1	29	35	-3	6	22	23	13	19	44	-14	175	4443	34	-4405	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	4	175
0	30	7	25	34	17	0	17	15	45	-15	175	-4391	18	19	4384	20	10	41	35	-13	49	3	175
-1	31	6	26	11	12	28	18	14	46	-16	175	4411	2	1	-4364	0	41	10	36	-14	50	2	175
-2	32	27	25	20	13	15	-1	16	47	-17	175	26	-4262	27	28	4199	29	30	11	35	51	1	175
-3	33	7	-4	12	19	17	31	33	48	-18	175	-4	4284	-5	-6	-4177	-7	-8	35	11	52	0	175
41	32	-4485	2406	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-52	175	38	56	-22	24	6	20	25	43	44	26	-85	175
-2	-32	4515	-2376	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	123	-19	175	14	-4	74	28	46	32	27	9	8	-85	26	175
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

24	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										175											
2	24	4419	-2382	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	7	175	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	4	175
23	22	-4395	2406	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	6	175	6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	3	175
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	5	175	5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-185	239	175
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	4	175	4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	2	175
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-161	215	175	3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	1	175
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	3	175	2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	0	175
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	2	175	1	27	31	-4395	2406	2025	-29	16	39	55	-1	175
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	1	175	0	-7	-32	4419	-2382	-2001	31	53	40	56	-2	175
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	0	175	101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-3	175
40	38	24	6	-1	20	25	45	46	27	-95	175	6899	43	-6863	44	45	24	6	20	25	27	-95	175
14	16	30	48	55	34	29	9	8	-95	27	175	-6845	11	6917	10	9	30	48	34	29	-95	27	175
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175

24	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										175
28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	3	17	51	-7	175	
-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	2429	-2385	175	
25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-8	175	
26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-9	175	
27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-128	148	-2609	2653	175	
24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-10	175	
7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-11	175	
24	6	33	34	-72	20	25	10	51	56	-12	175	
-4	14	-13	-14	92	0	-5	51	10	57	-13	175	
2406	44	45	46	-4514	47	2025	49	50	22	-45	175	
-2362	0	-1	-2	4558	-3	-1981	-5	-6	-45	22	175	
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	

24	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										175
-19	137	39	24	6	20	25	44	-145	57	-13	175	
-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-10	175	
-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-11	175	
-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-12	175	
-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-258	302	175	
-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-13	175	
-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-14	175	
-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-15	175	
255	-118	-20	-5	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-16	175	
46	47	48	2406	-4530	2025	51	52	53	22	-45	175	
-2	-3	-4	-2362	4574	-1981	-7	-8	-9	-45	22	175	
175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	175	

■ 176th Day of the Year - 25.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-45	84	176	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-54	56	176	
108	-78	25	6	-14	20	25	23	31	-168	198	176	
2	28	29	15	28	16	-26	24	30	43	-13	176	
1	29	19	-16	17	24	18	37	17	44	-14	176	
0	30	12	27	9	-13	27	25	29	45	-15	176	
-1	31	-23	30	22	15	18	26	28	46	-16	176	
-2	32	40	20	32	21	22	27	-46	47	-17	176	
-3	33	14	34	22	33	32	-46	27	48	-18	176	
41	31	-4585	2506	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-50	176	
-1	-30	4615	-2476	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	121	-19	176	
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	

25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
25	6	-6	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-3	176	
49	25	-2	26	-28	34	-4	-21	43	2433	-2379	176	
-1	-8	27	54	-2	-63	93	-22	44	-2610	2664	176	
32	27	-1	-35	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-4	176	
-35	20	52	5	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-5	176	
6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-6	176	
24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-7	176	
38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-8	176	
-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-9	176	
2506	50	-4603	51	52	53	54	55	2025	27	-94	176	
-2452	4	4657	3	2	1	0	-1	-1971	-94	27	176	
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	

25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176	25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176		
		-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-457	176			-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-2189	2243	176
		40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	5	176			-22	25	6	-6	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-7	176
		58	-37	25	6	4	20	25	-1	22	-632	686	176			-23	49	25	-2	26	-28	34	-4	45	1984	-1930	176
		-13	34	29	15	28	16	-8	25	-4	50	4	176			-24	-1	-8	27	54	-2	-63	93	46	62	-8	176
		-14	35	19	2	17	24	18	26	-5	51	3	176			-25	32	27	-1	-35	47	35	-5	47	63	-9	176
		-15	36	12	27	9	5	27	27	-6	52	2	176			-26	-35	20	52	5	28	36	-6	48	64	-10	176
		-16	37	-5	30	22	15	18	28	-7	53	1	176			-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-11	176
		-6	-84	-4470	2506	21	2025	23	57	50	54	0	176			-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-12	176
		105	24	4491	-2485	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	-1	176			326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-13	176
		6601	42	-6673	43	44	45	46	47	48	27	-94	176			2506	54	-4627	55	56	57	58	59	2025	27	-94	176
		-6547	12	6727	11	10	9	8	7	6	-94	27	176			-2452	0	4681	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-1971	-94	27	176
		176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176			176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176

25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176	25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176		
		37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	4370	-4316	176			-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	107	-53	176
		34	25	6	4	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-6	176			-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	1	176
		-117	49	25	-2	26	-18	137	230	-208	-4568	4622	176			-15	24	25	6	-6	20	25	6	37	-256	310	176
		35	-1	2	27	54	-2	-15	-25	47	61	-7	176			-16	-17	29	15	28	16	-18	47	38	54	0	176
		36	32	27	-1	-25	47	-16	-26	48	62	-8	176			-17	25	19	-8	17	24	18	5	39	55	-1	176
		33	-25	20	52	5	28	-13	-27	49	63	-9	176			-18	26	12	27	9	-5	27	4	40	56	-2	176
		42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-10	176			-19	23	-15	30	22	15	18	7	41	57	-3	176
		40	-33	-4546	41	2506	2025	44	11	34	65	-11	176			-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-4	176
		-18	55	4568	-19	-2484	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-12	176			262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-5	176
		52	53	-201	54	55	56	57	58	59	27	-94	176			45	46	-4580	2506	48	2025	50	51	52	27	-94	176
		2	1	255	0	-1	-2	-3	-4	-5	-94	27	176			9	8	4634	-2452	6	-1971	4	3	2	-94	27	176
		176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176			176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
-4	36	108	5	24	-22	10	5	-25	-45	84	176	
35	34	-78	25	6	52	20	25	55	-54	56	176	
108	-78	6	24	27	8	7	19	25	-168	198	176	
2	28	23	22	1	20	21	3	26	43	-13	176	
1	29	37	-9	3	28	29	7	21	44	-14	176	
0	30	3	25	46	20	-6	17	11	45	-15	176	
-1	31	2	26	11	12	37	18	10	46	-16	176	
-2	32	27	10	14	13	15	21	16	47	-17	176	
-3	33	18	18	14	15	13	31	7	48	-18	176	
41	31	-4585	2506	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-50	176	
-1	-30	4615	-2476	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	121	-19	176	
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	

25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
4521	-2005	-2486	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	9	176	
-6997	10	7017	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	8	176	
2506	2025	-4501	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-145	199	176	
-4496	14	4557	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	7	176	
4546	36	-4507	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	6	176	
-4487	18	19	4485	20	11	36	35	-15	49	5	176	
4509	4	3	-4463	2	36	11	36	-16	50	4	176	
26	-4370	27	28	4300	29	30	10	42	51	3	176	
-6	4390	-7	-8	-4280	-9	-10	42	10	52	2	176	
38	52	-10	25	6	20	25	43	44	27	-94	176	
16	2	64	29	48	34	29	11	10	-94	27	176	
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	

25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
6	24	4517	-2478	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	9	176	
23	22	-4489	2506	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	8	176	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	7	176	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	6	176	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-152	208	176	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	5	176	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	4	176	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	3	176	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	2	176	
40	49	25	6	-4	20	25	45	46	28	-104	176	
16	7	31	50	60	36	31	11	10	-104	28	176	
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	

25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										176
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	6	176	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	5	176	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-176	232	176	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	4	176	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	3	176	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	2	176	
1	27	46	-4489	2506	2025	-51	16	39	55	1	176	
0	-18	-54	4517	-2478	-1997	31	79	40	56	0	176	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-1	176	
7089	43	-7045	44	45	25	6	20	25	28	-104	176	
-7033	13	7101	12	11	31	50	36	31	-104	28	176	
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	

25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										176
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	1	17	51	-5	176	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	2528	-2482	176	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-6	176	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-7	176	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-133	151	-2699	2745	176	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-8	176	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-9	176	
25	6	33	34	-80	20	25	9	58	56	-10	176	
-7	12	-15	-16	98	-2	-7	58	9	57	-11	176	
2506	44	45	46	-4605	47	2025	49	50	23	-54	176	
-2460	2	1	0	4651	-1	-1979	-3	-4	-54	23	176	
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	

25	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										176
-20	137	39	25	6	20	25	44	-146	59	-13	176	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-8	176	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-9	176	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-10	176	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-251	297	176	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-11	176	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-12	176	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-13	176	
262	-119	-21	-7	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-14	176	
46	47	48	2506	-4621	2025	51	52	53	23	-54	176	
0	-1	-2	-2460	4667	-1979	-5	-6	-7	-54	23	176	
176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	176	

■ 177th Day of the Year - 26.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-43	83	177	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-53	56	177	
108	-78	26	6	-6	20	25	23	23	-168	198	177	
2	28	29	15	29	16	-18	24	22	43	-13	177	
1	29	19	-8	17	24	19	17	29	44	-14	177	
0	30	12	28	9	-5	27	25	21	45	-15	177	
-1	31	-15	30	22	16	18	26	20	46	-16	177	
-2	32	32	20	20	21	22	23	-21	47	-17	177	
-3	33	14	26	26	25	24	-21	23	48	-18	177	
41	30	-4685	2606	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-48	177	
0	-28	4715	-2576	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	119	-19	177	
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177
26	6	4	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	-1	177	
49	25	-1	26	-18	34	-14	-23	43	2552	-2496	177	
-1	2	27	54	-1	-88	108	-24	44	-2720	2776	177	
32	28	-1	-25	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	-2	177	
-25	20	52	6	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-3	177	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-4	177	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-5	177	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-6	177	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-7	177	
2606	50	-4694	51	52	53	54	55	2025	28	-103	177	
-2550	6	4750	5	4	3	2	1	-1969	-103	28	177	
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177	
		-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-460	177
		40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	7	177
		62	-42	26	6	4	20	25	-6	26	-628	684	177
		-14	34	29	15	29	16	-8	25	-5	50	6	177
		-15	35	19	2	17	24	19	26	-6	51	5	177
		-16	36	12	28	9	5	27	27	-7	52	4	177
		-17	37	-5	30	22	16	18	28	-8	53	3	177
		-1	-80	-4575	2606	21	2025	23	52	50	54	2	177
		100	24	4595	-2586	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	1	177
		6808	42	-6871	43	44	45	46	47	48	28	-103	177
		-6752	14	6927	13	12	11	10	9	8	-103	28	177
		177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177	
		-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-2268	2324	177
		-24	26	6	4	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-5	177
		-25	49	25	-1	26	-18	34	-14	45	2072	-2016	177
		-26	-1	2	27	54	-1	-88	108	46	62	-6	177
		-27	32	28	-1	-25	47	35	-15	47	63	-7	177
		-28	-25	20	52	6	28	36	-16	48	64	-8	177
		-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-9	177
		-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-10	177
		341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-11	177
		2606	54	-4718	55	56	57	58	59	2025	28	-103	177
		-2550	2	4774	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-1969	-103	28	177
		177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177	
		37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	4540	-4484	177
		34	26	6	-6	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-4	177
		-58	49	25	-1	26	-28	88	235	-215	-4729	4785	177
		35	-1	-8	27	54	-1	-5	-27	47	61	-5	177
		36	32	28	-1	-35	47	-6	-28	48	62	-6	177
		33	-35	20	52	6	28	-3	-29	49	63	-7	177
		-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-8	177
		40	18	-4704	41	2606	2025	44	10	41	65	-9	177
		-20	2	4724	-21	-2586	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-10	177
		52	53	-192	54	55	56	57	58	59	28	-103	177
		4	3	248	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-103	28	177
		177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177	
		-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	162	-96	177
		-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	13	177
		-29	24	26	6	4	20	25	-2	37	-257	323	177
		-30	-68	29	15	29	16	-8	90	38	54	12	177
		-31	25	19	2	17	24	19	-3	39	55	11	177
		-32	26	12	28	9	5	27	-4	40	56	10	177
		-33	23	-5	30	22	16	18	-1	41	57	9	177
		-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	8	177
		363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	7	177
		45	46	-4626	2606	48	2025	50	51	52	33	-153	177
		21	20	4692	-2540	18	-1959	16	15	14	-153	33	177
		177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177											
-2	36	104	6	26	-20	12	7	-23	-61	92	177	4620	-2003	-2584	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	9	177
35	34	-72	26	6	52	20	25	55	-60	56	177	-7193	11	7215	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	8	177
103	-71	6	24	27	8	7	19	22	-161	193	177	2606	2025	-4598	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-145	199	177
4	28	23	22	1	20	21	6	20	43	-11	177	-4595	14	4653	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	7	177
3	29	37	-9	4	26	27	7	21	44	-12	177	4643	34	-4605	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	6	177
2	30	3	25	42	19	-4	17	11	45	-13	177	-4591	18	19	4584	20	10	41	35	-13	49	5	177
1	31	2	26	11	12	34	18	10	46	-14	177	4611	2	1	-4564	0	41	10	36	-14	50	4	177
0	32	27	13	14	13	15	15	16	47	-15	177	26	-4462	27	28	4399	29	30	11	35	51	3	177
-1	33	15	12	14	15	13	31	13	48	-16	177	-4	4484	-5	-6	-4377	-7	-8	35	11	52	2	177
41	41	-4678	2606	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-66	177	38	54	-13	26	6	20	25	43	44	27	-93	177
-9	-46	4710	-2574	-6	-7	-8	-1993	-10	137	-17	177	16	0	67	28	48	34	29	11	10	-93	27	177
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										177											
2	24	4619	-2582	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	9	177	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	6	177
23	22	-4595	2606	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	8	177	6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	5	177
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	7	177	5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-176	232	177
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	6	177	4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	4	177
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-152	208	177	3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	3	177
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	5	177	2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	2	177
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	4	177	1	27	31	-4595	2606	2025	-29	16	39	55	1	177
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	3	177	0	-7	-32	4619	-2582	-2001	31	53	40	56	0	177
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	2	177	101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	-1	177
40	36	26	6	8	20	25	45	46	28	-103	177	7301	43	-7258	44	45	26	6	20	25	28	-103	177
16	20	30	50	48	36	31	11	10	-103	28	177	-7245	13	7314	12	11	30	50	36	31	-103	28	177
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										177
28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	1	19	51	-5	177	
-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	2627	-2581	177	
25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-6	177	
26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-7	177	
27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-126	146	-2798	2844	177	
24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-8	177	
7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-9	177	
26	6	33	34	-74	20	25	10	51	56	-10	177	
-6	14	-13	-14	94	0	-5	51	10	57	-11	177	
2606	44	45	46	-4705	47	2025	49	50	23	-53	177	
-2560	2	1	0	4751	-1	-1979	-3	-4	-53	23	177	
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	

26	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										177
-19	135	39	26	6	20	25	44	-145	59	-13	177	
-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-8	177	
-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-9	177	
-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-10	177	
-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-251	297	177	
-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-11	177	
-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-12	177	
-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-13	177	
255	-116	-20	-7	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-14	177	
46	47	48	2606	-4721	2025	51	52	53	23	-53	177	
0	-1	-2	-2560	4767	-1979	-5	-6	-7	-53	23	177	
177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	177	

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◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										178
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-41	82	178	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-52	56	178	
108	-78	27	6	-16	20	25	23	33	-168	198	178	
2	28	29	15	30	16	-28	24	32	43	-13	178	
1	29	19	-18	17	24	20	42	14	44	-14	178	
0	30	12	29	9	-15	27	25	31	45	-15	178	
-1	31	-25	30	22	17	18	26	30	46	-16	178	
-2	32	42	20	35	21	22	28	-50	47	-17	178	
-3	33	14	36	21	35	34	-50	28	48	-18	178	
41	29	-4785	2706	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-46	178	
1	-26	4815	-2676	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	117	-19	178	
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	

27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										178
27	6	-8	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	-1	178	
49	25	0	26	-30	34	-4	-21	43	2631	-2575	178	
-1	-10	27	54	0	-63	93	-22	44	-2799	2855	178	
32	29	-1	-37	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	-2	178	
-37	20	52	7	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-3	178	
6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-4	178	
24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-5	178	
38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-6	178	
-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-7	178	
2706	50	-4794	51	52	53	54	55	2025	28	-102	178	
-2650	6	4850	5	4	3	2	1	-1969	-102	28	178	
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	

27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										178	27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										178
	-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-455	178		-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-2387	2443	178
	40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	7	178		-22	27	6	-8	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-5	178
	58	-37	27	6	2	20	25	-1	22	-623	679	178		-23	49	25	0	26	-30	34	-4	45	2191	-2135	178
	-13	34	29	15	30	16	-10	25	-4	50	6	178		-24	-1	-10	27	54	0	-63	93	46	62	-6	178
	-14	35	19	0	17	24	20	26	-5	51	5	178		-25	32	29	-1	-37	47	35	-5	47	63	-7	178
	-15	36	12	29	9	3	27	27	-6	52	4	178		-26	-37	20	52	7	28	36	-6	48	64	-8	178
	-16	37	-7	30	22	17	18	28	-7	53	3	178		-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-9	178
	-6	-84	-4670	2706	21	2025	23	57	50	54	2	178		-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-10	178
	105	24	4691	-2685	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	1	178		326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-11	178
	7003	42	-7066	43	44	45	46	47	48	28	-102	178		2706	54	-4818	55	56	57	58	59	2025	28	-102	178
	-6947	14	7122	13	12	11	10	9	8	-102	28	178		-2650	2	4874	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-1969	-102	28	178
	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178		178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178

27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										178	27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										178
	37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	4572	-4516	178		-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	109	-53	178
	34	27	6	2	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-4	178		-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	3	178
	-117	49	25	0	26	-20	137	230	-208	-4761	4817	178		-15	24	27	6	-8	20	25	6	37	-249	305	178
	35	-1	0	27	54	0	-15	-25	47	61	-5	178		-16	-17	29	15	30	16	-20	47	38	54	2	178
	36	32	29	-1	-27	47	-16	-26	48	62	-6	178		-17	25	19	-10	17	24	20	5	39	55	1	178
	33	-27	20	52	7	28	-13	-27	49	63	-7	178		-18	26	12	29	9	-7	27	4	40	56	0	178
	42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-8	178		-19	23	-17	30	22	17	18	7	41	57	-1	178
	40	-33	-4746	41	2706	2025	44	11	34	65	-9	178		-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	-2	178
	-18	55	4768	-19	-2684	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-10	178		262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-3	178
	52	53	-192	54	55	56	57	58	59	28	-102	178		45	46	-4771	2706	48	2025	50	51	52	28	-102	178
	4	3	248	2	1	0	-1	-2	-3	-102	28	178		11	10	4827	-2650	8	-1969	6	5	4	-102	28	178
	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178		178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									178
-4	36	110	3	24	-22	10	5	-25	-41	82	178
35	34	-80	27	6	52	20	25	55	-52	56	178
108	-78	10	24	25	12	11	19	17	-168	198	178
2	28	23	22	7	20	21	15	10	43	-13	178
1	29	35	-3	5	24	25	13	19	44	-14	178
0	30	7	25	38	18	-2	17	15	45	-15	178
-1	31	6	26	11	12	31	18	14	46	-16	178
-2	32	27	22	20	13	15	5	16	47	-17	178
-3	33	10	2	12	19	17	31	27	48	-18	178
41	29	-4785	2706	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-46	178
1	-26	4815	-2676	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	117	-19	178
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178

27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									178
4721	-2005	-2686	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	11	178
-7397	10	7417	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	10	178
2706	2025	-4701	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-136	192	178
-4696	14	4757	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	9	178
4746	36	-4707	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	8	178
-4687	18	19	4685	20	11	36	35	-15	49	7	178
4709	4	3	-4663	2	36	11	36	-16	50	6	178
26	-4570	27	28	4500	29	30	10	42	51	5	178
-6	4590	-7	-8	-4480	-9	-10	42	10	52	4	178
38	50	-1	27	6	20	25	43	44	28	-102	178
18	6	57	29	50	36	31	13	12	-102	28	178
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178

27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									178
6	24	4717	-2678	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	11	178
23	22	-4689	2706	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	10	178
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	9	178
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	8	178
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-143	201	178
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	7	178
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	6	178
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	5	178
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	4	178
40	47	27	6	5	20	25	45	46	29	-112	178
18	11	31	52	53	38	33	13	12	-112	29	178
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178

27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT									178
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	8	178
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	7	178
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-167	225	178
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	6	178
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	5	178
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	4	178
1	27	46	-4689	2706	2025	-51	16	39	55	3	178
0	-18	-54	4717	-2678	-1997	31	79	40	56	2	178
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	1	178
7491	43	-7440	44	45	27	6	20	25	29	-112	178
-7433	15	7498	14	13	31	52	38	33	-112	29	178
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178

27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										178
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	-1	19	51	-3	178	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	2726	-2678	178	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-4	178	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-5	178	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-131	149	-2888	2936	178	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-6	178	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-7	178	
27	6	33	34	-82	20	25	9	58	56	-8	178	
-9	12	-15	-16	100	-2	-7	58	9	57	-9	178	
2706	44	45	46	-4796	47	2025	49	50	24	-62	178	
-2658	4	3	2	4844	1	-1977	-1	-2	-62	24	178	
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	

27	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										178
-20	135	39	27	6	20	25	44	-146	61	-13	178	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-6	178	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-7	178	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-8	178	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-244	292	178	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-9	178	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-10	178	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-11	178	
262	-117	-21	-9	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-12	178	
46	47	48	2706	-4812	2025	51	52	53	24	-62	178	
2	1	0	-2658	4860	-1977	-3	-4	-5	-62	24	178	
178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	178	

■ 179th Day of the Year - 28.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-39	81	179	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-51	56	179	
108	-78	28	6	-8	20	25	23	25	-168	198	179	
2	28	29	15	31	16	-20	24	24	43	-13	179	
1	29	19	-10	17	24	21	22	26	44	-14	179	
0	30	12	30	9	-7	27	25	23	45	-15	179	
-1	31	-17	30	22	18	18	26	22	46	-16	179	
-2	32	34	20	23	21	22	24	-25	47	-17	179	
-3	33	14	28	25	27	26	-25	24	48	-18	179	
41	28	-4885	2806	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-44	179	
2	-24	4915	-2776	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	115	-19	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179
28	6	2	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	1	179	
49	25	1	26	-20	34	-14	-23	43	2750	-2692	179	
-1	0	27	54	1	-88	108	-24	44	-2909	2967	179	
32	30	-1	-27	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	0	179	
-27	20	52	8	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	-1	179	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	-2	179	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-3	179	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-4	179	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-5	179	
2806	50	-4885	51	52	53	54	55	2025	29	-111	179	
-2748	8	4943	7	6	5	4	3	-1967	-111	29	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179	
		-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-458	179
		40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	9	179
		62	-42	28	6	2	20	25	-6	26	-619	677	179
		-14	34	29	15	31	16	-10	25	-5	50	8	179
		-15	35	19	0	17	24	21	26	-6	51	7	179
		-16	36	12	30	9	3	27	27	-7	52	6	179
		-17	37	-7	30	22	18	18	28	-8	53	5	179
		-1	-80	-4775	2806	21	2025	23	52	50	54	4	179
		100	24	4795	-2786	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	3	179
		7210	42	-7264	43	44	45	46	47	48	29	-111	179
		-7152	16	7322	15	14	13	12	11	10	-111	29	179
		179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179	
		-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-2466	2524	179
		-24	28	6	2	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-3	179
		-25	49	25	1	26	-20	34	-14	45	2279	-2221	179
		-26	-1	0	27	54	1	-88	108	46	62	-4	179
		-27	32	30	-1	-27	47	35	-15	47	63	-5	179
		-28	-27	20	52	8	28	36	-16	48	64	-6	179
		-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-7	179
		-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-8	179
		341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-9	179
		2806	54	-4909	55	56	57	58	59	2025	29	-111	179
		-2748	4	4967	3	2	1	0	-1	-1967	-111	29	179
		179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179	
		37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	4742	-4684	179
		34	28	6	-8	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	-2	179
		-58	49	25	1	26	-30	88	235	-215	-4922	4980	179
		35	-1	-10	27	54	1	-5	-27	47	61	-3	179
		36	32	30	-1	-37	47	-6	-28	48	62	-4	179
		33	-37	20	52	8	28	-3	-29	49	63	-5	179
		-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-6	179
		40	18	-4904	41	2806	2025	44	10	41	65	-7	179
		-20	2	4924	-21	-2786	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-8	179
		52	53	-183	54	55	56	57	58	59	29	-111	179
		6	5	241	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-111	29	179
		179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179	
		-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	164	-96	179
		-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	15	179
		-29	24	28	6	2	20	25	-2	37	-250	318	179
		-30	-68	29	15	31	16	-10	90	38	54	14	179
		-31	25	19	0	17	24	21	-3	39	55	13	179
		-32	26	12	30	9	3	27	-4	40	56	12	179
		-33	23	-7	30	22	18	18	-1	41	57	11	179
		-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	10	179
		363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	9	179
		45	46	-4817	2806	48	2025	50	51	52	34	-161	179
		23	22	4885	-2738	20	-1957	18	17	16	-161	34	179
		179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179
-2	36	106	4	26	-20	12	7	-23	-57	90	179	
35	34	-74	28	6	52	20	25	55	-58	56	179	
103	-71	10	24	25	12	11	19	14	-161	193	179	
4	28	23	22	7	20	21	18	4	43	-11	179	
3	29	35	-3	6	22	23	13	19	44	-12	179	
2	30	7	25	34	17	0	17	15	45	-13	179	
1	31	6	26	11	12	28	18	14	46	-14	179	
0	32	27	25	20	13	15	-1	16	47	-15	179	
-1	33	7	-4	12	19	17	31	33	48	-16	179	
41	39	-4878	2806	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-62	179	
-7	-42	4910	-2774	-6	-7	-8	-1993	-10	133	-17	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179
4820	-2003	-2784	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	11	179	
-7593	11	7615	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	10	179	
2806	2025	-4798	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-136	192	179	
-4795	14	4853	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	9	179	
4843	34	-4805	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	8	179	
-4791	18	19	4784	20	10	41	35	-13	49	7	179	
4811	2	1	-4764	0	41	10	36	-14	50	6	179	
26	-4662	27	28	4599	29	30	11	35	51	5	179	
-4	4684	-5	-6	-4577	-7	-8	35	11	52	4	179	
38	52	-4	28	6	20	25	43	44	28	-101	179	
18	4	60	28	50	36	31	13	12	-101	28	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179
2	24	4819	-2782	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	11	179	
23	22	-4795	2806	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	10	179	
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	9	179	
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	8	179	
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-143	201	179	
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	7	179	
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	6	179	
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	5	179	
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	4	179	
40	34	28	6	17	20	25	45	46	29	-111	179	
18	24	30	52	41	38	33	13	12	-111	29	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										179
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	8	179	
6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	7	179	
5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-167	225	179	
4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	6	179	
3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	5	179	
2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	4	179	
1	27	31	-4795	2806	2025	-29	16	39	55	3	179	
0	-7	-32	4819	-2782	-2001	31	53	40	56	2	179	
101	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	1	179	
7703	43	-7653	44	45	28	6	20	25	29	-111	179	
-7645	15	7711	14	13	30	52	38	33	-111	29	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT											179
28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	-1	21	51	-3	179	179	
-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	2825	-2777	179	179	
25	22	7	20	21	10	6	38	-18	52	-4	179	179	
26	15	30	16	2	17	5	39	-19	53	-5	179	179	
27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-124	144	-2987	3035	179	179	
24	13	20	17	14	16	7	40	-20	54	-6	179	179	
7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-7	179	179	
28	6	33	34	-76	20	25	10	51	56	-8	179	179	
-8	14	-13	-14	96	0	-5	51	10	57	-9	179	179	
2806	44	45	46	-4896	47	2025	49	50	24	-61	179	179	
-2758	4	3	2	4944	1	-1977	-1	-2	-61	24	179	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

28	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT											179
-19	133	39	28	6	20	25	44	-145	61	-13	179	179	
-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-6	179	179	
-13	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-7	179	179	
-14	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-8	179	179	
-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-244	292	179	179	
-16	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-9	179	179	
-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-10	179	179	
-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-11	179	179	
255	-114	-20	-9	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-12	179	179	
46	47	48	2806	-4912	2025	51	52	53	24	-61	179	179	
2	1	0	-2758	4960	-1977	-3	-4	-5	-61	24	179	179	
179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	179	

■ 180th Day of the Year - 29.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											180
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-37	80	180	180	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-50	56	180	180	
108	-78	29	6	-18	20	25	23	35	-168	198	180	180	
2	28	29	15	32	16	-30	24	34	43	-13	180	180	
1	29	19	-20	17	24	22	47	11	44	-14	180	180	
0	30	12	31	9	-17	27	25	33	45	-15	180	180	
-1	31	-27	30	22	19	18	26	32	46	-16	180	180	
-2	32	44	20	38	21	22	29	-54	47	-17	180	180	
-3	33	14	38	20	37	36	-54	29	48	-18	180	180	
41	27	-4985	2906	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-42	180	180	
3	-22	5015	-2876	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	113	-19	180	180	
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT											180
29	6	-10	20	25	33	-3	40	-18	57	1	180	180	
49	25	2	26	-32	34	-4	-21	43	2829	-2771	180	180	
-1	-12	27	54	2	-63	93	-22	44	-2988	3046	180	180	
32	31	-1	-39	47	35	-5	-23	45	58	0	180	180	
-39	20	52	9	28	36	-6	152	-130	59	-1	180	180	
6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	-24	46	60	-2	180	180	
24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	-25	47	61	-3	180	180	
38	-64	-59	39	40	41	42	11	34	62	-4	180	180	
-16	86	81	-17	-18	-19	-20	34	11	63	-5	180	180	
2906	50	-4985	51	52	53	54	55	2025	29	-110	180	180	
-2848	8	5043	7	6	5	4	3	-1967	-110	29	180	180	
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180	
		-17	39	42	-9	-10	-11	-12	5	95	511	-453	180
		40	38	-21	30	31	32	33	-74	13	49	9	180
		58	-37	29	6	0	20	25	-1	22	-614	672	180
		-13	34	29	15	32	16	-12	25	-4	50	8	180
		-14	35	19	-2	17	24	22	26	-5	51	7	180
		-15	36	12	31	9	1	27	27	-6	52	6	180
		-16	37	-9	30	22	19	18	28	-7	53	5	180
		-6	-84	-4870	2906	21	2025	23	57	50	54	4	180
		105	24	4891	-2885	0	-2004	-2	29	-36	55	3	180
		7405	42	-7459	43	44	45	46	47	48	29	-110	180
		-7347	16	7517	15	14	13	12	11	10	-110	29	180
		180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180	
		-29	166	38	39	40	41	42	43	-258	-2585	2643	180
		-22	29	6	-10	20	25	33	-3	44	61	-3	180
		-23	49	25	2	26	-32	34	-4	45	2398	-2340	180
		-24	-1	-12	27	54	2	-63	93	46	62	-4	180
		-25	32	31	-1	-39	47	35	-5	47	63	-5	180
		-26	-39	20	52	9	28	36	-6	48	64	-6	180
		-27	6	30	-24	31	32	15	10	49	65	-7	180
		-28	24	0	54	-1	-2	10	15	50	66	-8	180
		326	-144	-16	-17	-18	-19	-20	-21	51	67	-9	180
		2906	54	-5009	55	56	57	58	59	2025	29	-110	180
		-2848	4	5067	3	2	1	0	-1	-1967	-110	29	180
		180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180	
		37	51	30	-119	31	32	38	-23	45	4774	-4716	180
		34	29	6	0	20	25	-14	-24	46	60	-2	180
		-117	49	25	2	26	-22	137	230	-208	-4954	5012	180
		35	-1	-2	27	54	2	-15	-25	47	61	-3	180
		36	32	31	-1	-29	47	-16	-26	48	62	-4	180
		33	-29	20	52	9	28	-13	-27	49	63	-5	180
		42	-31	-10	139	-11	-12	-17	-28	50	64	-6	180
		40	-33	-4946	41	2906	2025	44	11	34	65	-7	180
		-18	55	4968	-19	-2884	-2003	-22	34	11	66	-8	180
		52	53	-183	54	55	56	57	58	59	29	-110	180
		6	5	241	4	3	2	1	0	-1	-110	29	180
		180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180	
		-21	142	30	31	32	33	34	35	-194	111	-53	180
		-14	27	51	20	-69	21	22	28	36	53	5	180
		-15	24	29	6	-10	20	25	6	37	-242	300	180
		-16	-17	29	15	32	16	-22	47	38	54	4	180
		-17	25	19	-12	17	24	22	5	39	55	3	180
		-18	26	12	31	9	-9	27	4	40	56	2	180
		-19	23	-19	30	22	19	18	7	41	57	1	180
		-20	-8	-21	10	99	9	8	3	42	58	0	180
		262	-120	-8	-9	-10	-11	-12	-13	43	59	-1	180
		45	46	-4962	2906	48	2025	50	51	52	29	-110	180
		13	12	5020	-2848	10	-1967	8	7	6	-110	29	180
		180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180
-4	36	112	1	24	-22	10	5	-25	-37	80	180	
35	34	-82	29	6	52	20	25	55	-50	56	180	
108	-78	8	24	26	10	9	19	24	-168	198	180	
2	28	23	22	4	20	21	6	24	43	-13	180	
1	29	36	-6	3	28	29	10	20	44	-14	180	
0	30	5	25	46	20	-6	17	13	45	-15	180	
-1	31	4	26	11	12	37	18	12	46	-16	180	
-2	32	27	13	17	13	15	19	16	47	-17	180	
-3	33	17	16	13	17	15	31	11	48	-18	180	
41	27	-4985	2906	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-42	180	
3	-22	5015	-2876	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	113	-19	180	
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180
4921	-2005	-2886	44	6	21	1	31	-11	45	13	180	
-7797	10	7817	15	35	22	0	32	-12	46	12	180	
2906	2025	-4901	16	34	23	-1	33	-13	-127	185	180	
-4896	14	4957	25	-20	-35	57	34	-14	47	11	180	
4946	36	-4907	-20	25	24	-2	-131	151	48	10	180	
-4887	18	19	4885	20	11	36	35	-15	49	9	180	
4909	4	3	-4863	2	36	11	36	-16	50	8	180	
26	-4770	27	28	4700	29	30	10	42	51	7	180	
-6	4790	-7	-8	-4680	-9	-10	42	10	52	6	180	
38	48	8	29	6	20	25	43	44	29	-110	180	
20	10	50	29	52	38	33	15	14	-110	29	180	
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180
6	24	4917	-2878	-1997	19	-11	33	7	47	13	180	
23	22	-4889	2906	2025	39	-46	34	6	48	12	180	
37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	35	5	49	11	180	
3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	36	4	50	10	180	
2	26	11	12	1	18	10	-73	113	-134	194	180	
27	46	13	14	15	-51	16	37	3	51	9	180	
-18	-54	15	14	13	31	79	38	2	52	8	180	
28	-1	29	30	-9	31	32	20	-40	53	7	180	
12	41	11	10	49	9	8	-40	20	54	6	180	
40	45	29	6	14	20	25	45	46	30	-120	180	
20	15	31	54	46	40	35	15	14	-120	30	180	
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										180
-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-180	50	10	180	
6	6	24	27	8	7	19	-11	34	51	9	180	
5	23	22	1	20	21	39	-46	35	-158	218	180	
4	37	-9	15	4	5	7	21	36	52	8	180	
3	3	25	-2	8	18	17	11	37	53	7	180	
2	2	26	11	12	1	18	10	38	54	6	180	
1	27	46	-4889	2906	2025	-51	16	39	55	5	180	
0	-18	-54	4917	-2878	-1997	31	79	40	56	4	180	
100	-78	12	11	10	9	8	7	41	57	3	180	
7893	43	-7835	44	45	29	6	20	25	30	-120	180	
-7833	17	7895	16	15	31	54	40	35	-120	30	180	
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										180
28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	-3	21	51	-1	180	
-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	37	-19	2924	-2874	180	
25	22	7	20	21	10	7	38	-20	52	-2	180	
26	15	30	16	2	17	6	39	-21	53	-3	180	
27	14	11	12	25	18	5	-129	147	-3077	3127	180	
24	13	20	17	14	16	8	40	-22	54	-4	180	
3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	41	-23	55	-5	180	
29	6	33	34	-84	20	25	9	58	56	-6	180	
-11	12	-15	-16	102	-2	-7	58	9	57	-7	180	
2906	44	45	46	-4987	47	2025	49	50	25	-70	180	
-2856	6	5	4	5037	3	-1975	1	0	-70	25	180	
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

29	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										180
-20	133	39	29	6	20	25	44	-146	63	-13	180	
-13	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-4	180	
-14	-21	16	12	15	18	19	53	32	55	-5	180	
-15	25	22	7	20	21	10	7	33	56	-6	180	
-16	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-237	287	180	
-17	27	14	11	12	25	18	5	35	57	-7	180	
-18	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-8	180	
-19	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-9	180	
262	-115	-21	-11	12	-2	-7	-26	38	60	-10	180	
46	47	48	2906	-5003	2025	51	52	53	25	-70	180	
4	3	2	-2856	5053	-1975	-1	-2	-3	-70	25	180	
180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	180	

■ 181st Day of the Year - 30.06.2025

◆ With Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 5

30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181
-4	36	240	-20	-21	-22	-23	-24	-25	-35	79	181	
35	34	-210	50	51	52	53	54	55	-49	56	181	
108	-78	30	6	-10	20	25	23	27	-168	198	181	
2	28	29	15	33	16	-22	24	26	43	-13	181	
1	29	19	-12	17	24	23	27	23	44	-14	181	
0	30	12	32	9	-9	27	25	25	45	-15	181	
-1	31	-19	30	22	20	18	26	24	46	-16	181	
-2	32	36	20	26	21	22	25	-29	47	-17	181	
-3	33	14	30	24	29	28	-29	25	48	-18	181	
41	26	-5085	3006	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-40	181	
4	-20	5115	-2976	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	111	-19	181	
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	

30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181
30	6	0	20	25	33	-13	55	-35	57	3	181	
49	25	3	26	-22	34	-14	-23	43	2948	-2888	181	
-1	-2	27	54	3	-88	108	-24	44	-3098	3158	181	
32	32	-1	-29	47	35	-15	-25	45	58	2	181	
-29	20	52	10	28	36	-16	140	-120	59	1	181	
-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	-26	46	60	0	181	
24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	-27	47	61	-1	181	
38	-64	-66	39	40	41	42	10	41	62	-2	181	
-18	84	86	-19	-20	-21	-22	41	10	63	-3	181	
3006	50	-5076	51	52	53	54	55	2025	30	-119	181	
-2946	10	5136	9	8	7	6	5	-1965	-119	30	181	
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	

30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181	
		-18	39	46	-10	-11	-12	-13	10	90	516	-456	181
		40	38	-26	30	31	32	33	-70	13	49	11	181
		62	-42	30	6	0	20	25	-6	26	-610	670	181
		-14	34	29	15	33	16	-12	25	-5	50	10	181
		-15	35	19	-2	17	24	23	26	-6	51	9	181
		-16	36	12	32	9	1	27	27	-7	52	8	181
		-17	37	-9	30	22	20	18	28	-8	53	7	181
		-1	-80	-4975	3006	21	2025	23	52	50	54	6	181
		100	24	4995	-2986	-1	-2005	-3	29	-32	55	5	181
		7612	42	-7657	43	44	45	46	47	48	30	-119	181
		-7552	18	7717	17	16	15	14	13	12	-119	30	181
		181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181

30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181	
		-31	168	38	39	40	41	42	43	-259	-2664	2724	181
		-24	30	6	0	20	25	33	-13	44	61	-1	181
		-25	49	25	3	26	-22	34	-14	45	2486	-2426	181
		-26	-1	-2	27	54	3	-88	108	46	62	-2	181
		-27	32	32	-1	-29	47	35	-15	47	63	-3	181
		-28	-29	20	52	10	28	36	-16	48	64	-4	181
		-29	-4	30	-39	31	32	10	41	49	65	-5	181
		-30	24	-10	59	-11	-12	41	10	50	66	-6	181
		341	-148	-18	-19	-20	-21	-22	-23	51	67	-7	181
		3006	54	-5100	55	56	57	58	59	2025	30	-119	181
		-2946	6	5160	5	4	3	2	1	-1965	-119	30	181
		181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181

30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181	
		37	61	30	-128	31	32	38	-25	45	4944	-4884	181
		34	30	6	-10	20	25	-4	-26	46	60	0	181
		-58	49	25	3	26	-32	88	235	-215	-5115	5175	181
		35	-1	-12	27	54	3	-5	-27	47	61	-1	181
		36	32	32	-1	-39	47	-6	-28	48	62	-2	181
		33	-39	20	52	10	28	-3	-29	49	63	-3	181
		-16	-31	0	158	-1	-2	-7	-30	50	64	-4	181
		40	18	-5104	41	3006	2025	44	10	41	65	-5	181
		-20	2	5124	-21	-2986	-2005	-24	41	10	66	-6	181
		52	53	-174	54	55	56	57	58	59	30	-119	181
		8	7	234	6	5	4	3	2	1	-119	30	181
		181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181

30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181	
		-35	156	30	31	32	33	34	35	-205	166	-96	181
		-28	27	43	20	-58	21	22	28	36	53	17	181
		-29	24	30	6	0	20	25	-2	37	-243	313	181
		-30	-68	29	15	33	16	-12	90	38	54	16	181
		-31	25	19	-2	17	24	23	-3	39	55	15	181
		-32	26	12	32	9	1	27	-4	40	56	14	181
		-33	23	-9	30	22	20	18	-1	41	57	13	181
		-34	46	-21	2	80	1	0	-5	42	58	12	181
		363	-148	-22	-23	-24	-25	-26	-27	43	59	11	181
		45	46	-5008	3006	48	2025	50	51	52	35	-169	181
		25	24	5078	-2936	22	-1955	20	19	18	-169	35	181
		181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181

◆ With Magic Squares of Order 3

30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181												
-4	36	113	0	24	-22	10	5	-25	-35	79	181	30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181
35	34	-83	30	6	52	20	25	55	-49	56	181	5020	-2003	-2984	41	7	21	-1	31	-9	45	13	181	
108	-78	10	24	25	12	11	19	20	-168	198	181	-7993	11	8015	15	33	22	-2	32	-10	46	12	181	
2	28	23	22	7	20	21	12	16	43	-13	181	3006	2025	-4998	16	32	23	-3	33	-11	-127	185	181	
1	29	35	-3	4	26	27	13	19	44	-14	181	-4995	14	5053	24	-15	-40	60	34	-12	47	11	181	
0	30	7	25	42	19	-4	17	15	45	-15	181	5043	34	-5005	-15	24	24	-4	-124	146	48	10	181	
-1	31	6	26	11	12	34	18	14	46	-16	181	-4991	18	19	4984	20	10	41	35	-13	49	9	181	
-2	32	27	19	20	13	15	11	16	47	-17	181	5011	2	1	-4964	0	41	10	36	-14	50	8	181	
-3	33	13	8	12	19	17	31	21	48	-18	181	26	-4862	27	28	4799	29	30	11	35	51	7	181	
41	26	-5085	3006	38	39	40	2025	42	49	-40	181	-4	4884	-5	-6	-4777	-7	-8	35	11	52	6	181	
4	-20	5115	-2976	-8	-9	-10	-1995	-12	111	-19	181	38	50	5	30	6	20	25	43	44	29	-109	181	
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	20	8	53	28	52	38	33	15	14	-109	29	181	
181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	181	

30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181												
2	24	5019	-2982	-2001	19	0	33	7	47	13	181	30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ ©IJT										181
23	22	-4995	3006	2025	24	-24	34	6	48	12	181	-1	118	28	29	30	31	32	33	-179	50	10	181	
39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	35	5	49	11	181	6	2	24	29	4	3	19	0	34	51	9	181	
-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	36	4	50	10	181	5	23	22	-5	20	21	24	-24	35	-158	218	181	
-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	-73	113	-134	194	181	4	39	-15	12	10	11	1	23	36	52	8	181	
27	31	7	14	15	-29	16	37	3	51	9	181	3	-1	25	10	11	12	17	7	37	53	7	181	
-7	-32	17	10	9	31	53	38	2	52	8	181	2	-2	26	11	12	10	18	6	38	54	6	181	
28	-13	29	30	3	31	32	20	-39	53	7	181	1	27	31	-4995	3006	2025	-29	16	39	55	5	181	
12	53	11	10	37	9	8	-39	20	54	6	181	0	-7	-32	5019	-2982	-2001	31	53	40	56	4	181	
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30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										181	30	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/ ©IJT										181
	28	53	21	-65	22	23	29	-3	23	51	-1	181		-19	131	39	30	6	20	25	44	-145	63	-13	181
	-26	16	12	15	18	19	57	37	-17	3023	-2973	181		-12	28	54	21	-65	22	23	29	31	54	-4	181
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	27	14	11	12	25	18	4	-122	142	-3176	3226	181		-15	26	15	30	16	2	17	6	34	-237	287	181
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	7	-22	10	96	9	8	3	41	-21	55	-5	181		-17	24	13	20	17	14	16	8	36	58	-8	181
	30	6	33	34	-78	20	25	10	51	56	-6	181		-18	3	-22	11	97	10	9	4	37	59	-9	181
	-10	14	-13	-14	98	0	-5	51	10	57	-7	181		255	-112	-20	-11	13	-1	-6	-25	38	60	-10	181
	3006	44	45	46	-5087	47	2025	49	50	25	-69	181		46	47	48	3006	-5103	2025	51	52	53	25	-69	181
	-2956	6	5	4	5137	3	-1975	1	0	-69	25	181		4	3	2	-2956	5153	-1975	-1	-2	-3	-69	25	181
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4 Author’s Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author’s contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** please see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers, <https://inderjtaneja.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

References

- [1] **A. de Winkel**, The magic Encyclopedia, <http://home.wanadoo.nl/aaledewinkel/Encyclopedia/index.html>
- [2] **C. Boyer**, Multimagic Squares and Cubes, <http://www.multimagie.com>
- [3] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/Download.html>
- [4] **F. Gaspalou**, “Magic Squares” <http://www.gaspalou.fr/magic-squares/>
- [5] **W. Trump**, <http://www.trump.de/magic-squares>
- [6] **H. White**, Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/MagicSquares.html>
- [7] **W.S. Andrews**, Magic squares and Cubes, Dover Publications, New York

- [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.
- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Nested Magic Squares With Perfect Square Sums, Pythagorean Triples, and Borders Differences, **Zenodo**, June 14, 2019, pp. 1-59, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3246586>.
- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Symmetric Properties of Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, June 29, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3262170>.
- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, General Sum Symmetric and Positive Entries Nested Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, July 04, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3268877>.
- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered Magic Squares With Order Square Magic Sums, **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp. 1-26, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613690>.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2020. **Zenodo**, January 20, 2020, pp.1-25. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3613698>.
- [19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Fractional and Decimal Type Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2021, **Zenodo**, December 16, 2020, pp. 1-33, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4327333>.
- [20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic Squares With Magic Sum 2022, **Zenodo**, December 28, 2021, pp. 1-38, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5807789>
- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.

- [22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.
- [23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>.
- [24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. **Zenodo**, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.
- [25] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Double digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 108, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8230214>.
- [26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, May 23, 2023, pp. 1-23, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960679>.
- [27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-71, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8000467>.
- [28] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 81, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8231157>.
- [29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Reflexive Year 25: Mathematics of 25 and 2025 in Numbers and Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, December 20, 2024, pp. 1-94, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14533193>.
- [30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Numbers and Magic Squares Representations of Hardy-Ramanujan Number-1729, **Zenodo**, December 20, 2024, pp. 1-127, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14538297>.
- [31] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Orders 3 to 7 Representing Dates and Days of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 04, 2025, pp. 1-474, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15338142>.
- [32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 8 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 04, 2025, pp. 1-134, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15338246>.
- [33] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 9 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 09, 2025, pp. 1-132, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15375349>.
- [34] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 10 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, May 21, 2025, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15481738>.
- [35] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares of Order 11 Representing Days and Dates of the Year 2025, **Zenodo**, June 02, 2025, pp. 1-111, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15576562>.